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APPLICATION OF SEMI-SUPERVISED MEAN TEACHER TO ROCK IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Accurate segmentation of rock images is crucial for studying the internal structure and properties of rocks. To address the issue of requiring a large number of labeled images for model training in traditional image segmentation methods, this paper proposes an improved semi-supervised Mean Teacher algorithm based on ResNet34-UNet. This method achieves relatively accurate rock image segmentation using only a small amount of labeled data. Initially, we use ResNet34-UNet as the base model to create Student Model and Teacher Model with identical structures. Then, we introduce self-attention mechanism into the semi-supervised Mean Teacher algorithm to further enhance its performance in rock image segmentation. Finally, by comparing the performance of supervised and semi-supervised Mean Teacher algorithms on image segmentation tasks, we validate the effectiveness of semi-supervised learning in rock image segmentation.

Keywords: Image segmentation; ResNet; Rock image; Self-attention; Semi-supervised learning; Unet.

INTRODUCTION

Rock images are a vital source of geological data that are essential for understanding the composition and characteristics of rocks. In contrast to natural photographs, accurate rock image segmentation typically depends on experts annotating the images based on their own experience, which makes obtaining large-scale labeled datasets a difficult and time-consuming operation. The topic of image segmentation has seen a lot of activity and applications recently (Cai *et al.* (2024); Huang *et al.* (2024); Lou *et al.* (2024); Liu *et al.* (2024); Mazher *et al.* (2024); Liu *et al.* (2023); Zhao *et al.* (2024)). The work of rock segmentation can be completed more precisely by combining image processing and rock image recognition technologies. This has significant practical implications for geological research and resource optimization.

The application of picture segmentation in petrology has grown with the swift advancement of deep learning and computer vision technology. While segmentation can be achieved to some extent using traditional pixel-based techniques like threshold segmentation, region-growing, and edge detection, handling complicated rock textures and structures can frequently be challenging. In the field of image segmentation, deep learning-based techniques like U-Net (Ronneberger *et al.* (2015)), SegNet (Badrinarayanan *et al.* (2017)), and Mask R-CNN (Murray *et al.* (2021)) have made impressive strides.

These techniques are well-suited for challenging feature extraction and segmentation tasks in rock images and can better capture the semantic information of the image.

Enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of segmentation can be achieved by processing the complex features of rock images more efficiently through the use of deep learning methods, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNN) (Cao *et al.* (2022); Chen *et al.* (2024); Niu *et al.* (2020); Roslin *et al.* (2023)). Researchers are able to do automatic rock images segmentation by building suitable neural network topologies and optimization algorithms. This lessens the need for manual annotation by experts and expedites data processing and analysis.

RockSeg network combining CNN and Transformer methods (Fan *et al.* (2023)) is proposed to effectively segment rock images in deep space environments; an automatic segmentation method combining texture analysis and deep learning is proposed (Manzoor *et al.* (2023)) in the task of segmenting the porosity and mineral composition of digital rock images. An algorithm combining local adaptive thresholding and an improved watershed transform (Dong and Jiang (2013)) was used in the rock image segmentation task. This algorithm solves the incorrect segmentation problem caused by sticking, stacking, and edge blurring in the blasting rock images more quickly and accurately. Xia Lin *et al.* also proposed an algorithm for classifying microscopic images of rock sheets based on the deep residual

contraction network and the attention mechanism (Zhang *et al.* (2023)), which is one of several techniques to improve the accuracy of segmentation of rock images.

However, in order to train rock images segmentation models, these approaches typically require a big amount of labeled data, which will take a lot of time and labor and may restrict the algorithm use in practical situations. Semi-supervised learning methods prove to be a useful substitute in resolving this issue. This research is motivated by the fact that semi-supervised learning algorithms may learn features from a significant amount of unlabeled image data, reducing the demand for labeled data and improving model performance and generalization ability.

Semi-supervised image segmentation is one of the important methods for segmenting images, which can effectively use limited labeled data to improve the performance and generalization ability of the model by combining labeled and unlabeled data. In complex scenarios such as rock images, semi-supervised learning methods provide new ideas and solutions to improve model performance and reduce the demand for labeled data, such as a method combining simple linear iterative clustering algorithm (SLIC) and semi-supervised self-training has been proposed (Liu and Lv (2023)) for automated segmentation and component recognition of rock images, and an improved semi-supervised SVM-FCM based on chaotic algorithm (CSVM-CMF) was proposed (Liang and zou (2020))for segmentation of pores and rocks. Semi-supervised learning techniques offer fresh ideas and solutions to improve the model performance and reduce the demand for labeled data in complex scenarios like rock images. In addition, semi-supervised learning has also shown potential and importance in medical image analysis (Weng *et al.* (2024)) disease diagnosis (Han *et al.* (2024);Sinha *et al.* (2023)), etc. such as in the segmentation of liver images in clinical diagnosis (Huang *et al.* (2024)) and the segmentation of skin lesions (Zhang *et al.* (2022)), which further validate the value and advantages of semi-supervised image segmentation in a variety of complex scenarios, and provide useful references and lessons for future image segmentation research and applications.

Therefore, this paper proposes an improved Mean Teacher algorithm based on Resnet34-UNet for rock segmentation. By using a significant amount of unlabeled data for feature learning, the approach lessens the reliance on labeled data and enhances the robustness and accuracy of segmenting rock

images. Furthermore, this research introduces a self-attention mechanism that helps the model better focus on the significance of various parts in the image, Compared to traditional semi-supervised learning methods, our algorithm demonstrates higher robustness and accuracy in dealing with complex textures of rocks. In particular, with limited labeled samples, by introducing a self-attention mechanism, the model better focuses on the importance of different regions in the image and improves the ability to capture detailed information such as rock structure and texture. We anticipate that our work will advance the development and use of rock images segmentation, lead to new discoveries, and advance related fields' practice and research.

RELATED WORKS

RESNET34-UNET

A neural network model called ResNet34-Unet combines the architectures of Unet and ResNet34 to perform image segmentation tasks. In this model, Unet serves as the decoder component, producing the segmentation results of the picture, and ResNet34 serves as the encoder component, extracting the characteristics of the image. ResNet34-Unet is able to provide precise picture segmentation and feature extraction by fusing the potent feature extraction capabilities of ResNet34 with the segmentation capabilities of Unet.

Fig. 1. Residual structure

Among the ResNet family, ResNet34 is a traditional deep residual network model with a stronger feature extraction capacity and a deeper network structure. The model utilizes residual structure, as shown in Fig. 1, which through a shortcut connection, the input signal is directly added to the

output signal, so as to realize the identity mapping, solve the problem of gradient disappearance and gradient explosion in the training process, and improve the training efficiency of the deep network. ResNet34 extends the network depth while preserving model performance in contrast to the shallower network structure, which allows it to more effectively capture the image's semantic content and abstract properties.

The Unet structure has jump connections and an upsampling layer in addition to acting as a decoder. By using the jump connection to retain more detailed information, the decoder improves the accuracy of the segmentation process by reducing the feature maps extracted by the encoder to a segmentation result of the same size as the input image through upsampling.

In summary, ResNet34-Unet integrates the benefits of both ResNet34 and Unet, demonstrates strong performance in image segmentation assignments, and can successfully achieve precise segmentation and feature extraction of rock images.

MEAN TEACHER ALGORITHM

In order to enhance the model performance and capacity for generalization, semi-supervised learning combines a large number of unlabeled examples with a limited number of labeled samples. Semi-supervised learning has a larger range of application scenarios than supervised learning because it is more difficult to gather huge amounts of labeled data in real-world scenarios. Conversely, semi-supervised learning can train a model with a similar level of accuracy to a supervised model by combining a big amount of unlabeled data with a little amount of labeled data. Semi-supervised learning methods are mainly classified into two categories: consistent regularization method and proxy labeling.

In this paper, the Mean Teacher algorithm based on consistent regularization (Tarvainen and Valpola (2017)) is used to segment rock images with the flow chart shown in Fig. 2, the whole algorithm consists of two networks, teacher network and student network, in which the student network updates the parameters through gradient descent, and the teacher network updates the parameters through the student network parameters. The algorithm mainly includes the following five steps:

- (1) Set up the Teacher networks G_t and Student networks G_s , which often share the same network topology.
- (2) Load the labels training datasets $D_l = (x_i^l, y_i^l)_{i=1}^N$ and the unlabeled training dataset $D_u = (x_i^u)_{i=1}^M$, where x_i^l is the labeled image, y_i^l is the corresponding label,

x_i^u is the unlabeled image, N is the number of labeled samples, and M is the number of unlabeled samples.

- (3) Describe the loss function $L_{total} = L_{labeled} + \omega * L_{unlabeled}$, where ω is a hyperparameter that weighs the two losses.

- (4) Training loop, each time through the training process:

- a. Draw a batch of data from the labeled training dataset.

- b. Draw a batch of data from the unlabeled training dataset.

- c. Use the Student network G_s to forward propagate the labeled data and compute the loss $L_{labeled}$.

- d. Use the Teacher network G_t to forward propagate the unlabeled data and compute the loss $L_{unlabeled}$.

- e. Calculate the total loss $L_{total} = L_{labeled} + \omega * L_{unlabeled}$, use backpropagation to update the network's parameters, and optimize the total loss.

- f. Use the Exponential Moving Average (EMA) to update the teacher network parameters G_t , the exponential moving average update formula is $\theta_t = \alpha \theta_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) \theta_t$, where θ_t is the parameter value following the t th update, θ_{t-1} is the parameter value following the last update, and α is the attenuation coefficient of the exponential moving average. Typically, α takes a value between 0 and 1, which is used to control the amount of influence that the historical parameter values have on the current parameter update, which is chosen as $\alpha = 0.999$ in this paper.

- (5) Validate the model performance using the validation set and evaluate the generalization ability of the model.

- (6) Adjust hyperparameters

such as learning rate, etc. to optimize model performance. In order to guarantee that the model has good initial performance and stability, we combine the Mean Teacher algorithm on the base model for model training in this paper. We also use the pre-training parameters of the base model to investigate in detail the potential role of semi-supervised learning in rock images segmentation and to assess the effects of various training strategies on the model performance. We are dedicated to enhancing the precision and efficacy of rock images segmentation through our research technique, offering helpful references and perspectives for scholarly studies and real-world applications in this domain.

SELF-ATTENTION MECHANISM

The Self-Attention mechanism (Vaswani *et al.* (2017)) is an attention mechanism used to compute the relationship between elements in a sequence. The algorithm generates attention weights by calculating

Fig. 2. Mean Teacher training method diagram

the similarity between the input features, thus improving the model attention to features at different spatial locations. In particular, a self-attention function $Attention(Q, K, V)$ is constructed, in which Q stands for the query, K for the key, and V for the value.

Fig. 3. Self-attention mechanism schematic diagram

The schematic of the self-attention mechanism is shown in Fig. 3, this mechanism obtains the attention weight α by calculating the similarity between the query and the key. Afterwards, the weighted feature representation is obtained by applying the attention weight to the value V . The following is the calculation formula

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V, \quad (1)$$

where d is the vector dimension.

This procedure can enhance the model depiction of spatial location attributes and efficiently capture the connections among various places.

THE METHOD OF IMPROVED SEMI-SUPERVISED MEAN TEACHER

SELF-ATTENTION ENHANCED MEAN TEACHER MODULE

The Mean Teacher algorithm has been widely used in semi-supervised learning tasks, and its core idea is to improve model performance by integrating labeled and unlabeled data. To further enhance the model ability to understand the global context, we propose the method of integrating self-attention in the Mean Teacher algorithm (MTSA). By introducing the self-attention module, we enable the model to adaptively focus on important regions in the input data, thus improving its performance in image classification tasks. The network structure is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Specifically, we build on the Mean Teacher algorithm by embedding the self-attention module after the third and fourth layers of the downsampling phase of the ResNet34-Unet network. This module allows the network to automatically learn and pay attention to the dependencies between different regions of the input data while extracting features, allowing the model to better capture global contextual information during feature extraction and dynamically adjust its

Fig. 4. MTSA network structure

attention during training, thus improving the accuracy of image segmentation.

EVALUATING INDICATOR

In machine learning tasks, evaluation metrics are one of the most important criteria for assessing the performance of a model. By measuring a model performance on a particular job, evaluation metrics allow us to compare the performance of various models. Confusion matrix is a commonly used tool for evaluating the performance of a classification model, it compares the predicted results of the model with the true labels and shows how the model classifies on different categories. In the rock image segmentation task, we will use the confusion matrix Table 1 to help understand the classification results of the model and compute the evaluation metrics to evaluate the model performance.

Table 1. Confusion matrix.

	Predicted negative	Predicted positive
Actual negative	TN	FP
Actual positive	FN	TP

In this paper, we will use the mIoU (Mean Intersection over Union) value as the only evaluation metric to evaluate the performance of the model in the rock image segmentation task. mIoU value is a commonly used evaluation metric for semantic segmentation tasks, which calculates the ratio of the intersection and concatenation between the predicted segmentation results and the real segmentation results, which reflects the model segmentation accuracy for different categories. accuracy, the mIoU value is calculated as follows:

$$Miou = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

THE RESULTS OF EXPERIMENT

DATASET AND HYPERPARAMETERS

The rock images dataset used in this paper consists of 430 unlabeled and 50 labeled rock images. To ensure the diversity and representativeness of the experiment, these rock images feature a variety of rock sample kinds and shapes.

In order to guarantee the fairness and practicability of the studies, the models in the experiments all use the same parameters and experimental environment configurations, which include the method of terminating the training iterations, the optimizer, the learning rate, the size of the batch size, and the selection of the loss function, etc, and the specific parameters are listed in the Table 2:

Table 2. Training parameter settings.

Parameter name	Parameter setting
Accuracy degradation limits	5
Categorical Loss Function	Cross Entropy Loss
Consistency Loss Function	Mean Square Error Loss
Optimizer	SGD
Learning rate	0.01
Batch_size	4

In the semi-supervised control experiments, the overall size of batch_size is set to 4, but it should be noted that each batch actually contains 22 image samples. Specifically, each batch contains 2 labeled samples and the corresponding 20 unlabeled samples to maintain a ratio of labeled to unlabeled data of 1:10. This setting helps to efficiently utilize the unlabeled data in the semi-supervised learning task and improve the model performance.

THE RESULTS OF RESNET34-UNET MODEL

When training the ResNet34-Unet model using a fully supervised approach, the best mIoU value we obtained on the data validation set was 0.7687. As can be observed from the Fig. 5, the variation of mIoU values during fully supervised training shows a relatively smooth upward trend in the training set, whereas the mIoU in the test set varies more drastically, which suggests that the model performance is limited when trained with only a small amount of This indicates that the performance of the model is limited when it is trained with only a small amount of labeled data, and it cannot fully capture the complex features of the data to realize its potential.

Fig. 5. Variation in mIoU during Supervision training

THE RESULTS OF MEAN TEACHER

When the model is trained by the Mean Teacher method, the change of mIoU value is not stable on the test set, which may indicate that the Mean Teacher method may have encountered training difficulties or challenges in the model generalization ability at some stages, and this phenomenon may originate from the training mechanism of the Mean Teacher method, which introduces supervised signals from unlabeled data, resulting in the the model to suffer from more data interference during the learning process, which in turn leads to fluctuations in performance performance. In this paper, the weights of the unsupervised loss function are adjusted by combining the grid search method to further optimize the model performance and reduce the impact of performance fluctuations, and the optimal parameters are finally determined as $\omega = 0.6$.

As of right now, the model best mIoU value on the data validation set is 0.8237. Compared to the supervised, the Mean Teacher method shows some performance enhancement throughout the training phase, according to the findings of the observed experiments in Fig. 6. All things considered,

the Mean Teacher approach has to contend with training instability in addition to performance gains, which offers helpful information for additional study and method optimization. It enhances the model performance and capacity for generalization and fosters the growth of the semi-supervised learning field by thoroughly examining the Mean Teacher method’s optimization techniques and performance features in many contexts.

Fig. 6. Variation in mIoU during Semi-supervision training

The advantage of Mean Teacher may lie in its ability to utilize unlabeled data for training, thus improving the model ability to learn data features and hence performance performance. This semi-supervised learning approach helps to address the problem of costly data labeling while improving model performance and generalization.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF MEAN TEACHER INCORPORATING SELF-ATTENTION MECHANISMS

Although Mean Teacher has made some progress in improving the model performance, there is still room for improvement in dealing with data labeling noise and model instability, and the ability to capture complex features still needs to be improved, in order to further improve the model performance, we introduce a self-attention mechanism based on Mean Teacher algorithm, which enhances the model’s ability to capture global dependencies. In order to further improve the performance of the model, we introduce the self-attention mechanism based on Mean Teacher algorithm to enhance the model ability to capture global dependencies. After experimental validation, we observe that after adding the self-attention mechanism, the optimal mIoU value of the model is further improved to 0.8792, which is higher than that of the Mean Teacher algorithm only. This indicates that the introduction of the self-attention

mechanism effectively enhances the model attention to spatial location features, which further improves the model performance in the image segmentation task.

Fig. 7. Variation in mIoU during Mean Teacher Incorporating Self-Attention Mechanisms training

According to Fig. 7 analyzing the experimental results comprehensively, we can find that although Mean Teacher has achieved some success in semi-supervised learning, it still has deficiencies in dealing with data labeling noise and model instability. The introduction of the self-attention mechanism can effectively improve the performance of the ResNet34-Unet model in the image segmentation task, so that it can better capture the complex features of the data and thus achieve better segmentation results. This experimental result provides a useful reference and inspiration for further research and application of the self-attention mechanism in the field of image segmentation.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

In the comparative analysis section, we compare the performance of three different models in the image segmentation task, namely ResNet34, Mean Teacher and Meanteacher+attention models. The Table 3 shows their mIoU values on the training and test sets:

Table 3. Performance of different models.

Model	Miou_train	Miou_test
ResNet34-Unet	0.7906	0.7687
Mean Teacher	0.8609	0.8237
Meanteacher+attention	0.9408	0.8792

From the Table 3, it can be seen that the mIoU value of Mean Teacher model is significantly improved on both the training and test sets compared to the model ResNet34-Unet. On the training set, the mIoU value of the Mean Teacher model reaches 0.8609, which is 0.0703 higher than that of ResNet34-Unet, and on the test set, the mIoU value reaches 0.8237, which is 0.055 higher than that of ResNet34-Unet,

which suggests that the semi-supervised learning method Mean Teacher achieves better results in the image segmentation task and can effectively improve the performance of the model.

Further, the performance of the Mean Teacher model is further improved on the training and test sets by introducing the self-attention mechanism based on the Mean Teacher model. In the training set, the mIoU value reaches 0.9408, which is 0.0799 higher than that of the Mean Teacher model, and in the test set, the mIoU value reaches 0.8792, which is 0.0555 higher than that of the Mean Teacher model, indicating that the introduction of the self-attention mechanism effectively enhances the model focus on spatial location features, which further enhances the model performance in the image segmentation task. A comparison of the results of the rock image samples segmented under different methods is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Test samples and model outputs for the rock dataset, (a) test sample images, (b) test sample labels, (c) graph of threshold segmentation results, (d) graph of segmentation results for the supervised ResNet34-Unet model, (e) graph of segmentation results for Mean Teacher, and (f) graph of segmentation results for Meanteacher+Self attention.

In summary, the Mean Teacher Incorporating Self-Attention Mechanisms model achieves the best performance in this study, with a mIoU value of 0.8792 on the test set, which is 0.1105 higher than the benchmark model, ResNet34. This further validates the effectiveness of the self-attention mechanism in the image segmentation task and provides strong support for the model performance improvement.

CONCLUSION

The advantage of the semi-supervised Mean Teacher approach is its ability to utilize unlabeled data for training, which improves the model ability to learn the features of the data, and thus improves the performance performance. Although this method helps to solve the problem of high cost of data labeling, but it is still unavoidable that the Mean Teacher approach also faces the challenge of unstable training on the validation set. The Mean Teacher model with the introduction of the self-attention mechanism further improves the performance of the image segmentation task. The self-attention mechanism can effectively capture the complex features of the data and enhance the model attention to the spatial location features, which makes the model more accurate and stable in handling the image segmentation task. However, the method still faces the challenge of unstable training, which leads to fluctuations in model performance or difficulty in convergence.

To further improve the performance and stability of the model, future research can focus on the following aspects: first, exploring more stable training strategies, such as introducing more effective loss function design, optimizer selection, or learning rate adjustment methods, in order to improve the stability of the model performance on the validation set. Then, to address the problem that the pseudo-labels generated in the Mean Teacher algorithm may have certain noise and inaccuracy, we explore the improvement of the pseudo-label generation strategy and the introduction of a more accurate and reliable pseudo-label generation method. By improving the training strategy of the algorithm and introducing different pseudo-label generation methods to improve its accuracy, it is expected to achieve more significant performance enhancement and stability improvement in image segmentation tasks in the future.

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IMAGE EXPERIENCE PREDICTION FOR HISTORIC DISTRICTS USING A CNN-TRANSFORMER FUSION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses fundamental challenges in historic district planning and design, specifically incorporating the emotional value of streetscape images into the design process. A deep learning-based sentiment analysis system was developed, utilising a convolution neural network (CNN) and transformer models to assess emotional tendencies and temporal states within images. The system employs a multi-view feature extraction framework, integrating VGG, ResNet CNNs, and the Swin Transformer model, resulting in a novel feature matrix. The attention mechanism and transfer learning strategy significantly enhance model accuracy in label recognition and classification. The primary contribution of this study is developing a novel multimodal fusion model, which markedly improves sentiment recognition accuracy and practical applicability. The application of this system to the Jiangnan Historic District underscores the enhanced appeal through the integration of emotional value. By identifying emotional tendencies in streetscape images, designers can make better-informed decisions that foster positive experiences. This research innovatively applies sentiment analysis to historic district design, highlighting the potential of the system to guide culturally sensitive and engaging urban planning. Our analysis of images from 12 Jiangnan historic districts demonstrated the efficiency of the system in aligning images with existing imaging libraries, offering valuable references and feedback. The results underscore the practical potential of deep learning in visual sentiment analysis and emphasize the significance of emotional value in enhancing experiences in historic districts. This study provides new insights and methodological support for planning and designing such areas.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN); Evaluation System; Historic Districts; Sentiment Analysis; Transformer Model.

INTRODUCTION

Over time, historic districts have increasingly assumed multifaceted roles in urban development. These districts, as custodians of urban culture, preserve rich historical narratives and significantly influence the emotional experiences of residents and visitors.

Consequently, the strategies employed in their design and preservation are pivotal for safeguarding the historical heritage and cultural dynamism of a city.

PROBLEM ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT SITUATION OF HISTORIC DISTRICTS

The rejuvenation of historic districts in Jiangnan has spanned over four decades, beginning with the regeneration of Tunxi Old Street in 1983. Although this process

has led to some physical environmental improvement, the prevailing urban regeneration model has introduced numerous issues.

DAMAGE TO SPATIAL TEXTURE

Driven by traditional urban renewal thinking, Jiangnan historic districts have adopted measures such as restoring old buildings, widening streets, opening blocked alleys, and improving public facilities. Consequently, these transformations extend beyond restoration, incorporating diverse new building materials and distinctive decorative elements, evolving into 'historic streets' that blend nostalgic charm with modern aesthetics. This synthesis caters to the refined tastes and consumption preferences of the upper class, reflecting a fusion of heritage preservation and contemporary luxury (Sanchez, 2023). While these new buildings satisfy

aesthetic tastes, they have marred the traditional look of these historic districts. Historic districts are envisioned as multifunctional spaces imbued with vibrancy, harmonising residents' living, production, interaction, and leisure activities. Nevertheless, as urbanisation accelerates, urban land resources have grown increasingly scarce (Giglio *et al.*, 2019), leading to a rapid widening of gaps in land rents, drastically affecting their original community functions and patterns of interpersonal interactions (Zhao *et al.*, 2018).

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to develop a sophisticated image sentiment analysis system using deep learning techniques to balance historic district preservation with modern urban development. By leveraging a hybrid model of CNNs and transformers, it seeks to enhance urban planners' and designers' understanding of public emotional responses, fostering empathy and cultural sensitivity in their design choices. This approach provides robust data support for preservation and renewal initiatives, offering real-time feedback and facilitating informed, historically sensitive urban regeneration strategies.

To balance historic preservation with urban development, this study uses both quantitative and qualitative measures to evaluate key structural variables: architectural integrity, streetscape cohesion, and pedestrian density. Quantitative scoring assesses the alignment of each variable with traditional or modern design requirements. Complementary qualitative insights from surveys capture local residents' and visitors' emotional responses to specific district changes. These approaches collectively provide a structured framework to determine the efficacy of design interventions in balancing cultural heritage with contemporary utility.

Building on this framework, the study utilises a deep learning model to categorise streetscape visual elements as positive or negative, measuring both sentiment intensity and diversity. By associating these emotional responses with specific design features—such as architectural details or vegetation—the model identifies elements that elicit favourable reactions. These insights are then translated into actionable design recommendations, enabling planners to refine historic district designs to better align with public sentiment, thereby enhancing engagement and positive emotional responses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sentiment analysis techniques traditionally applied to text have expanded to image and video analyses to explore cross-modal sentiment recognition. Research using similarity techniques for sentiment detection has

shown promising results in recognising and analysing emotions in digital texts (Mozafari and Tahayori, 2019, Pratibha *et al.*, 2022). The application of CNN-Bi-LSTM models incorporating attention mechanisms in electroencephalogram (EEG)-based emotion recognition has validated these methods' maturity and efficacy (Huang *et al.*, 2023). In image sentiment analysis, numerous studies have utilised target detection algorithms to identify salient regions within images. Sentiment analysis is then conducted on both the salient target and original image separately using VGGNet, enhancing prediction accuracy through result fusion (Roshan *et al.*, 2024, Wu *et al.*, 2020). An RGBT (visible light and infrared) object tracking method based on multimodal hierarchical relationship modelling integrates multiple Transformer encoders and includes a dynamic component feature fusion module, significantly enhancing multimodal image feature aggregation and recognition accuracy, enabling dynamic importance assessment and contextual adaptation of each modality (Yao *et al.*, 2024). A deep learning ensemble model for eye disease detection combines multi-layer CNN architectures such as VGG16, DenseNet201, and ResNet50, showing superior performance in medical image classification tasks (Jeny *et al.*, 2023).

Experimental findings indicate that this fusion-based training approach outperforms traditional methods. Some studies have integrated visual self-attention mechanisms into CNN emotion classification frameworks, utilising salient targets in images as prior knowledge to optimise the visual attention learning area and address the limitations of self-attention mechanism in capturing emotional features (Song *et al.*, 2018, Thilagavathy *et al.*, 2023). Further innovations include an image sentiment analysis strategy that merges overall and local region embeddings for object localisation, employing deep neural networks to capture the sentiment attributes of localised regions, followed by classifiers for sentiment prediction (Cai *et al.*, 2019, Gupta *et al.*, 2023). Advances in CNNs enhanced with feature pyramids have facilitated multi-scale salient target emotion feature extraction by integrating saliency targets, facial recognition, and overall image analysis (Miao *et al.*, 2021). Sentiment information in images, often represented as high-level visual feature abstractions, is more readily interpreted through the subjects or attributes within the images (Xu *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, CNNs have transitioned from image subject recognition to sentiment analysis, enhancing their adaptability and accuracy in contexts rich with emotional and semantic content (Acheampong *et al.*, 2020, Zhang *et al.*, 2017).

Sentiment analysis of multimodal data utilises the integration of information from various modalities through associative and complementary methods to enhance sentiment classification (Chalasanani *et al.*, 2020, Mahima *et al.*, 2021). Current fusion techniques for multimodal data are categorised into three types (Baltrušaitis *et al.*, 2018): feature-level (Poria *et al.*, 2016, Tao *et al.*, 2020), decision-level (Cao *et al.*, 2016, Yuqing *et al.*, 2019), and hybrid (Huang *et al.*, 2019, Truong and Lauw, 2019, Zhao *et al.*, 2019). Feature-level fusion combines features from different modalities early in the processing stage, decision-level fusion aggregates outcomes at the output stage, and hybrid fusion merges both to maximise information utilisation, with deep multimodal attention fusion frameworks exploring associations between images and text. For instance, the Deep Multimodal Attention Fusion (DMAF) framework (Huang *et al.*, 2019, Kumar *et al.*, 2021, You *et al.*, 2016b) has surpassed the Cross-modal Consistency Regression (CCR) model across several datasets. The CCR model enhanced with visual attention (CCR-V) (You *et al.*, 2017), the tree-structured Long Short-term Memory (LSTM) with visual attention (T-LSTM-E) (You *et al.*, 2016a), and the Tensor Fusion Network (TFN) model (Zadeh *et al.*, 2017) exemplify cutting-edge advancements in graphic fusion research. In computer vision, although CNNs remain dominant, there is increasing interest in integrating CNNs with self-attention mechanisms to develop novel model architectures. For instance, a standard transformer applied to image processing has attained moderate accuracy on medium-sized datasets compared to the traditional ResNet architecture. However, on larger datasets, the Vision Transformer (ViT) model (Dosovitskiy *et al.*, 2020) has achieved superior performance, equalling or surpassing state-of-the-art result in several image recognition benchmarks. These advancements underscore the significant potential of multimodal data fusion and deep learning techniques to drive further progress in sentiment analysis.

Song *et al.*, (2022) introduced a Multi-scale Fusion Network (CTMFNet), which integrates CNN and transformer mechanisms to enhance the semantic segmentation of remotely sensed urban scenes. This network leverages local and global contextual information through a multilayer densely connected network decoder, demonstrating superior accuracy over existing methods in practical scenarios. Notably, deep learning techniques, particularly CNNs and their integration with transformer models, have driven significant advancements in image classification, segmentation, and recognition (Espinoza *et al.*, 2023, Jayaswal *et al.*, 2024). A comprehensive review has highlighted these

developments and the persisting challenges in the field, indicating a critical need for innovative deep models and computational systems to interpret image content more efficiently (Jiao and Zhao, 2019). In design evaluation, image classification is employed to assess compliance and aesthetic quality (Nasution *et al.*, 2023). Research into the aesthetic attributes of images across mixed multi-attribute datasets has advanced methodologies for assessing aesthetic quality (Bhushanam, 2023, Jin *et al.*, 2023, Jin *et al.*, 2019). Recent studies examining visual assessments of historic districts have evolved from traditional analyses of architectural styles and spatial layouts to modern approaches incorporating public participation and social dynamics (Middel *et al.*, 2019). By analysing visitor photography and perceptions, this research underscores the importance of preserving the authenticity and visual integrity of these areas (Naoi *et al.*, 2011).

This literature review highlights notable achievements in the utilisation of deep learning for image processing, advancements in sentiment analysis techniques, and real-world applications of image classification in design assessment.

These studies have enriched our understanding of visual assessment methodologies and exemplified the capabilities of deep learning models. Additionally, they demonstrate the extensive potential of sentiment analysis techniques in enhancing image analysis.

The current literature on sentiment analysis exhibits several limitations: it predominantly focuses on text-based methods, with limited incorporation of image-based analysis, thereby restricting comprehensive emotional representation across multimodal scenes. Studies investigating image learning in various historic district settings are also scarce, reducing the diversity of visual data utilised for model training and impacting adaptability. Traditional CNNs often struggle to manage complex visual contexts, and many models focus on localised features rather than adopting a holistic, integrated approach, thereby diminishing sentiment recognition accuracy. While sentiment analysis shows potential in design, practical applications in historic district contexts remain rare, leading to limited real-world validation. Furthermore, models trained on small, homogeneous datasets frequently fail to generalise across diverse historic settings, and temporal or spatial factors—such as time of day or seasonal variations—are often overlooked, restricting broader applicability. Future research should prioritise integrating multimodal data, diversifying visual data sources, enhancing model adaptability, and validating applications across diverse design contexts to better support sentiment analysis in historic districts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, data were collected through field photography and Web access, resulting in a comprehensive dataset of 3,295 images related to historic districts (Shi *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, subjective evaluations of various

street photographs from 12 historic districts (Table 1), encapsulating both positive and negative emotions, were conducted through interviews with 426 tourists. Each image in the dataset was meticulously labelled to facilitate detailed analysis.

Table 1: Summary of the results of information on 12 popular historic districts in Jiangnan. Street-level images of these districts were acquired for the field survey.

Serial num.	Block (between streets)	Spatial texture	District atmosphere
1	Huangshan Tunxi Old Street	The fishbone pattern is complete, featuring numerous Huizhou-style buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys feature many original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets and hardware shops, which contribute to a strong sense of local life. Conversely, the main street is dominated by tourists, hotels, commercial establishments, creating a distinctly commercial environment.
2	Suzhou Pingjiang Road Districts	The checkerboard pattern is complete, featuring numerous Jiangnan buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys are characterised by numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, creating a strong sense of local life. In contrast, the main street is frequented by many tourists and features an abundance of cafes, hotels, and shops, fostering a distinctly commercial environment.
3	Suzhou Shantang Old Street	The one-river-and-two-streets pattern is complete, featuring numerous Jiangnan buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys host numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, creating a strong sense of local life. Conversely, the main street is frequented by tourists and features an abundance of cafes, hotels, and shops, creating a distinctly commercial environment.
4	Shaoxing Houத்துyniau Historic Quarter	The grid pattern is complete, featuring numerous Huizhou-style buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys feature numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, contributing to a strong sense of local life. In contrast, there are few tourists, cafes, hotels, and shops, resulting in a weak commercial atmosphere.
5	Lanxi Tianfu Mountain Districts	The grid pattern is complete, featuring numerous Huizhou-style buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys are characterised by numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, creating a strong sense of local life. Conversely, there are few tourists, cafes, hotels, and shops, resulting in a weak commercial atmosphere.
6	Hangzhou Nan Song Royal Street	The fishbone pattern is complete, integrating Jiangnan and Chinese–Western architecture, characterised by high spatial integration, unobstructed streets and lanes with good accessibility.	The branch alleys host numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, fostering a strong sense of local life. The area attracts numerous tourists and is populated with cafes, express hotels, speciality lodgings, and shops, reflecting a strong commercial presence.
7	Shanghai Tianzifang	The field pattern is complete, featuring numerous Shikumen buildings, high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and unobstructed streets and lanes with good accessibility.	The district exhibit sparse original residents, few old shops, a lack of daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets. This contributes to a weak sense of local life. In contrast, there are more tourists, cafes, hotels, and shops, creating a strong commercial atmosphere.
8	Shanghai Xintiandi (shopping, eating, and entertainment district of Shanghai)	The grid pattern is complete, featuring numerous Shikumen buildings, high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The area has few original residents, fewer old shops, and lacks daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops and night markets, leading to a weak sense of local life. Conversely, it attracts numerous tourists and features many cafes, hotels, and shops, resulting in a strong commercial atmosphere.
9	Hangzhou Qiaoxi Districts	The river–street–alley pattern is complete, incorporating numerous Jiangnan buildings, high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The branch alleys host numerous original residents, old shops, teahouses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, fostering a strong sense of local life. Additionally, there are many tourists, hotels, and shops, contributing to a strong commercial atmosphere.

10	Hangzhou Wuhe Historic District	The street–river–street pattern is complete, featuring numerous Huizhou-style buildings, high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The area hosts numerous original residents, old shops, tea-houses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, fostering a strong sense of local life. Conversely, the presence of few tourists, few cafes, hotels, and shops, contributes to a weak commercial atmosphere.
11	Shaoxing Cangqiao Zhijie	Fishbone layout is well-defined, featuring numerous Huizhou-style buildings, high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	The area hosts numerous original residents, old shops, tea-houses, and daily amenities such as vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, fostering a strong sense of local life. In contrast, there are few tourists, cafes, hotels, and shops, resulting in a weak commercial atmosphere.
12	Huangshan Liyang Old Street	The area features numerous Huizhou-style buildings with high interface similarity, high spatial integration, and smooth, accessible streets and lanes.	There are few original residents, a lack of daily habitats, such as old shops, vegetable markets, hardware shops, and night markets, and a weak sense of life. There are many tourists, cafes, hotels, and shops, and a strong commercial atmosphere.

STUDY AREA

The Jiangnan region generally encompasses areas south of the Yangtze River, primarily southern Jiangsu, northern Zhejiang, and southern Anhui in eastern China. Known for its warm and humid climate, extensive network of waterways, and fertile land, Jiangnan is renowned as the "Land of Fish and Rice." The historical districts in Jiangnan cities are intricately integrated with the natural environment, featuring interconnected waterways and lush greenery that exemplify the distinctive charm of water towns in the region. These districts preserve rich historical and cultural information, documenting the development and transformation of Jiangnan, and actively protect the ecological environment and maintain urban ecological balance. Characterised by exquisite architectural art and traditional garden landscapes, Jiangnan's historical urban districts exhibit high aesthetic value and have become significant tourist attractions, drawing numerous domestic and international visitors.

In the geographic map, the primary historical districts are marked with red dots using GIS tools (Fig. 1), predominantly concentrated in the core area of the Yangtze River Delta. This distribution underscores the unique integration of human and natural landscapes in the Jiangnan region.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experiments utilised high-performance computing resources, primarily Google Colab, for efficient model training and evaluation. Essential Python packages were imported and the dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing subsets. PyTorch DataLoader managed batch processing and data shuffling. The setup prioritised GPUs using CUDA technology, defaulting to CPUs if GPUs were unavailable, ensuring optimal resource utilisation. All models were trained and tested in a standardised environment with carefully selected

hyperparameters. The dataset was segmented into training and testing portions for performance evaluation (Garcea *et al.*, 2023, Xia *et al.*, 2017).

Fig. 1. Distribution of major historical districts in the Jiangnan Region.

Street photographs from 12 typical historic districts were selected and pre-processed through resizing and normalisation to ensure high-quality data input into the model. The dataset was split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets to optimise model training and test evaluation precision.

SENTIMENT CLASSIFICATION DATASET

Participants in the evaluation classified each photograph as either 'positive' or 'negative' based on their emotional reactions. To meet the input specifications of the model, all collected street photographs underwent initial pre-processing, including cropping and standardisation of dimensions. Each photograph was then assigned a sentiment label derived from a consensus of tourist evaluations. For label accuracy and consistency, a

photograph was included in the final dataset only if it achieved > 75% agreement in tourist ratings.

SYSTEM FRAMEWORK MODELLING INNOVATION INTEGRATION

The advanced image emotion learning and prediction system developed in this study employs a hybrid model architecture incorporating classical CNNs and a sophisticated transformer model (Khan *et al.*, 2019, Zunair and Hamza, 2020). This integrated deep learning model, named ‘Big Model’, aims to improve the accuracy of emotion classification for images of historic districts by extracting and amalgamating multiple visual features. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the model synergistically combines three state-of-the-art deep-learning architectures: VGG13, ResNet18, and Swin Transformer. Each architecture offers distinct advantages: VGG13 excels in capturing texture details, ResNet18 in discerning global structural information, and the Swin Transformer in identifying dynamic relationships (Tu *et al.*, 2022). Each base model independently extracts features from the input images, capturing diverse information from various viewpoints and scales. These extracted features are then merged through a transformer encoder layer (Shang *et al.*, 2023), optimising their complementary strengths. Finally, the integrated feature vectors are processed using a fully connected layer to classify and output the emotion category of the image. The training process for the fusion model was structured into three sequential steps: pre-processing, model fine-tuning, and end-to-end training (Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

Fig. 2. The framework of Big Model structure.

IMAGE PREDICTION MODEL

The image prediction model (Fig. 3) utilises cosine similarity to assess the resemblance between a specific query vector and a set of target vectors, aiming to identify the top k vectors that most closely match the query vector (Sejal *et al.*, 2016). The process begins by calculating similarity scores between the query vector and each vector in the target set using a cosine similarity function:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{similarity} = \cos(\theta) &= \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \|B\|} \\ &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (A_i)^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (B_i)^2}} \end{aligned}$$

These scores are sorted to identify the k vectors exhibiting the highest similarity. The model selects the k indices with the highest similarity scores and their corresponding values, efficiently identifying the vector most resembling the query vector. This method benefits applications such as recommender systems, image recognition, and other scenarios requiring rapid identification of similar items (Islam *et al.*, 2024, Liu *et al.*, 2022). Upon training completion, the trained ‘Model Big’ was employed to predict the sentiment of images from historic districts. Following pre-processing, the image was input into the model, which classified the emotional category and output the corresponding prediction probability. The model determines whether an image is likely to portray a positive or negative emotion based on prediction probability.

Fig. 3. The framework of image prediction model.

RESULTS

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF DEEP LEARNING MODELS

We conducted tests on 1,480 graphs, producing classification report detailed in Tables 2 to 5. We evaluated the performance of three deep learning models—CNN, ResNet, and Swin Transformer—and their combined fusion model on a classification task with 1,480

images. The Swin Transformer and fusion models exhibited high accuracy and robust performance, outperforming the CNN and ResNet models. The CNN model achieved 88.9% accuracy, with precision and recall varying by category. The ResNet model attained 84.4% accuracy, with high precision but varied recall. The Swin Transformer excelled with 97.8% accuracy, demonstrating high precision and recall across both categories. The fusion model achieved 97.8% accuracy, equal to the Swin Transformer, highlighting the benefits of a multi-model fusion strategy for complex classification tasks requiring high accuracy and reliability. This combination effectively captured the complex visual features of the Jiangnan Historic District for accurate sentiment analysis.

Table 2. *CNN model classification report:*

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.842	0.889	0.865	592
1	0.923	0.889	0.906	888
accuracy			0.889	1480
macro avg	0.883	0.889	0.885	1480
weighted avg	0.891	0.889	0.889	1480

Table 3. *ResNet classification report:*

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.720	1.000	0.837	592
1	0.923	0.889	0.851	888
accuracy			0.844	1480
macro avg	0.860	0.870	0.844	1480
weighted avg	0.888	0.844	0.846	1480

Table 4. *Swin Transformer classification report:*

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.947	1.000	0.973	592
1	1.000	0.963	0.981	888
accuracy			0.978	1480

macro avg	0.974	0.981	0.977	1480
weighted avg	0.979	0.978	0.978	1480

Table 5. *Three-model fusion classification report:*

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.000	0.955	0.977	724
1	0.958	1.000	0.979	756
accuracy			0.978	1480
macro avg	0.979	0.977	0.978	1480
weighted avg	0.979	0.978	0.978	1480

CONSTRUCTION OF A POSITIVE-NEGATIVE MODELLING SYSTEM

We evaluated the positive-negative model over five training cycles, processing 1,620 images per cycle. The performance of the model steadily improved, evidenced by a reduction in loss and an increase in test accuracy and stability. Detailed results for each epoch are presented in Fig. 4. In Epoch 5, the initial loss was 0.560, and the end loss was reduced to 0.436. The test accuracy peaked at 88.8%, and the average loss decreased to 0.378. The second test maintained an accuracy of 71.4% with an average loss of 0.592.

These results demonstrate a continuous reduction in loss and consistent improvement in accuracy across the training epochs, reflecting gradual model optimisation and enhanced learning efficiency. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the model in image classification tasks, showcasing its ability to adapt and improve over time.

To thoroughly assess the performance of our binary classification model, we employed the confusion matrix function from the `sklearn.metrics` library, which computes a matrix based on actual labels (`label_array`) and predicted labels (`predict_array`). The confusion matrix proved invaluable for evaluating the performance of our classification model across different categories (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Five training epoch of the positive–negative modelling system.

Positive–Negative Modelling					Confusion Matrix	
	precision	recall	f1-score	support		
0	0.667	0.769	0.714	751	0.769	0.231
1	0.769	0.667	0.714	869	0.333	0.667
accuracy			0.714	1620		
macro avg	0.718	0.718	0.714	1620		
weighted avg	0.722	0.714	0.714	1620		

Fig. 5. Positive–negative modelling classification report and confusion matrix.

The confusion matrix visually and numerically represents model performance, with rows indicating actual categories and columns indicating predicted categories. This matrix effectively demonstrates the capability of the model to distinguish between categories, highlighting areas of strong performance and those requiring improvements.

APPLICATION AND PERFORMANCE OF THE PREDICTIVE MODEL

In this study, we employed the model to predict a single nighttime image from the Qiaoxi Historic District (Fig. 6). Located west of Gongchen Bridge, along the Hangzhou section of the Grand Canal, this district epitomises canal transport culture. Presently, Qiaoxi district preserves a blend of heritage sites and modern establishments, such as Huichun Hall, courtyards, piers, pavilions, museums, shopping centres, and cafes, creating a rich commercial atmosphere.

In our analysis, we selected images from the galleries for testing (Table 6 and Fig. 7). The results demonstrate that the model is highly effective in identifying images similar to the input. The most similar image was the same

nighttime photo of image No.20, used as the input. The second most similar image was a nighttime scene from image No.9, and the third was another view from image No.15. Despite foreground similarities, the system effectively recognised distinct differences in the scenes, including modern residential buildings in the background of the third image.

Fig. 6. Photo of nighttime image from the Qiaoxi Historic District.

The model recommended six images based on their high visual similarity and shared positive emotional tones, demonstrating its ability to efficiently retrieve and recognise images that align with the input in style and mood. It accurately captures emotional tendencies, particularly positive emotions, which is valuable for emotion analysis in historic districts or temporal settings. This capability aids urban planning and historic preservation projects by enabling designers to predict realistic scenarios and assess emotional states before renovations, thus assisting decision-makers in effectively utilising visual and emotional information.

Fig. 7. Filter out the corresponding images.

Table 6. List of filter out the corresponding images.

	name	l_emotion	l_time	file_path
20	Qiaoxi	Positive	Night	/content/QX2.jpeg
9	Wuhe	Positive	Night	/content/WH2.jpeg
15	Qiaoxi District	Positive	Night	/content/QX11.jpeg
11	Pingjiang Road	Positive	Night	/content/PJ8.jpeg
16	Tunxi Old Street	Positive	Night	/content/TX14.jpeg
6	Southern Song Imperial Street	Positive	Night	/content/NSYJ6.jpeg
7	Cambridge and Kurama	Positive	Night	/content/CQ12.jpeg
5	Tunxi Old Street	Positive	Night	/content/TX5.jpeg
14	Mountain Pond	Positive	Night	/content/ST7.jpeg
4	Punjab, Province of Pakistan	Positive	Night	/content/WH23.jpeg

DISCUSSION

HOMOGENISATION ANALYSIS OF HISTORIC DISTRICTS

In restoring historic districts, renovation efforts often prioritise operational convenience or cost control. Typically, these projects preserve a few iconic elements, such as ancient trees, courtyards, and stone bridges, while introducing modern public art. However, there is a tendency to demolish many ordinary old buildings and redesign streets and lanes to meet spatial quality evaluation indices such as integration, accessibility, and comprehensibility. Unfortunately, these aggressive renovation practices can disrupt

the original spatial texture of districts and sever the social bonds these spaces embody, thus erasing the collective memory of the area. Additionally, the transformation often involves replacing everyday staples, such as vegetable markets, teahouses, hardware shops, and night markets, with upscale venues featuring international brands and fashion symbols. This shift significantly alters the once vibrant, bustling atmosphere filled with local colour, distancing it from its historical roots.

Utilising deep learning models such as CNNs and transformers to analyse image data from historic districts allows us to identify visual elements commonly associated with specific emotional labels. This analysis elucidates the

intricate relationship between visual elements and emotional responses and aids in understanding the underlying causes of visual and emotional homogeneity across different districts.

ADVANTAGES OF FUSION MODELLING

Merging three deep learning architectures, specifically ResNet, VGG, and Swin Transformer, into a single integrated model offers multiple advantages for image recognition and processing tasks.

Comprehensive feature extraction capability: ResNet and VGG models effectively capture local image features, such as edges, textures, and shapes, which are crucial for detail comprehension. Conversely, the Swin Transformer excels in capturing global dependencies via a self-attention mechanism. The integration of both local and global features enhances the comprehensive understanding of image content.

Efficiency and accuracy trade-off: In practical applications, a balance must be maintained between the computational efficiency of a model and its prediction performance. By integrating the models, the high efficiency of ResNet, the robust feature extraction of VGG, and the global understanding capability of the Swin Transformer can be leveraged to achieve high-precision prediction at relatively low computational costs.

Enhanced performance in complex scenes: Complex scenes, such as images of historic districts, encompass diverse information, including various architectural styles and complex background elements. The three-model fusion approach improves handling of complex data and enhances the accuracy of classification, recognition, and other tasks by combining their distinct features.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

The proposed model effectively integrates tourists' subjective ratings with automated image analysis for emotion classification. However, it encounters challenges in capturing the complexity of emotional states. To address this, more advanced models and algorithm incorporating multidimensional data, such as textual comments and social media feedback, are being developed. Temporal state classification is heavily influenced by lighting and sky colour, necessitating robust feature recognition techniques and the inclusion of multimodal data, such as weather information, to improve accuracy. Future research should integrate multiple data sources, including text and sound, with image data to enhance the comprehensiveness of sentiment analysis. Ongoing innovations in model structures, including leveraging advanced techniques such as GANs and

self-supervised learning, will enhance model capabilities and generalisability.

In conclusion, the experimental results provide significant insights into the performance, limitations, and potential applications of the multimodal sentiment analysis model developed for historic district imagery. First, the fusion model, integrating CNN, ResNet, and Swin Transformer architectures, offers considerable advantages over single-model approaches, particularly in handling the complex visual contexts typical of historic districts. This superiority is evidenced by its enhanced accuracy, precision, and recall, highlighting the efficacy of multimodal integration in capturing both local detail and global dependencies. Detailed sentiment classification analysis reveal that the model excels in distinguishing between positive and negative emotions, as confirmed by the confusion matrix, suggesting that the ability of the Swin Transformer to capture nuanced emotional cues is instrumental in improving classification accuracy. Further analysis highlights the impact of specific visual features—such as architectural styles and cultural symbols—on sentiment outcomes, offering practical insights into the ways these elements shape public emotional responses. This capability renders the model a valuable tool for sentiment-driven urban design, allowing designers to anticipate and incorporate elements that evoke positive reactions. Nonetheless, limitations persist, such as decreased model performance in extreme settings including low-light or crowded scenes. Addressing these limitations in future studies—by expanding dataset diversity and enhancing image preprocessing techniques—could improve adaptability. These findings underscore the potential of multimodal sentiment analysis to inform culturally sensitive design and suggest pathways for future optimisation and broader application.

CONCLUSION

This study presents an image-emotion learning system employing deep-learning techniques tailored to classify emotions and temporal states in street photographs of historic districts. By integrating CNN and transformer models with subjective tourist evaluations, the model achieved over 80% classification accuracy across multiple dimensions. These findings affirm the efficacy of hybrid models in image sentiment analysis and underscore the potential of merging human subjective perception with machine-vision analysis. This system provides urban planners and designers with a novel tool for assessing the emotional impacts of historic districts. The emotion-based assessment approach offers robust data for creating emotionally appealing and resonant urban spaces. Additionally, analysing the emotional tendencies in images of historic districts enhances understanding of public emotional reactions to different historic environments, which is essential for humane and

sensitive urban cultural heritage preservation and restoration.

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DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated and analysed during this study were collected and photographed by the authors. User evaluations were conducted with participants' consent. These data are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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EFFICIENT IMAGE SUPER-RESOLUTION WITH MULTI-BRANCH MIXER TRANSFORMER

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ABSTRACT

Deep learning methods have demonstrated significant advancements in single image super-resolution (SISR), with Transformer-based models frequently outperforming CNN-based counterparts in performance. However, due to the self-attention mechanism in Transformers, achieving lightweight models remains challenging compared to CNN-based approaches. In this paper, we propose a lightweight Transformer model termed Multi-Branch Mixer Transformer (MBMT) for SR. The design of MBMT is motivated by two main considerations: while self-attention excels at capturing long-range dependencies in features, it struggles with extracting local features. Secondly, the quadratic complexity of self-attention forms a significant challenge in building lightweight models. To address these problems, we propose a Multi-Branch Token Mixer (MBTM) to extract richer global and local information. Compared to other Transformer-based SR networks, MBTM achieves a balance between capturing global information and reducing the computational complexity of self-attention through its compact multi-branch structure. Specifically, MBTM consists of three parts: shifted window attention, depthwise convolution, and active token mixer. This multi-branch structure handles both long-range dependencies and local features simultaneously, enabling us to achieve excellent SR performance with just a few stacked modules. Experimental results demonstrate that MBMT achieves competitive performance while maintaining model efficiency compared to SOTA methods.

Keywords: active token mixer, multi-branch token mixer, single image super-resolution, transformer.

INTRODUCTION

Single-image super-resolution (SISR) is focused on upscaling low-resolution (LR) images to generate high-resolution (HR) images. The success of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in the field of SR can be attributed to their robust feature extraction capabilities and end-to-end learning framework. Researchers have achieved significant advancement by training CNN models to learn the mapping from LR to HR images (Dong *et al.*, 2016a;b; Kim *et al.*, 2016a; Ledig *et al.*, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Tai *et al.*, 2017b; Lim *et al.*, 2017a). Despite the impressive performance of CNN models in generating high-quality SR images, the depth and complexity of these networks result in large model sizes and high computational requirements, presenting obstacles to deployment in resource limited environments. To address these challenges, researchers are actively exploring the design of lightweight super-resolution architectures, aiming to reduce model size and computational costs while maintaining performance standards (Hui *et al.*, 2019; Ahn *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2022c; Kong *et al.*, 2022; Liu *et al.*, 2020; Lai *et al.*, 2017; Shi *et al.*, 2016; Tai *et al.*, 2017a; Kim *et al.*, 2016b).

The receptive field of CNN-based SR models is primarily constrained by the limitations in the size and depth of convolutional kernels. These limitations restrict the model's ability to capture long-term dependencies in images, potentially leading to distortion or blurriness, particularly evident in larger-sized images or complex scenes. To tackle this challenge, researchers have recently started exploring the utilization of emerging architectures like Transformers for super-resolution tasks (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017; Dosovitskiy *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2024; Cao *et al.*, 2022; Zhou *et al.*, 2023; Chen *et al.*, 2023). Unlike CNNs, Transformers are not constrained by the limitations of receptive fields, enabling models to effectively capture global information and long-term dependencies, which has the potential to enhance the performance and effectiveness of SR models. Although Transformers have made significant progress in computer vision, the training and inference require significant computational resources, largely attributed to self-attention (SA) (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017), which results in a quadratic growth in computational complexity as the token length increases. Moreover, transformers struggle with handling local information, which consequently limits the model's performance. Based on these reasons, designing lightweight

transformer-based SR models remains a challenging problem in the field (Choi *et al.*, 2022; Gao *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2023; Liang *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023).

To address the aforementioned issues, this paper proposes a lightweight SR network named Multi-Branch Mixer Transformer (MBMT), which effectively balances global and local feature extraction by incorporating multiple token mixing strategies. In contrast to other conventional Transformer architectures, the proposed MBMT introduces a unique module named multi-branch token mixer (MBTM), which adopts multiple token mixing methods, including self-attention. MBTM represents a more complex token mixing approach, designed to trade off network depth for wider width, thus strengthening the model’s learning capability and generalization ability. It consists of three branches: self-attention, depthwise convolution (DWConv)(Howard *et al.*, 2017a), which refers to a 1×1 convolution, and active token mixer(ATM) (Wei *et al.*, 2022), which is a method for providing long-range dependencies through pixel reorganization. Each branch is tasked with capturing long-term dependencies, extracting local features, and expanding the global information space, respectively. Compared to other Transformer-based models, MBTM leverages the DWConv branch to effectively extract local information, addressing the limitation of Transformers in capturing fine-grained details. Additionally, the ATM branch expands the global feature space captured by the Self-Attention branch while maintaining a lower computational complexity than Self-Attention. This multi-branch design allows MBTM to achieve performance comparable to deeper Transformer-based models with fewer network layers, effectively addressing the limitations in current SOTA methods. Drawing inspiration from DAT (Chen *et al.*, 2023), we incorporate adaptive spatial and channel attention mechanisms to ensure sufficient interaction among the information extracted from the three branches, hence augmenting MBTM’s feature representation capability. Benefiting from the efficiency of MBTM and a shallower network structure, our MBMT significantly enhances SR model performance and reduces complexity, as shown in Fig. 1.

The primary contributions of this paper are enumerated as follows:

1. We propose a novel multi-branch token mixer designed to capture long-term dependencies while simultaneously extracting local information. Additionally, we employ spatial and channel attention mechanisms to interact features at

different levels, significantly enhanced the model’s super-resolution performance.

2. We introduce ATM within MBTM to achieve richer global information interaction while avoiding excessive computational costs associated with the self-attention mechanism.
3. We conduct extensive experiments to demonstrate that our proposed MBMT achieves superior image restoration quality while maintaining low complexity.

Fig. 1. Performance vs parameters comparison for BSD100 ×4 dataset. The proposed MBMT achieves better SR quality than previous approaches, with a slimmer model.

RELATED WORK

EFFICIENT SR METHODS

In the domain of CNN-based SISR, the restoration of high-quality HR images typically relies on complex network architectures and a substantial number of parameters. However, these architectures commonly demand significant computational resources, consequently limiting their practicality in resource-constrained environments. To achieve a balance between model complexity and performance, there is a growing focus on lightweight image super-resolution approaches (Dong *et al.*, 2016b; Hui *et al.*, 2019; Ahn *et al.*, 2018; Kong *et al.*, 2022; Liu *et al.*, 2020; Lai *et al.*, 2017; Shi *et al.*, 2016; Li *et al.*, 2022c). With a straightforward convolutional architecture, SRCNN (Dong *et al.*, 2016a) accomplishes end-to-end SISR, highlighting the pioneering role of convolutional neural networks in super-resolution tasks. FSRCNN (Dong *et al.*, 2016b) significantly improves inference speed while

maintaining excellent SR performance by optimizing the network architecture of SRCNN. ESPCN (Shi *et al.*, 2016) innovatively proposes the use of sub-pixel convolutional layers to rearrange LR features into HR images, effectively addressing the limitations associated with pixel-wise operations in conventional upscale approaches. The approach demonstrates remarkable outcomes in terms of both visual fidelity and computational efficiency. The inception of ResNet (He *et al.*, 2016) has stimulated the growth of numerous lightweight SR models with residual structures, driving substantial progress in the field of super-resolution (Zhang *et al.*, 2018; Hui *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2020; Kong *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2022c;b). In recent years, there has been a growing trend of transformer-based SR networks (Choi *et al.*, 2022; Chen *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2023; Zhang *et al.*, 2023) achieving comparable or even superior performance compared to traditional CNN methods.

TRANSFORMER FOR SR

The success of the Transformer in natural language processing has paved the way for innovative approaches in image processing tasks through its application into computer vision, achieving performance levels that match or even surpass those of traditional convolutional neural networks (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017; Dosovitskiy *et al.*, 2021; Liu *et al.*, 2021). Employing the Transformer in super-resolution tasks enables the model to leverage its strength in capturing global information, thus contributing to the understanding of image structure and content for the generation of high-quality HR images (Zhou *et al.*, 2023; Cao *et al.*, 2022; Chen *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2024). TTSR (Yang *et al.*, 2020) introduces a texture transformer to compute the correlation between the LR image and the reference (Ref) image. By utilizing both hard-attention and soft-attention modules to learn the joint features between LR and Ref, it effectively transfers texture information from Ref to the HR image. SWinIR (Liang *et al.*, 2021) makes use of the Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.*, 2021) architecture for SISR tasks. It capitalizes on the Transformer’s self-attention mechanism to capture long-term dependencies in images, thereby enhancing feature extraction and processing efficiency through hierarchical structures. In comparison to conventional convolutional neural networks, SWinIR demonstrates outstanding performance in various SR tasks. ESRT (Lu *et al.*, 2022) is a lightweight architecture that combines CNN and Transformer. The model employs the feature split module to split long sequences into multiple sub-sequences, enabling attention operations on these sub-sequences

to reduce GPU memory consumption. To tackle the limited receptive field challenge in SWinIR, Haram *et al.* (Choi *et al.*, 2022) introduced N-Gram (Li *et al.*, 2022a) context into SWin and proposed NGSWin. NGSWin enlarges the visible region and restores degraded pixels through sliding window self-attention interaction. LBNet (Gao *et al.*, 2022) introduces a recursive mechanism within the Transformer, allowing the model to learn global information effectively without significantly increasing GPU memory consumption and model parameters. DAT (Chen *et al.*, 2023) employs a strategy of alternating spatial and channel self-attention within Transformer blocks. This enables feature aggregation across spatial and channel dimensions, enhancing the model’s image representation capabilities and significantly improving image super-resolution performance.

TOKEN MIXER

Within the Transformer model, the input feature is decomposed into a sequence of tokens, where each token interacts with other tokens via a self-attention mechanism. This interaction process is commonly referred to as token mixing (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017; Dosovitskiy *et al.*, 2021). However, self-attention leads to quadratic growth in computational complexity with longer sequences, resulting in increased costs and slower training and inference speeds, requiring a significant increase in computational resources. MLP-like mixer (Tolstikhin *et al.*, 2021; Touvron *et al.*, 2022) demonstrated that exclusively employing MLPs can match Transformer’s performance, indicating the potential for substituting self-attention with basic token mixers. Poolformer (Yu *et al.*, 2022) is a Transformer-based model that replaces the self-attention module in Transformer with a simple spatial pooling operation as a token mixer for basic token mixing. This approach enables the model to achieve performance equivalent to Transformer and MLP-like models. Huang *et al.* (Huang *et al.*, 2023) employed Fourier transformation to transform tokens into the frequency domain and conducted adaptive filtering operations on the transformed tokens, enabling lightweight token mixing. ATM (Wei *et al.*, 2022) accomplishes adaptive global information integration by recomposing tokens, demonstrating outstanding performance with limited computational cost.

THE METHOD

In this section, we extensively describe the technical details of the proposed MBMT. Firstly, we provide a comprehensive description of the

Fig. 2. The architecture of Multi-Branch Mixer Transformer (MBMT).

overall architecture of the network in Section 3.1. In Section 3.2, we further explore the details of the core module of multi-branch token mixer (MBTM). Finally, we introduce the structure of active token mixer (ATM) in detail.

NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

The MBMT illustrated in Fig. 2 aims to learn the end-to-end mapping function $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ from I_{LR} to I_{HR} images.

$$\hat{I}_{HR} = \mathcal{F}(I_{LR}; \theta), \quad (1)$$

where, θ denotes the learnable parameters. The overall structure of the proposed MBMT can be decomposed into three parts: the expanding layer, the feature extraction layer, and the image reconstruction layer.

Expanding layer The expanding layer is mainly utilized to increase the channel dimensions of the input image, thereby introducing additional features and contextual information to enhance the model’s performance:

$$F_l = \text{Conv}_3(I_{LR}), \quad (2)$$

where, $\text{Conv}_3(\cdot)$ denotes a 3×3 convolutional kernel, while F_l represents the low-level features extracted through the expanding layer.

Feature extraction layer To further extract complex and contextually meaningful features from the input low-level features, F_l is fed into the feature extraction layer to generate high-level features F_h :

$$F_h = \mathcal{F}_{ext}(F_l) + F_l, \\ \mathcal{F}_{ext}(\cdot) = \text{Conv}_3(\text{LN}(\mathcal{H}_{MBTM}^i(\cdot))), \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

As demonstrated in the above equation, the feature extraction layer is composed of a feature extraction function $\mathcal{F}_{ext}(\cdot)$ and a residual connection. Where, $\mathcal{H}_{MBTM}^i(\cdot)$ denotes the i -th MBTM, and $\text{LN}(\cdot)$ represents layer normalization.

Reconstruction layer Finally, we scale up the feature maps F_h in the image reconstruction layer to restore high-resolution images.

$$\hat{I}_{HR} = \mathcal{F}_{rec}(F_h), \\ \mathcal{F}_{rec}(\cdot) = \text{UP}_s(\text{Conv}_3(\cdot)), \quad (4)$$

where $\text{UP}_s(\cdot)$ denotes the sub-pixel convolution (Shi *et al.*, 2016) and s is the upscale factor. In the training process, we adopt L_1 loss (Zhao *et al.*, 2017) as the cost function, the optimization objective can be calculated as:

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\mathcal{F}(I_i^{LR}; \theta) - I_i^{HR}|. \quad (5)$$

MULTI-BRANCH TOKEN MIXER

In this subsection, we will introduce the core component of the proposed MBMT model, the MBTM. The MBTM adopts the general macro architecture of the metaformer (Yu *et al.*, 2022), which can be formulated as follows:

$$F_{hidden} = \mathcal{T}(\text{LN}(F_{in})) + F_{in}, \\ F_{out} = \text{MLP}(\text{LN}(F_{hidden})) + F_{hidden}, \quad (6)$$

where, F_{in} , F_{out} , and F_{hidden} respectively denote the input feature, output feature, and hidden layer feature. $\mathcal{T}(\cdot)$ represents multi-branch token mixer, and $\text{MLP}(\cdot)$ refers to multi-layer perceptron.

Multi-branch token mixer In computer vision, a token mixer enables interaction among information (tokens) between different spatial positions (patches) within an image to extract global features. Previous works (Yu *et al.*, 2022; Huang *et al.*, 2023) have explored different token mixing approaches, with self-attention mechanism being the most commonly utilized. However, given that stacking

Fig. 3. The architecture of multi-branch token mixer (MBTM).

self-attention modules in deeper network may lead to decreased inference efficiency, we have proposed a more efficient token mixing method: the multi-branch token mixer. As shown in Fig. 3, the module consists of three branches, stated as follows:

$$\mathcal{T}(F_{in}) = \mathcal{T}_{SW}(F_{in}) + \mathcal{T}_{DW}(F_{in}) + \mathcal{T}_{ATM}(F_{in}). \quad (7)$$

where, $\mathcal{T}_{SW}(\cdot)$ represents shifted window (Swin) self-attention mixer (Liu *et al.*, 2021), $\mathcal{T}_{DW}(\cdot)$ denotes 3×3 depthwise convolution layer, and $\mathcal{T}_{ATM}(\cdot)$ stands for active token mixer (Wei *et al.*, 2022). The computational formula for the Swin self-attention is given below:

$$SW(Q, K, V) = \mathcal{S} \left(\frac{Q \otimes K^T}{\sqrt{d}} + B \right) \odot M \otimes V, \quad (8)$$

$$Q, K, V = \mathcal{P}(F_{in}),$$

where, Q , K , and V denote the query, key, and value matrices, respectively, with d as the feature dimension. M is the mask matrix, and B is the bias matrix. $\mathcal{P}(\cdot)$ represents the linear projection layer, and $\mathcal{S}(\cdot)$ denotes the softmax function. We also utilized depthwise convolution layer to extract local features:

$$DW(V) = GELU(BN(DWConv_3(V))), \quad (9)$$

$$V = \mathcal{P}(F_{in}),$$

where, $GELU(\cdot)$ denotes Gaussian Error Linear Unit activation function (Hendrycks and Gimpel, 2016), $DWConv_3(\cdot)$ denotes the 3×3 depthwise convolution (Howard *et al.*, 2017b), and $BN(\cdot)$

represents the batch normalization. Additionally, to ensure complete integration of local and global information extracted by different modules, we conduct interaction on features across different branches:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{SW}(\cdot) &= SW(\cdot) \odot CA(DW(\cdot)), \\ \mathcal{T}_{DW}(\cdot) &= DW(\cdot) \odot SA(SW(\cdot)) \odot CA(ATM(\cdot)), \\ \mathcal{T}_{ATM}(\cdot) &= ATM(\cdot) \odot SA(DW(\cdot)), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard product, $SA(\cdot)$ and $CA(\cdot)$ represent spatial attention and channel attention, respectively. and $ATM(\cdot)$ stands for adaptive token mixer. We will provide detailed explanations of the implementation details of ATM in the Section 3.3.

Multi-layer perceptron In the architecture of metaformer-style models, a feedforward layer is typically appended following the token mixer. The feedforward layer generally employs linear transformations and nonlinear activation functions to enhance the model's capacity for nonlinear learning. Inspired by the DAT network (Chen *et al.*, 2023), we introduce the Spatial-Gate Feed-Forward Network (SGFN) as the feedforward layer. The SGFN adopts the structure of the self-gated activation function (Swish) (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2017) and utilizes depthwise convolution to reduce channel redundancy, thus enhancing the model's inference efficiency. The structure of SGFN is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. (a) The architecture of active token mixer (ATM). (b) Illustration of ATM along the horizontal direction (ATM_W).

ACTIVE TOKEN MIXER

In the token mixer module, we have enriched the feature information and enhanced the overall network performance by broadening the model’s width. Given that the token mixing method of self-attention would increase the load on the network, we have adopted a more efficient mixing approach, named active token mixer. The steps for calculating $ATM(\cdot)$ (Wei *et al.*, 2022) are described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 ATM(F_{in}) &= \mathcal{P}(F_{fusion}), \\
 F_{fusion} &= \lambda_W \odot F_W + \lambda_H \odot F_H + \lambda_I \odot F_I, \\
 F_W, F_H, F_I &= ATM_W(F_{in}), ATM_H(F_{in}), \mathcal{P}(F_{in}), \\
 [\lambda_W, \lambda_H, \lambda_I] &= MLP(F_W + F_H + F_I).
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

In the equation above, $ATM_W(\cdot)$ and $ATM_H(\cdot)$ denote the adaptive token mixers along the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively, while \mathcal{P} represents the linear projection layer. F_H , F_W , and F_I represent the recomposed features along the vertical and horizontal directions, as well as the original features. Subsequently, we utilize learned weights $[\lambda_W, \lambda_H, \lambda_I]$ to mix the three sets of features into the fused feature F_{fusion} . Token recombination, illustrated by $ATM_W(\cdot)$, is performed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 ATM_W(F_{in}^{[i,j,c]}) &= F_{in}^{[i,j+o,c]}, \\
 ATM_H(F_{in}^{[i,j,c]}) &= F_{in}^{[i+o,j,c]}, \\
 O &= \mathcal{P}(F_{in}).
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Variables i , j , c and o respectively represent the indices of the feature’s height, width, channel, and the corresponding offset for the queried feature value. The $O \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ denotes the query offset matrix.

Complexity Analysis For an input $F_{in} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$ (assuming the channel dimension C is not considered), the computational complexity of self-attention is calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{O}(SW) = H \times W \times H \times W = \mathcal{O}(H^2W^2). \tag{13}$$

This results from the pairwise interaction between all spatial locations in the input, leading to a quadratic complexity in both height H and width W .

For the active token mixer (ATM), under the same input, the complexity of generating an offset matrix in the channel dimension is:

$$\mathcal{O}(ATM) = H \times W = \mathcal{O}(HW). \tag{14}$$

This represents the complexity of computing a token mixer that generates offsets based on spatial dimension, which results in a linear complexity with respect to the spatial size $H \times W$.

Compared to self-attention, the computational complexity of ATM is significantly lower. The specific numerical reduction depends on the network structure and implementation details. In practice, the linear complexity of ATM makes it a more efficient choice, especially for large-scale image inputs, where the quadratic complexity of self-attention becomes computationally expensive.

EXPERIMENTS

SETUP

Datasets and Metrics Similar to most supervised models in SISR, we use the DF2K (Agustsson and

Manga109(x4):Cooking

GT
PSNR/SSIM

Bicubic
25.20/0.6716

IDN
27.36/0.7709

BSRN
27.75/0.7718

ESRT
27.90/0.7744

SWinIR
27.84/0.7728

SWinIR-NG
27.66/0.7689

MBMT(Ours)
27.93/0.7765

Urban100(x4):img098

GT
PSNR/SSIM

Bicubic
19.71/0.3991

IDN
20.41/0.5407

BSRN
20.82/0.5414

ESRT
20.91/0.5467

SWinIR
20.91/0.5543

SWinIR-NG
20.80/0.5441

MBMT(Ours)
20.94/0.5532

Urban100(x4):img073

GT
PSNR/SSIM

Bicubic
19.53/0.4448

IDN
20.07/0.5739

BSRN
20.13/0.5737

ESRT
20.50/0.5890

SWinIR
20.10/0.5914

SWinIR-NG
20.73/0.5991

MBMT(Ours)
20.92/0.6130

Fig. 5. Qualitative comparison with state-of-the-art SR($\times 4$) methods on Urban100/Manga109 datasets.

Fig. 6. Qualitative comparison with state-of-the-art SR($\times 4$) methods on Set14/BSD100 datasets.

Table 1. *Quantitative comparison results of the state-of-the-art methods on public benchmark datasets, with the first and second best results highlighted in Red and Blue respectively. ‘–’ indicates that the item is not included in the original paper.*

Scale	Model	Params[K]	Set5	Set14	BSD100	Urban100	Manga109
			PSNR \uparrow / SSIM \uparrow				
$\times 2$	VDSR(Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2016a)	666	37.53 / 0.9587	33.03 / 0.9124	31.90 / 0.8960	30.76 / 0.9140	37.22 / 0.9750
	CARN(Ahn <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	1592	37.76 / 0.9590	33.52 / 0.9166	32.09 / 0.8978	31.92 / 0.9256	38.36 / 0.9765
	IDN(Hui <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	553	37.83 / 0.9600	33.30 / 0.9148	32.08 / 0.8985	31.27 / 0.9196	– / –
	IMDN(Hui <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	694	38.00 / 0.9605	33.63 / 0.9177	32.19 / 0.8996	32.17 / 0.9283	38.88 / 0.9774
	RFDN(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	534	38.05 / 0.9606	33.68 / 0.9184	32.16 / 0.8994	32.12 / 0.9278	38.88 / 0.9773
	RLFN(Kong <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	527	38.07 / 0.9607	33.72 / 0.9187	32.22 / 0.9000	32.34 / 0.9299	– / –
	BSRN(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2022c)	332	38.10 / 0.9610	33.74 / 0.9193	32.24 / 0.9006	32.34 / 0.9303	39.14 / 0.9782
	SWinIR-light(Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	878	38.14 / 0.9611	33.86 / 0.9206	32.31 / 0.9012	32.76 / 0.9340	39.12 / 0.9783
	ESRT(Lu <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	677	38.03 / 0.9600	33.75 / 0.9184	32.25 / 0.9001	32.58 / 0.9318	39.12 / 0.9774
	ELAN-light(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	582	38.17 / 0.9611	33.94 / 0.9207	32.30 / 0.9012	32.76 / 0.9340	39.11 / 0.9782
	SWinIR-NG(Choi <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	–	– / –	– / –	– / –	– / –	– / –
	SPIN(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	497	38.20 / 0.9615	33.90 / 0.9215	32.31 / 0.9015	32.79 / 0.9340	39.18 / 0.9784
	MBMT(Ours)	455	38.18 / 0.9617	33.85 / 0.9198	32.31 / 0.9014	32.79 / 0.9343	39.29 / 0.9787
	$\times 4$	VDSR(Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2016a)	666	31.35 / 0.8838	28.01 / 0.7674	27.29 / 0.7251	25.18 / 0.7524
CARN(Ahn <i>et al.</i> , 2018)		1592	32.13 / 0.8937	28.60 / 0.7806	27.58 / 0.7349	26.07 / 0.7837	30.47 / 0.9084
IDN(Hui <i>et al.</i> , 2018)		553	31.82 / 0.8903	28.25 / 0.7730	27.41 / 0.7297	25.41 / 0.7632	– / –
IMDN(Hui <i>et al.</i> , 2019)		715	32.21 / 0.8948	28.58 / 0.7811	27.56 / 0.7353	26.04 / 0.7838	30.45 / 0.9075
RFDN(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2020)		550	32.24 / 0.8952	28.61 / 0.7819	27.57 / 0.7360	26.11 / 0.7858	30.58 / 0.9089
RLFN(Kong <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		543	32.24 / 0.8952	28.62 / 0.7813	27.60 / 0.7364	26.17 / 0.7877	– / –
BSRN(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2022c)		352	32.10 / 0.8966	28.73 / 0.7847	27.65 / 0.7387	26.27 / 0.7908	30.84 / 0.9123
SWinIR-light(Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2021)		897	32.44 / 0.8976	28.77 / 0.7858	27.69 / 0.7406	26.47 / 0.7980	30.92 / 0.9151
ESRT(Lu <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		751	32.19 / 0.8947	28.69 / 0.7833	27.69 / 0.7379	26.39 / 0.7962	30.75 / 0.9100
ELAN-light(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		601	32.43 / 0.8975	28.78 / 0.7858	27.69 / 0.7406	26.54 / 0.7982	30.92 / 0.9150
SWinIR-NG(Choi <i>et al.</i> , 2022)		770	32.44 / 0.8978	28.80 / 0.7863	27.70 / 0.7407	26.47 / 0.7977	30.97 / 0.9147
SPIN(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2023)		555	32.48 / 0.8983	28.80 / 0.7862	27.70 / 0.7415	26.55 / 0.7998	30.98 / 0.9156
MBMT(Ours)		475	32.44 / 0.8983	28.80 / 0.7863	27.73 / 0.7416	26.57 / 0.8012	31.03 / 0.9141

Fig. 7. *Analysis of model performance and complexity. (a) Comparison of running time between different models. (b) Comparison of MACs between different models. (c) Pie chart of FLOPs distribution among different modules in the MBMT. The running times, FLOPs, and MACs are calculated on the Manga109 dataset.*

Timofte, 2017; Lim *et al.*, 2017b) dataset to train our model in the experiments. This dataset adopts bicubic downscaling to obtain corresponding low resolution images, with a total of 3550 images, of which 3450 images for training, 100 images for validation. We use peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and structure similarity index (SSIM) (Wang *et al.*, 2004) as benchmarks to evaluate the performance of our model and compare it to other models on five standard benchmark datasets: Set5 (Bevilacqua *et al.*, 2012), Set14 (Zeyde *et al.*, 2010), BSD100 (Martin *et al.*, 2001), Urban100 (Huang *et al.*, 2015), Manga109 (Matsui *et al.*, 2015).

Implementation details The proposed MBMT comprises 8 Multi-branch token mixers (MBTMs). Within each MBTM, the number of self-attention heads, channel dimensions, and dimension expansion factor are set to 6, 64, and 2, respectively. In MBTM, the offset generation layer interval is set to 1, and the dimension expansion factor is 2. We randomly crop images to 192×192 as the input to the model, using a mini-batch size of 16. To enhance model performance, we apply horizontal flip and random rotations (90° , 180° , 270°) for data augmentation. The dataset is enlarged by a factor of 100 times the original size. During the model training, we set the

Fig. 8. Attribution analysis for different transformed-based SR models. Top row: GT images with a highlighted red box. Bottom three rows: Heatmaps showing pixel contributions to the red box in the SR process.

initial learning rate to 1×10^{-3} , with a total of 2×10^6 iterations. We employ the Cosine Annealing scheduler to dynamically adjust the learning rate throughout the training stage. Our model is implemented using the PyTorch framework and trained on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 SUPER GPU.

BENCHMARK RESULTS

As shown in Table 1, we compared MBMT with state-of-the-art lightweight SR approaches. This comparative analysis includes model parameters and the performance of $2\times$ and $4\times$ SR results across five benchmark testsets. The outcomes demonstrate the outstanding performance of MBMT in terms of both model efficiency and multi-scale super-resolution capabilities. Compared to SwinIR-NG (Choi *et al.*, 2022) and SPIN (Zhang *et al.*, 2023), the proposed MBMT achieves average PSNR gains of 0.04 and 0.01 dB on the testsets for $4\times$ SR. Despite transformed-based models generally outperforming CNN-based SR models, they often come with larger model sizes. In contrast, our model achieves impressive SR performance while maintaining a smaller model size compared to some CNN-based counterparts. In Figs. 5 and 6, we provide a visual comparison of our proposed MBMT with other models on the testset for $4\times$ SR results. The figure demonstrates MBMT’s superior ability in restoring fine details and textures compared to other methods.

Comparison on Model Complexity We conducted comparative experiments on different models, including comparisons of model parameters, running time, and multiply-accumulate

operations (MACs). To ensure fairness in our comparisons, we focused on SR methods that provide pre-trained models. Figure 7a depicts a comparison of parameters and execution time across different SR models on the Manga109 dataset. It is apparent that transformer-based models typically demonstrate slower execution speeds compared to CNN-based SR models. Importantly, among transformer-based models, MBMT exhibits certain advantages. The computational complexity analysis in Fig. 7b indicates that our MBMT model maintains similar levels of MACs to CNN-based SR models. However, our model excels in terms of super-resolution (SR) quality, demonstrating that it achieves superior performance even with limited computational resources. This highlights the effectiveness of our approach in balancing both efficiency and high-quality results. Specifically, the reduced computational complexity of our model makes it particularly suitable for real-time applications where resource constraints are critical, such as in mobile devices, edge computing, or remote sensing tasks. In these scenarios, the model’s ability to process high-resolution images with minimal memory usage and faster inference times allows for practical deployment without compromising on performance.

Attribution analysis We applied Local Attribution Maps (LAM) (Gu and Dong, 2021) to conduct attribution analysis on three Transformer-based models: SwinIR, SwinIR-NG, MBMT. As illustrated in Fig. 8, the red regions in the heatmap indicate the network’s attention to specific pixel areas during the SR. These pixels are crucial for generating the GT image within the red box. It is evident from the

figure that the proposed MBMT exhibits a markedly larger receptive field in comparison to SWinIR and SWinIR-NG. This observation suggests that MBMT is capable of leveraging a wider range of pixels for image reconstruction, consequently leading to enhanced SR performance.

ABLATION STUDY

Table 2. Ablation study of multi-branch token mixer on model performance. All models were trained from scratch with the same hyperparameters. FLOPs calculated on 1280×720 GT images.

Scale	SWin	DWConv	ATM	Params[K]	FLOPs[G]	Mem[M]	DIV2K100 PSNR/SSIM
$\times 4$		✓	✓	465	33	2160.05	30.2472/0.8332
$\times 4$	✓		✓	460	36	2886.34	30.5133/0.8401
$\times 4$	✓	✓		289	40	2502.36	30.4742/0.8391
$\times 4$	✓	✓	✓	475	43	2915.93	30.5320/0.8404

Table 3. Ablation study of active token mixer on model performance. All models were trained from scratch with the same hyperparameters. MACs calculated on 1280×720 GT images.

Scale	ATM _H	ATM _W	Identity	Params[K]	MACs[G]	DIV2K100 PSNR/SSIM
$\times 4$		✓	✓	438	20.73	30.5246/0.8401
$\times 4$	✓		✓	438	20.73	30.5175/0.8398
$\times 4$	✓	✓		438	19.07	30.5253/0.8401
$\times 4$	✓	✓	✓	475	20.73	30.5320/0.8404

Effectiveness of multi-branch token mixer To analyze the effectiveness of the multi-branch token mixer structure, we performed separate ablation experiments on each individual branch and validated the models using the high-resolution dataset DIV2K100. Table 2 demonstrates that the SWin+DWConv+ATM multi-branch structure attained the highest SR performance. Among the three branches, SWin has the most significant impact on SR, followed by ATM, with DWConv making the smallest contribution. Despite SWin’s smaller parameters, its quadratic computational complexity due to the self-attention mechanism leads to higher FLOPs, consequently impacting the model’s efficiency. While ATM has a larger parameter count, ATM’s computational load mainly focuses on offset calculations, resulting in lower FLOPs. As depicted in Fig. 7c, SWin, ATM, and DWConv account for 24.08%, 8.07%, and 16.37% of the total FLOPs in the model, respectively. Considering their impact on SR performance, it indicates the importance of the ATM branch in achieving lightweight SR.

Effectiveness of active token mixer Table 3 shows the results of ablative experiments conducted on the ATM to assess the influence of identity features, as well as adaptive token mixers along both horizontal and vertical dimensions, on the performance of $\times 4$ SR.

Overall, the three factors have roughly equal influence. Although the parameters and model complexity of adaptive token mixers along the horizontal and vertical dimensions are identical, the influence in the horizontal dimension on SR performance is slightly greater than in the vertical dimension. In comparison, identity features have a slight advantage in model size, model complexity, and SR performance. Combining the conclusions from Table 2, we can infer that the ATM significantly contributes to the model’s lightweight structure.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a lightweight SR model, MBMT, which achieves the goal of simultaneously extracting global and local features through a multi-branch structure design. This innovative design significantly reduces network depth while slightly increasing network width, paving the way for a lightweight super-resolution Transformer. Extensive experimental results demonstrate that MBMT achieves SOTA performance in both super-resolution quality and model complexity across benchmark datasets. However, considering that the self-attention branch still has a greater impact on model performance compared to other branches, designing a more efficient token mixer remains a significant challenge. As a potential future direction, replacing the active token mixer with a more efficient token mixer, such as the State Space Model (SSM) (Gu and Dao, 2024), could further reduce complexity (with linear complexity) while maintaining performance.

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RESEARCH ON VISUAL DETECTION METHOD OF SOUND FILM BROKEN GLUE DEFECT

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ABSTRACT

Broken glue defect is a common defect in sound film dispensing. Aiming at the problem of fuzzy glue region boundary frequently occurring in the detection process, an improved iterative maximum interclass variance method was proposed to detect broken glue defects. Due to the skewness distribution of the gray curve of the sound film, the median value of the gray value of the image was replaced by the average value of the improved iterative method to eliminate the sound film. The initial threshold of the sound film dispensing region was quickly converged. The maximum inter-class variance method was combined to improve the extraction accuracy of the glue region boundary. The image features of single gap, multi gap, and dislocation defect types in qualified and broken products were compared, and the number and offset of glue areas were calculated to identify defects accurately. Fifteen thousand products were randomly selected on the production line for testing, and the results showed that the detection accuracy rate of qualified products was 100%, and the detection accuracy rate of broken glue was 99.1%, which met the needs of enterprises.

Keywords: Broken glue defect, Improved iteration, Maximum interclass variance method, Threshold segmentation.

INTRODUCTION

The sound film and the voice coil are the main vocal components of the micro loudspeaker, most of which are dispensed with the sound film by the dispensing machine, but the passing rate and accuracy of the dispensing are low, which affects the quality of the micro loudspeaker.

According to the characteristics of glue, machine vision is mainly used to detect the quality of glue. The glue area image taken is segmented by threshold value to obtain glue information and determine whether there are defects. Liao (2015) expressed the deviation of the glue line position by comparing the deviation between the feature points of the standard glue picture and the control points of the actual glue picture. He *et al.* (2020) obtained the target region using the traditional threshold segmentation method and then obtained the region outline of the subpixel edge fixer. The above methods must be manually thresholded and overly dependent on human experience. Zhang *et al.* (2021) used an improved Canny algorithm and maximum inter-class variance (OTSU) method to obtain the glue-coated area and then detected the defects with subtraction in the glue area of

the standard picture. Chen *et al.* (2020) proposed a visual detection method for adhesive coating that did not rely on standard images. The standard adhesive coating trajectory was generated using engineering drawings, and the sampling points on the standard adhesive coating trajectory were converted into actual points through camera calibration to obtain adhesive strip information. Yu *et al.* (2023) proposed a method to detect the offset and width of gluing by K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classification without standard gluing pictures. Both methods measured linear gluing trajectories, but the accuracy of arc gluing trajectories was not well.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DETECTION SYSTEM DESIGN

Hardware Design

A specific model of the sound film in the production line of the enterprise was taken as the detection object, as shown in Fig.1(a). The size of the sound film was $15 \times 11 \text{mm}^2$, Z_1 -frame、 Z_2 -frame surrounded the dispensing area, and the shape of the area was similar to a circular rounded rectangle. In production, detecting

whether the glue was broken in the dispensing area was necessary.

The detection scheme's hardware composition was shown in Fig.1(b), mainly composed of an industrial camera, lens, light source, etc. The detection workpiece was placed at the center of the platform. Above it, the industrial camera, lens, and light source were successively installed, and the focal length and working distance of the lens were meticulously adjusted until the camera captured a clear image. To ensure that the image could retain all product information, the camera field of view was $16 \times 13 \text{ mm}^2$, and the accuracy requirement was 0.02 mm . Therefore, the pixel width in the long side direction was 800 pixels, and the pixel width in the short side direction was 650 pixels. Considering the distortion of the camera edge field of view and the stability requirements of the system, it was usually multiplied by 3 in industrial detection, that is, 2400×1950 pixels. Thus, selecting a camera with a resolution of 500W pixels could meet the requirements. The formula for calculating the focal length of an industrial lens was as follows:

$$f = Dw / (1 + 1/F) \quad (1)$$

Where f represented the lens's focal length, Dw represented the working distance, and F represented the magnification. The formula for calculating the focal length of an industrial lens was derived from the relationship between the lens, the working distance, and the magnification, and it was used to determine the appropriate lens for a given setup.

$$F = \min\{h/H, v/V\} \quad (2)$$

Where h and v represented the length and width of the selected camera chip, and H and V represented the shooting field's length and width, respectively.

Given that the working distance Dw was 115 mm , h was 12.4 mm , and v was 9.8 mm when formula (2) was substituted into formula (1), f was 49.4 mm . A lens with a focal length of 50 mm was selected. Since the color of the glue was similar to the background color of the dispensing area, both were red. The background was silver-white. Selecting a blue light source with a wavelength between 400 and 480 nm eliminated the background color and significantly enhanced the glue area's contrast, providing a favorable environment for subsequent image processing.

Dispensing Defect

Under normal circumstances, the qualified glue was evenly distributed in the specified area, showing a whole attitude, the glue outline was clear, with no fracture, as shown in Fig.2(a). However, the occasional dispensing

defects mainly included scraping, overflowing, and breaking glue. The first two defects can be identified directly by calculating the area of the glue. The glue-breaking defects can be divided into the following three situations:

1. A single gap in the glue track resulted in the glue head and tail not being connected, as shown in Fig.2(b).
2. There were multiple gaps in the glued track, and the guide glue was divided into multiple segments, as shown in Fig.2(c).
3. Glue hitting outside the specified area led to misalignment, as shown in Fig.2(d).

Fig. 1. Sound film and detection apparatus: (a) Sound film image, (b) Testing mechanism diagram

Among them, the first two defects were mainly caused by the glue nozzle's blockage, and the misplacement of the front cover caused the last one. Accurately identifying the type of broken glue defect can help enterprises quickly find the root cause of the problem and feed it back to the control system for rapid processing.

Fig.2. Sound film dispensing image: (a) Qualified product, (b) Single gap, (c) Multiple gaps, (d) Misalignment

SOUND FILM BROKEN GLUE DETECTION

Image Denoising

Since there was inevitable noise in the image, it affected the detection accuracy, so reducing the noise

processing was necessary. Standard methods for noise reduction with median filtering, mean filtering, and Gauss filtering (Liang *et al.*, 2023), the experiment showed that the median filtering could effectively save the glue edge information, and the effect was better, as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3. Image filtering: (a) Pre-filtered image, (b) Noise area, (c) Filtered image

Improved Iterative Maximum Inter-class Variance Method

The core of glue quality detection was threshold segmentation. OTSU method (Yu *et al.*, 2022), as a classical threshold segmentation method, divided the image into background region and target region, and the segmentation effect was shown in Fig. 6(b). It can be found that when the traditional OTSU method divided the sound film dispensing image, the glue region could not be accurately extracted, resulting in poor anti-interference and insufficient stability. It was because the OTSU method had an excellent segmentation effect on images with bimodal gray distribution. However, when the image distribution was skewed, or there were abnormal data, the segmentation effect was not ideal. As shown in Fig.4 (a), the gray level curve of the sound film dispensing image belonged to the right-skewed distribution, the effect of directly using the OTSU method was not good, so abnormal data should be eliminated first. In order to make up for the shortcomings of the traditional OTSU

method, the improved iterative method and OTSU method were combined to avoid the interference of abnormal data.

The iterative method was a global threshold segmentation method, which took the average gray value of the image as the starting point of segmentation, iterated continuously, and took the final convergence value as the final segmentation threshold (Li *et al.*, 2022). The processing effect was shown in Fig.6(c), but the segmentation effect cannot meet the requirements. The main reason was that this method was mainly suitable for occasions where there was little difference between the target area and the background area. However, the target area of the research object was quite different from the background area. It can be seen from Fig.4(a) that the gray level distribution of the background area of the image belonged to the skewed distribution. For the data with skewed distribution, the median is not affected by the extreme value, which can better reflect the central tendency of the data. Therefore, GV_{m0} , the median gray value of the image, was selected as the primary threshold. After the initial segmentation, the sound film dispensing image was divided into the background area Z_g and the target area Z_t , the median gray value GV_{gm} in the Z_g area and the average gray value GV_m in the Z_t area were calculated. The average GV_{mi} of GV_{gm} and GV_m were continuously updated through iterative calculation until the difference between GV_m and GV_{mi} was less than Δt . The calculation process of the improved iterative method is shown in Fig.5. And the iterative calculation formula is shown in equation (3).

$$\begin{cases} GV_{mi} = \frac{GV_{gmi} + GV_{tmi}}{2} \\ |GV_m - GV_{mi}| < \Delta t \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Finally, the threshold GV_m was used for image segmentation, and the gray level curve of the sound film after iteration was shown in Fig.4(b).

Fig.4. Grayscale curve of sound film: (a) Pre-iteration, (b) After iteration

Fig.5. Calculation flow of improved iterative method

OTSU method mainly divided the gray image into two parts, the target C_1 and the background C_2 , according to the threshold GV determined by the gray histogram, so the interclass variance of C_1 and C_2 was the largest (Guo *et al.*, 2023).

$$\sigma^2 = p_1(GV_{m_1} - GV_M)^2 + p_2(GV_{m_2} - GV_M)^2 \quad (4)$$

σ^2 represented the interclass variance of C_1 and C_2 , p_1 was the probability of the pixel in the C_1 area, p_2 was the probability of the pixel in the C_2 area, GV_{m_1} was the average value of the gray value in the C_1 area, GV_{m_2} was the average value of the gray value in the C_2 area, and GV_M was the average value of the total gray value of the image.

Assuming that the image gray level was L , then in the image of $[0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, L-1]$, the optimal threshold selection principle of OTSU method was as follows:

$$GV_b = \max \left(\sum_{i=0}^{L-1} \sigma^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

When selecting the optimal threshold, OTSU method needed to traverse 0-255 gray levels for 8-bit images, which led to a lengthy calculation process. When Fig.6(a) was used as the input image, GV_m was used as the traversal starting point, and the maximum image gray value GV_{max} was used as the traversal endpoint, which reduced the traversal range. The improved method's processing effect was shown as Fig.6 (d).

Fig. 6. Comparison of segmentation effect: (a) Sound-film dispensing image, (b) Traditional OTSU method, (c) Traditional iterative method, (d) Improved iterative maximum inter-class variance method

The mean intersection over union ($MIOU$) was introduced as an image segmentation accuracy evaluation index to compare each algorithm's advantages and disadvantages in a quantitative analysis (Huang *et al.*, 2020). The larger the $MIOU$ value, the better the image segmentation effect. $MIOU$ was calculated as follows.

$$MIOU = \frac{1}{k+1} \cdot \frac{A \cap B}{A \cup B} \quad (6)$$

k represented the number of categories of the foreground target, A represented the number of pixels in the dispensing area, and B represented the number of pixels obtained by the segmentation of various algorithms. The average crossover ratio of different algorithms was calculated, as shown in Table 1.

Table1. Comparison of segmentation effect of different algorithms

Detection object	Evaluation index	Traditional OTSU	Iterative method	Textual algorithm
Sound film dispensing	Threshold value	87	85	141
	MIUO	0.273	0.257	0.497

As shown in Table 1, the proposed algorithm was superior to the iterative method and the traditional OTSU method in image segmentation accuracy, and the glue region obtained by segmentation had clear boundaries, better stability, and anti-interference.

SOUND FILM BROKEN GLUE RECOGNITION

The identification of sound film broken glue mainly includes edge location and glue detection. Edge location was to obtain the edge of the sound film and determine the product's position through coarse and fine positioning, then cut the image according to the edge to reduce the detection range. Glue detection first eliminated noise points through image denoising, then obtained the optimal threshold GV_b according to Improved iteration maximum interclass variance (IIMIV), and then got the glue region by threshold segmentation. The different regional characteristics were used to determine the types of broken glue defects. The specific detection process was shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 7. Glue testing process

Template Matching

Due to the many complex factors affecting the dispensing quality, the track and shape of the glue on different sound films were slightly different, so it was not appropriate to choose the glue area directly as the template. In order to improve the accuracy of template matching, template selection must meet two conditions: ① The template area must be independent of the glue detection area. ② The position of the template area in the image was relatively fixed and easy to find. Therefore, A_1 -Frame and A_2 -Frame, as shown in Fig.1, were selected as templates.

After gray-scaling the image, the sound film base and edge contour were very fuzzy in the image, as shown in Fig.8(a), which could have been more conducive to template matching and positioning. The image needed to be enhanced, and linear gray transformation was used to change the gray value of each pixel in the image (Guo *et al.*, 2022). The enhanced image was shown in Fig.8(b) and used as the template image.

Fig. 8. Image enhancement: (a) Grayscale image, (b) Enhanced image

Template matching methods included correlation-based template matching (Ma *et al.*, 2019) and shape-based template matching (Shen *et al.*, 2023). The two methods were used to compare and match 30 products, respectively, and the matching results were shown in Fig.9. As can be seen from Fig.9, the stability and matching scores of template matching based on correlation were better than those based on shape.

Fig. 9. Comparison of template matching scores

Product Positioning

After successfully creating the template, affine transformation was used to determine the product position (Zou *et al.*, 2024). Due to the unclear contrast between the edge of the sound film and the base, the edge extraction accuracy was improved by using coarse positioning first and then fine positioning.

Coarse positioning. Template matching was used for coarse positioning, and the affine transformation matrix was obtained by using the position and angle relationship between the matching region Z'_m and the template region Z_m of the image to be matched, as shown in Fig.10. The affine transformation matrix consisted of two parts: rotation matrix and transfer matrix. The rotation matrix R was obtained according to the angle

relationship between the matching region and the template region, the translation matrix T was obtained using the position relationship between them. The final affine transformation matrix H was obtained by multiplying matrix R and T .

Fig. 10. Template matching position

$$H = T \cdot R \quad (7)$$

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & P_x \\ 0 & 1 & P_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -P_x \\ 0 & 1 & -P_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & T_x \\ 0 & 1 & T_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

P_x and P_y represented the row and column coordinates of the template center, respectively, θ represented the angle between the matching region Z'_m of the image to be matched and the template region Z_m . T_x and T_y represented the distance that the template center moved on the x and y axes, respectively.

The point of the template image $P_m(\text{row}1, \text{column}1)$ with matching corresponding point on the image $P'_m(\text{row}1', \text{column}1')$ satisfied the following relations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{row}1' \\ \text{column}1' \end{bmatrix} = H \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \text{row}1 \\ \text{column}1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Fine positioning. As shown in Fig.11, n non-parallel auxiliary lines (subject $n=4$) were drawn on the template image, the endpoint coordinates of each auxiliary line were recorded, the positioning line of each auxiliary line was obtained by fitting the measuring caliper, and then the center point $M(\text{row}2, \text{column}2)$ of the intersection points of the n positioning lines and their average deflection angle α

$$\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_i}{n}$$

were obtained, as shown in Fig.12(a). Through affine transformation matrix H, the position of the end-point of the auxiliary line in the image to be measured was obtained, and the auxiliary line was generated, the positioning line was generated by fitting the measuring caliper. The center point N(row2', column2') of the lines' intersection point was located, and the average deflection angle was denoted as

$$\theta(\beta = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i}{n}),$$

as shown in Fig.12(b). According to the coordinates of M and N, the angle α and β , the fine positioning affine transformation matrix H_1 was obtained by equation (7)-(9).

Fig. 11. Auxiliary line of fine positioning

Fig. 12. Auxiliary line of fine positioning: (a) Template image, (b) Image to be tested

After the precision positioning, the auxiliary lines of the product edge were drawn on the template image, and the auxiliary lines' positioning line (edge line) was found by measuring the caliper. The intersection coordinates of n edges were obtained, namely n vertices of the product, and the product edges of the template image were generated, as shown in Fig.13(a). The affine transformation matrix H_1 was used to obtain n vertices of the product under the image under test, and then the product edges of the image to be tested were brought.

the edges of the product as the boundary to obtain a single product image, as shown in Fig.13.

Fig. 13. Image clipping: (a) Pre-crop image, (b) Image clipping

Identification Of Broken Glue Defects

In order to avoid the influence of the gray level of the sound film background, the image is cropped with

After obtaining the glue area by the IIMIV method, the opening operation was used to split the area and calculate the number of glue areas. If the number were greater than 1, it would be judged as a multi-gap defect, as shown in Table 2, the number was 13. If the quantity was equal to 1, for the qualified product, the glue area formed a closed pattern with internal holes, that was, the diagonal part in the figure, for a single gap defect, the glue area cannot form a closed pattern, and there were no holes inside, so qualified products or single-notch defects can be judged by calculating whether the hole area in the glue area was 0.

Table2. Sound film dispensing quality detection

Detection result	multi gap defect	qualified product	Single gap defect
Original image			
Threshold segmentation			
Open operation			
Dispersed region			

For the misalignment defect, the product edge was obtained according to the affine transformation matrix H_1 , the center coordinate $O_1(r_1, c_1)$ was calculated, then the center coordinate $O_2(r_2, c_2)$ of the glue region was obtained. The Euclidean distance d between O_1 and O_2 was calculated. The misalignment judgment method was as follows:

$$\begin{cases} d = \sqrt{(r_1 - r_2)^2 + (c_1 - c_2)^2} \leq D, & \text{Nonmalposition} \\ d = \sqrt{(r_1 - r_2)^2 + (c_1 - c_2)^2} > D, & \text{Malposition} \end{cases}$$

D was half of the width of the dispensing area of the product, after obtaining the glue area of the qualified product, filled the area, calculated the height of the area

as h_1 , and then made a difference between the filled area and the original glue area to obtain the difference area, calculated the height of the area as h_2 . The difference between h_1 and h_2 was $1/4 D$. As shown in Fig.14.

Fig. 14. Misalignment diagram

RESULTS

DETECTION EXPERIMENT

In order to verify the accuracy of the detection method, 15,000 products were selected from the production line for retesting. After the unqualified products caused by other defects were removed, the retesting results were shown in Table 3. The detection accuracy of qualified products was 100%, and the detection accuracy of three types of broken glue defects was 98%, 100%, and 100%, respectively, indicating that the algorithm in this paper can accurately identify OK products and broken glue NG products, and distinguished the types of broken glue. Through the analysis, the misjudgment of multi-gap defect detection was because part of the product glue path was thin, which led to the deviation of glue region segmentation during the opening operation. In addition, ten replicates of qualified products and defective products were selected for 100 times detection, and the detection results were consistent, which proved that the stability and accuracy of the detection method were good.

Table 3. Test results of broken glue quality

Detection result	Quantity/piece	Miscalculation number/piece	Accuracy rate/%
OK	14836	0	100
Multi gap NG	68	1	98
Single gap NG	40	0	100
Misaligned NG	15	0	100

DISCUSSION

In this paper, aiming at the problem of existing dispensing quality detection in enterprises, a visual detection method of sound film dispensing quality was proposed. According to the gray distribution of the image, abnormal data were removed by an improved iterative method, and the initial segmentation threshold of the sound film dispensing image was obtained, which was combined with the OTSU method to obtain the best segmentation threshold and then accurately extracted the dispensing area. This method improved the traditional OTSU method when the image gray curve had a skewed distribution, the segmentation effect was not ideal. The experimental test showed that the scheme could accurately identify the broken glue defect and distinguish the broken glue type, the overall detection accuracy was 99.1%.

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PALMPRINT CLASSIFICATION WITH MULTIPLE FILTER FACES, FOURIER FEATURES AND VOTING TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a novel method for palmprint classification. We extract the central region from the palmprint image, calculate eight filter faces (FF) from the region based on eight pairs of filters, compute the Fourier features from each FF, classify each of them to one known class, and then perform majority voting to determine the final class label of the unknown palmprint image. By examining the structures of the selected filters, we can see that our new method can suppress random noise and at the same time it can extract directional features from the palmprint images. This is the main reason why FF-based methods are better than non-FF-based methods for palmprint classification. In addition, the majority winning policy (voting) based on eight FFs improves classification accuracies significantly. Experimental results demonstrate that our new method outperforms several existing methods for palmprint classification.

Keywords: Fast Fourier transform (FFT); filter faces (FF); majority voting technique; palmprint recognition.

INTRODUCTION

Palmprint classification is a very important topic in computer vision. We briefly review several existing methods for palmprint classification here. Zhang *et al.* (1999) studied two novel characteristics in palmprint verification: Datum point invariance and line feature matching. You *et al.* (2002) analyzed hierarchical palmprint identification via multiple feature extraction. Dong *et al.* (2004) investigated digital curvelet transform for palmprint recognition. Chen *et al.* (2006) performed palmprint classification by dual-tree complex wavelets. Zhang *et al.* (2003) studied on-line palmprint identification in 2003. Trabelsi *et al.* (2022) developed efficient palmprint biometric identification systems with deep learning and feature selection methods. Wu *et al.* (2021) studied triple-type feature extraction for palmprint recognition. Zhao *et al.* (2023) analyzed multiview learning-based generic palmprint recognition. Fei *et al.* (2019) worked on feature extraction methods for palmprint recognition. Alausa *et al.* (2022) surveyed on contactless palmprint recognition system in 2022. Idrissi *et al.* (2020) performed a comparative study on palmprint recognition with state-of-the-art local texture descriptors.

PROPOSED METHOD

In this paper, propose a new method for palmprint classification. We extract the central region from the

palmprint images, compute eight FFs from the region according to eight pairs of filters and then calculate the Fourier feature maps from each FF and take the Fourier spectra. We perform classification with the extracted feature maps and then conduct majority voting to determine the final class label of the unknown palmprint image.

We define eight pairs of high-pass filters (HF) and low-pass filters (LF) as follows, where the first four pairs of filters are of size 7×7 and the second four pairs of filters are of size 9×9 .

$$HF\{1\} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{2\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{3\} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{4\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$LF\{1\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$LF\{2\}=LF\{1\},$$

$$LF\{3\}=LF\{1\},$$

$$LF\{4\}=LF\{1\},$$

$$HF\{5\} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{6\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{7\} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$HF\{8\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$LF\{5\} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$LF\{6\}=LF\{5\},$$

$$LF\{7\}=LF\{5\},$$

$$LF\{8\}=LF\{5\}.$$

(1)

The $FF\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$, can be defined as Chen *et al.* (2018):

$$FF\{i\}(x, y) = \arctan \frac{HF\{i\} * I(x, y)}{LF\{i\} * I(x, y)} \quad (2)$$

where $*$ is the convolution operator, $HF\{i\}$ is the high-pass filter, $LF\{i\}$ is the low-pass filter, and I is the palmprint image. It is not difficult to prove that the $FF\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$, are approximately illumination invariant for any $LF\{i\}$ and $HF\{i\}$. We extract the Fourier features from each FF by means of *fft2* available in Matlab and then take the spectra. Fig.1 shows the flow-chart of the proposed algorithm in this paper. We extract eight FF s from the input palmprint image, perform the 2D FFT transform to each FF , classify the palmprint image with the nearest neighbour classifier, and then conduct majority voting to determine the final class label of the unknown palmprint image

We provide the algorithm for training palmprint images here:

- 1) Read the palmprint image and extract the central region (Fig. 2).
- 2) Calculate $FF\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$ from the central region.
- 3) Extract the Fourier features from the $FF\{i\}$ and take the spectra, denoted as $Spec\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$.
- 4) Save the features in a database for later query.

We provide the algorithm for testing palmprint images here:

- 1) Read the palmprint image and extract the central region (Fig. 2).
- 2) Calculate $FF\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$ from the central region.
- 3) Extract the Fourier features from the $FF\{i\}$ and take the spectra, denoted as $Spec\{i\}$, $i \in [1,8]$.
- 4) Use the extracted features to query the feature database by the nearest neighbour (NN) classifier. Let us denote the calculated class labels as $ID = \{idk\}$, $k \in [1,8]$.
- 5) Conduct majority voting on ID to determine the final class label of the testing palmprint image.
- 6) Compute the correct classification rate of our new algorithm, which is defined as the ratio between the number of correct classification and the number of total palmprint images.

Our majority voting technique selects the most frequent element in an array as the class label of the unknown palmprint image, which improves the classification accuracy significantly as demonstrated in our experiments. We count the number of times an element in an array occurs and then find the array index corresponding to the value with the most occurrences. Finally, we output the element in the array with most occurrences as the class label of the unknown palmprint image.

We have the following observations about the speed of our new algorithm. We have implemented our new algorithm in unoptimized Matlab code in this paper, so it is a bit slow. We can port it to the faster C++ programming language in the future. In our new algorithm, we select to use eight FFs to extract the feature maps from the palmprint image. Since these FFs are independent of each other, we can implement them in parallel such that faster execution can be achieved. We can also run our new algorithm on Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) so that we can recognize palmprint images even faster.

The computational complexity of our new algorithm can be summarized as follows. The eight FFs can be calculated in $O(8MN)$ operations, where the palmprint image has $M \times N$ pixels. The Fourier features can be extracted with $O(8MN \log(MN))$ operations. The NN classifier and the voting technique can be computed in linear time. Therefore, the overall computational complexity of our new method is $O(8MN \log(MN))$.

The main reason why we choose handcrafted features instead of deep learning in this paper is because the number of classes in palmprint recognition can change frequently. When new palmprint classes are available, we need to train the deep learning networks again, which

is very time consuming. In addition, the number of palmprints for each class should be large for deep learning, so collecting many palmprint samples is a difficult task. Existing pattern classification problems such as traffic sign recognition and handwritten digits recognition are good for deep learning since the numbers of classes in both problems do not change over time. As a result, handcrafted features such as those proposed in this paper are better suited for our palmprint recognition problem.

The main contribution of this paper is the following. We extract eight FFs from the extracted palmprint central region according to eight pairs of filters. By examining the structures of the selected eight pairs of filters, we can see that they can extract directional features from the palmprint images, and they can suppress random noise as well. This is the main reason why FF-based methods are better than non-FF-based methods for palmprint classification. Furthermore, the majority winning policy (voting) based on eight FFs improves classification accuracies significantly. Our experimental results demonstrate the success of our new algorithm proposed in this paper for palmprint classification.

Fig. 1. The flow-chart of the proposed algorithm in this paper.

Fig. 2. Palmprint image and extracted central region.

RESULTS

We perform experiments for palmprint classification with the PolyU palmprint database, which contains

100 different palms, and each has six samples collected in two sessions. For each palm, we use four of the six palmprint samples for training and the rest of samples for testing. The size of the original palms without pre-processing is of 284×384 pixels. We extract the central

region of the palm image for palmprint classification with a size of 128×128 pixels.

We test the effect of additive Gaussian white noise (AGWN) on palmprint classification. We add AGWN to clean palmprint image as follows:

$$B = A + \sigma_n N(0,1), \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. *Palmprint images with different noise levels ($\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35).*

Fig. 4. *Palmprint images (first column), $FF\{1\}$ (second column), $FF\{2\}$ (third column), $FF\{3\}$ (fourth column), $FF\{4\}$ (fifth column), $FF\{5\}$ (sixth column), $FF\{6\}$ (seventh column), $FF\{7\}$ (eighth column), and $FF\{8\}$ (ninth column). The first to the last rows correspond to different noise levels $\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35 , respectively.*

Fig. 3. shows palmprint images with different noise levels ($\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35). In addition, Fig. 4 displays the palmprint images (first column) and their eight extracted FFs (second to last column). The first to the last rows correspond to different noise levels $\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35 , respectively. It can be seen in Fig. 4 that the FFs are very robust to AGWN since the extracted FFs are very clean without showing any noise content in them. This shows that the FFs are good at invariant palmprint classification even when AGWN is present in palmprint images.

Our experimental results with the PolyU palmprint database have the following observations. The best results are highlighted in bold font in both Tables 1 and 2. From Table 1, we can see that our proposed method (98.97%) is better than Zhang and Shu (1999) (93.3%), You *et al.* (2002) (95%), Dong *et al.* (2004) (95.25%), Chen *et al.* (2006) (97%), and Zhang *et al.* (2003) (98%) for palmprint classification. In addition, from Table 2, we can see that the Fourier features are better than the HOG features, the LBP features, and the DWT features for palmprint classification. The major reason why the Fourier features are the best for palmprint classification is because the Fourier spectra are invariant to spatial shifts, which is very important in invariant palmprint recognition. In our experiments, the DWT is chosen as Daubechies-4 wavelet transform. Furthermore, from Table 2, we can see that our method with FF is always better than that without FF for palmprint classification no matter what features (HOG, LBP, DWT and FFT) are used. In addition, the Fourier features combined the FF achieves the best classification results for all noise levels ($\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35) without exception. This demonstrates the success of our new method proposed in this paper for palmprint classification.

Table 2. *The correct classification rates (%) of the proposed method with and without filter faces for different features (HOG, LBP, DWT and FFT) and different noise levels ($\sigma_n=0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35) for palmprint classification. The best results are highlighted in bold font.*

Filter Faces	Features	Noise (σ_n)							
		0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35
No	HOG	87.63	84.54	74.23	38.14	13.92	5.15	2.06	1.55
	LBP	78.87	13.40	2.58	1.03	1.55	1.03	1.03	0.52
	DWT	62.37	62.37	61.86	61.86	62.37	61.86	62.37	46.91
	FFT	94.85	95.88	94.85	93.30	89.69	75.26	62.37	61.86
Yes	HOG	92.27	89.18	86.60	81.44	73.20	51.03	38.66	23.71
	LBP	97.94	88.14	41.24	11.86	4.64	3.61	2.58	2.06
	DWT	74.23	73.71	72.68	72.16	72.16	72.68	72.68	71.13
	FFT	98.97	99.48	99.48	98.97	98.45	97.42	95.36	90.21

Table 1. *The correct classification rates (%) of different methods for palmprint classification. The best results are highlighted in bold font.*

Zhang and Shu (1999)	You <i>et al.</i> (2002)	Dong <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Chen <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Proposed Method
93.3	95	95.25	97	98	98.97

CONCLUSIONS

Palmprint classification is a very challenging research topic. In existing literature, many techniques have been proposed to deal with this problem. Nevertheless, there still exists a need to further improve existing methods and propose new ones for palmprint classification.

In this paper, we have proposed a new method for palmprint classification. We extract the central region from the input palmprint image, compute eight FFs from the extracted region based on eight pairs of filters, calculate the Fourier features from each FF, classify each of them to one known class, and then perform majority voting to determine the final class label of the input palmprint image. Experimental results show that our new method performs the best for palmprint classification even if noise is present in the palmprint images. Future research will be conducted by experimenting with deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) for palmprint classification. We can also perform a systematic study to compare our new method proposed in this paper with many state-of-the-art methods developed in the past.

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IMAGE MOSAIC BASED ON LOCAL GUIDANCE AND DARK CHANNEL PRIOR

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ABSTRACT

Image mosaic is of significance in various areas such as object tracking and drone reconnaissance. Aiming at the problems of poor performance and high rate of false match in foggy images, an improved stitching method based on local guided KAZE and dark channel prior is proposed. First of all, the KAZE algorithm is utilized for rough feature matching. Secondly, a local fixed point asymptotic method is introduced to optimize the global objective and eliminate mismatched point pairs. Then, the warp images are obtained by the estimated transformation matrix. Thirdly, the compensation of color and luminance difference of the overlap is applied to the overall image, which improves the inhomogeneity of stitching image. Eventually, the final result is obtained by enhancing algorithm based on dark channel prior. The proposed algorithm is assessed through intuitive renderings and quantitative values. Furthermore, the proposed method is compared with other common stitching methods. The results reveal that the method proposed in this paper gives the best performance in terms of the magnitude of feature matching pairs, the mean absolute error (MAE), the root mean square error (RMSE) and the processing time.

Keywords: dark channel; image mosaic; KAZE; local guided.

INTRODUCTION

Image mosaic is the process of combining several images contained overlapped area from different imaging devices and perspectives into an image with higher resolution (Lin *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2020). Currently, mosaics is still a hot topic which is widely used in multiple fields such as ground reconnaissance, medical image analysis and criminal case investigation (Gómez-Reyes *et al.*, 2022; Nie *et al.*, 2022; Wan *et al.*, 2021). However, it still faces many challenges such as disparity, image distortion, ghosting, inhomogeneity and a series of issues (Pham *et al.*, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2022; Lin *et al.*, 2022). In addition, the blurred images due to environment and weather greatly increases the difficulty of stitching.

At present, researchers have proposed various methods for image stitching, including feature based, region based and deep learning based stitching algorithms. Liu *et al.* (Liu *et al.*, 2022) proposed a fast stitching method based on improved SIFT Algorithm. The feature pairs are gained by gradient normalization-based feature descriptors to improve the matching accuracy. The progressive sample consistency algorithm is applied to

eliminate the mismatch points and optimizes the transformation model in their method.

To solve the problems of high dimension of feature descriptor and low matching accuracy when the angle of rotation and angle of view is too large, Zhang *et al.* (Zhang *et al.*, 2020) raised an stitching method based on improved SURF. They establish descriptors for each feature point by Harris wavelet response and calculated simultaneously to form a new feature descriptor by the normalized gray-level difference and second-order gradient in the neighborhood. In addition, the random sample consensus (RANSAC) algorithm is used to eliminate the mismatch points. In order to improve the matching accuracy and robustness, Han *et al.* (Han *et al.*, 2018) presented a moving object detection algorithm based on binary robust invariant scalable key points (BRISK) considering the real-time and robustness requirements of detection algorithms in dynamic background. The improved BRISK algorithm is used to detect feature points. Next, the k-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm is applied to match feature points. Finally, the RANSAC is utilized to obtain the optimal global motion parameters.

In 2020, Wang *et al.* (Wang *et al.*, 2020) introduced an improved Harris corners extraction algorithm, which

consists of coarse screening and fine screening in the corners extraction process. Aiming at the poor matching effect, Xie *et al.* (Xie *et al.*, 2022) proposed a novel fast target recognition algorithm under the dynamic scene moving target recognition. Firstly, the template image and each frame of the video stream are processed by grayscale. Secondly, the template image and the image to be input in the video stream are processed by adaptive histogram equalization. Thirdly, the feature point descriptors of the ORB feature are quantized by the Hamming distance. Finally, the KNN algorithm is used to match and screen feature points. Peng *et al.* (Peng *et al.*, 2023) presented a novel optimal seamline detection strategy via graph cuts for HSI stitching in this work. They used robust feature matching and elastic warp to align multiple adjacent images into a common geometrical transformation. After that, they designed a novel energy function composing both the spatial and spectral information of HSI to determine an optimal seam in continuous regions with high texture consistency. Finally, the graph cuts method is used to eliminate visible artifacts. Ordóñez *et al.* (Ordóñez *et al.*, 2021) indicated a hyperspectral remote sensing image registration method based on MSER for feature detection and SIFT for feature description, which efficiently exploits the information contained in the different spectral bands to improve the image alignment.

With the deepening development of deep learning, image stitching algorithms based on deep learning are widely used. Chilukuri *et al.* (Chilukuri *et al.*, 2021) developed a robust and reliable image stitching methodology (l,r-Stitch Unit), which considers several non-homogeneous image sequences as input to generate a reliable panoramic image. The l,r-Stitch Unit further consists of a pre-processing, post-processing sub-modules and a l,r-PanoED-network, Each submodule of the method is a robust ensemble of several deep-learning, computer-vision and image-handling techniques. Zhu *et al.* (Zhu *et al.*, 2023) proposed an improved VGG16 Siamese network for the UAV remote sensing image stitching model to achieve end-to-end stitching. In their method, an improved squeeze and excitation module was introduced to effectively extract the features of the overlapping areas of the images. A network of regressing affine matrix was designed by using the LeakyReLU activation function to protect the relevant feature maps after feature fine matching, which improves the accuracy of image stitching. However, there are still issues with excessive resource and time consumption in image stitching based on deep learning at present.

Alcantarilla *et al.* (Alcantarilla *et al.*, 2012) proposed the KAZE feature which is more effective than

other feature detection algorithms. Roy *et al.* (Roy *et al.*, 2022) introduced a robust and discrimination capable hash function by considering KAZE point feature descriptor for combinatorial manipulations. The local features detected by KAZE are used to generate the hash function and this hash function not only provides a good discrimination capable value with good robustness but also shows good results for double attacks and multiple combinations of attacks.

In KAZE, nonlinear diffusion filtering is utilized to establish the scale level, which can decline speckle noise and smooth the image while preserving edge information (Fan *et al.*, 2018). In order to solve the problem of poor stitching effect and high mismatch rate caused by unclear images, an improved stitching method based on local guided KAZE and dark channel prior is proposed in this paper. The contributions of the paper are as follows: firstly, after rough matching based on KAZE features, a local fixed-point asymptotic method is introduced to optimize global objectives. This method can effectively eliminate mismatched point pairs and upgrade matching efficiency. Secondly, a compensation method based on local color and luminance difference is applied to smooth the overall image before fusing images, which can perfectly solve the problem of uneven color brightness and eliminate stitching seams. Thirdly, a dark channel prior based image defogging algorithm is introduced to enhance the foggy image and further improve the stitching effect.

This paragraph introduces the organization of the remainder of this article. Section 2 depicts the KAZE algorithm in summary. Section 3 provides the detailed introduction of the proposed stitching method in the article. Section 4 depicts the experimental results and analysis. Eventually, conclusions, shortage of the proposed method and the pending issues are indicated in Section 5.

MATERIAL

We briefly introduced the KAZE algorithm in this section. At present, the KAZE algorithm based on RANSAC is relatively popular. The process is shown in the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The flow of KAZE algorithm based on RANSAC.

Firstly, a nonlinear scale space at maximum evolution time is constructed through variable transfer to diffusion and additive operator splitting (AOS) algorithms in the KAZE (Shen *et al.*, 2019; Jong *et al.*, 2023). The

Equation (1) provides the classic nonlinear diffusion formula.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial t} = \text{div}(c(x, y, t) \cdot \nabla L) \quad (1)$$

Where div and ∇ express the operations of divergence and gradient separately. In addition, $c(x, y, t)$ is the conduction function, where x and y are horizontal pixels and vertical pixels respectively, and t is the scale parameter. L represents the image luminance.

The discretization in Equation (1) in vector matrix representation can be expressed as following.

$$\frac{L^{i+1} - L^i}{\tau} = \sum_{i=1}^m A_i(L^i) L^{i+1} \quad (2)$$

Among them, A_i is the matrix which encodes the image conversion of each level and m represents the matrix dimension. L^{i+1} is gained by Equation (3).

$$L^{i+1} = (I - \tau \sum_{i=1}^m A_i L^i)^{-1} L^i \quad (3)$$

Each level of the KAZE uses the same resolution as the input image in KAZE algorithm. According to the Difference of Gaussian (DOG) pyramid model (Setumin *et al.*, 2018), each level of the DOG pyramid requires $S+2$ layers to seek the extreme value of S scales. Thus, the scale space is constructed by Equation (4).

$$\sigma(o, s) = \sigma_0 2^{o+\frac{s}{S}}, o \in [0, 1, \dots, O-1], s \in [0, 1, \dots, S+2] \quad (4)$$

Among them, σ_0 is benchmark layer scale, o means the index of the level octave and s means the index of the inner layer of the group. The scales of the key points can be calculated based on the quantity of layers within the level and the above equation.

It is important to transform the scales into evolution time in the nonlinear diffusion filtering model. Assumed that the standard deviation in the Gaussian space is σ , then the convolution can be seen as performing a duration of $t = \frac{\sigma^2}{2}$. Through a serials of evolution times, the nonlinear scale space of the whole image is attained by Equation (5).

$$L^{i+1} = [I - (t_{i+1} - t_i) \sum_{i=1}^m A_i(L^i)]^{-1} L^i \quad (5)$$

Where I means the image matrix. In feature point detection and location, KAZE feature points are gained by searching the maximum value of the normalized Hessian determinant of various scales from the local points. To meet the requirements of multi-scale feature detection, the differential operator set is normalized by Equation (6).

$$L_{\text{Hessian}} = \sigma^2 (L_{xx} L_{yy} - L_{xy}^2) \quad (6)$$

Where L_{xx} , L_{yy} and L_{xy} indicate the second order derivatives in the horizontal, vertical and cross directions respectively. The response of the detector at different scale levels is checked on a window with a size of 3×3 pixels to swiftly find out the extreme value.

Fig.2. Extraction of feature points.

Fig. 2 shows the detection and location of feature points. Each point is paralleled with the surrounding 26 pixels. Then the extreme point which is greater than all adjacent points is selected as the key point.

After that, a window of $24\sigma_i \times 24\sigma_i$ on the gradient image centered on the feature point is selected to generate the feature description operators. The window is divided into 16 subdomains with a size of $9\sigma_i \times 9\sigma_i$ which have overlapping regions with size of $2\sigma_i$. Usually, the weight of the Gaussian kernel is set to $\sigma_1 = 2.5\sigma_i$ during calculating the subdomain description vector. The description vector of the subdomain can be obtained by Equation(7).

$$d_v = (\sum L_x, \sum L_y, \sum |L_x|, \sum |L_y|) \quad (7)$$

Then, the vector d_v of the subdomain is filtered by an unequal Gaussian kernel with a weight of $\sigma_2 = 1.5\sigma_i$. Ultimately, a vector with 64 dimensions is obtained according to normalizing.

The feature matching of KAZE algorithm is sensitive to parameter settings, which affects the matching accuracy to some extent. To avoid this issue, the RAN-SAC algorithm (Salehi *et al.*, 2022) is adopted to decline the mismatched pairs.

Firstly, Four noncollinear sample data is extracted from all detected feature pairs randomly, and the transformation matrix H can be calculated by the following:

$$s \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_{11} & h_{12} & h_{13} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & h_{23} \\ h_{31} & h_{32} & h_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Then the model is applied for all matching pairs to acquire the number of points and the projection error until find the optimal model whose loss function is the

smallest. The loss function can be calculated by Equation (9).

$$f_{loss} = \sum_{i=1}^k \left(x_i \frac{h_{11}x_i + h_{12}y_i + h_{13}}{h_{31}x_i + h_{32}y_i + h_{33}} \right)^2 + \left(y_i \frac{h_{21}x_i + h_{22}y_i + h_{23}}{h_{31}x_i + h_{32}y_i + h_{33}} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

It is worth noting that the number of iterations k is constantly updated. The number of iterations is determined by Equation (10).

$$k = \frac{\log(1-p)}{\log(1-\omega^m)} \quad (10)$$

Among them, p is the confidence level, ω indicates the proportion of interior points and m means the minimum value of the samples required for calculating the model.

METHODS

This section provides a detailed introduction of the proposed method. Addressing the issues of poor stitching performance and high mismatch rate for foggy images, an improved image stitching method based on local guided KAZE and dark channel prior for image enhancing is proposed in this paper. The Fig. 3 depicts the framework process of the method proposed in this article.

Fig.3. The framework process of the proposed method.

Since the shortcoming that KAZE feature points are usually very numerous and concentrated, we use KAZE algorithm with RANSAC for rough feature matching. Secondly, a local asymptotic optimization method is introduced to further eliminate mismatched point pairs. This step includes selecting the nearest neighbor of feature points by KNN, calculating and constructing local affine matrices, applying affine matrix asymptotic optimization to global images, and eliminating mismatched pairs. Thirdly, the warped images are obtained by the transformation matrix which is established by the remaining correct matching pairs.

Due to the differences in luminance and color of the input images, there are obvious seams in the final result. To improve the mosaic effect, we raise a compensation method which compensates the global luminance and color by calculating the difference of the luminance space and color space of overlapping area. Finally, a dark channel prior based image defogging method is applied to enhance the stitching results after fusing the distorted images. Moreover, the method proposed in this article can be used for stitching multiple images.

Rough matching

Nonlinear scale spaces are more stable which do not cause boundary blurring and detail loss. The KAZE algorithm detects feature points by constructing a nonlinear scale space, which can preserve more image details. The robustness of KAZE method is much better than other methods or blurred images caused by noise interference, weather, and other factors. However, the sensitivity of KAZE features to details is easy to cause mismatches. Therefore, we adopt the KAZE detection algorithm based on RANSAC for rough matching. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of KAZE feature matching results with other features in the absence of fog.

In the Fig. 4, (a) and (b) are the original images. (c) - (g) are the feature matching results of several comparison matching methods. Fig. 5 (h) shows the matching results of the KAZE feature matching based on RANSAC. It can be summarized that the ORB method has the most and concentrated matching pairs in clear images. However, excessive matching pairs can affect stitching efficiency to some extent.

The Fig. 5 shows the comparison results between KAZE feature matching and other feature matching in the case of fogged images. We increased the visibility to 20% fog in the original image and perform different feature matching on foggy images in the same intensity. The stitching results of different feature matching algorithms are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 (a) and Fig. 5 (b) are the input images that have been increased the visibility to 20% fog into the original images. Fig. 5 (c) - (g) represents the feature matching results of several common comparison methods corresponding to Fig. 4. Fig. 5 (h) shows the matching result of the KAZE features used in this paper. It can be seen that KAZE features can detect more matching pairs compared with other methods though image quality seriously affects feature matching results. ORB can detect the most feature pairs in clear images, but its performance is significantly inferior to KAZE in foggy image.

Fig.4. The comparison of KAZE feature with other features in the original images: (a) and (b) are the original images; (c) is the matching result of SURF; (d) is the matching result of Harris ; (e) is the matching result of MinEigen; (f) is the matching result of MSER; (g) is the matching result of ORB; (h) is the matching result of proposed method.

Fig.5. The comparison of KAZE feature with other features in the foggy images: (a) and (b) are the foggy images; (c) is the matching result of SURF; (d) is the matching result of Harris ; (e) is the matching result of MinEigen; (f) is the matching result of MSER; (g) is the matching result of ORB; (h) is the matching result of proposed method.

Local Progressive Optimization

Aiming at the issues of mismatch and excessive concentration of the KAZE feature pairs, a fixed point

progressive optimization solution is introduced in this paper. To ensure robustness to outlier, a set of methods for iteratively identifying other interior point sets

guided by high matching rate interior point sets are proposed, so as to obtain the best matching set.

For the N feature points obtained from rough matching, the descriptor similarity correspondence can be defined by Equation (11).

$$S = (u_j, u'_j) \quad (11)$$

where $u_j = (a_j, b_j, 1)^T$ and $u'_j = (a'_j, b'_j, 1)^T$ are the spatial homogeneous coordinates of two corresponding feature points, and j is the index of the matching pairs. To distinguish internal points from S and remove external points, the objective formula can be obtained by following:

$$y_k = \arg \max_y y^T \hat{A} x_k, y \in [0,1]^N \quad (12)$$

Where y_k is the maximum possible increase in both discrete and continuous domains. \hat{A} is a non positive definite matrix, known as a complete affinity matrix. In the continuous domain, a second order of Taylor expansion around the solution x_k of the quadratic score can be evaluated by Equation (13):

$$x^T \hat{A} x \approx x_k^T \hat{A} x_k + 2x_k^T \hat{A} (x - x_k) + (x - x_k)^T \hat{A} (x - x_k) \quad (13)$$

The last two terms of x_k can be estimated through the following equations.

$$B = x_k^T \hat{A} (y_k - x_k) \quad (14)$$

$$C = (y_k - x_k)^T \hat{A} (y_k - x_k) \quad (15)$$

The convergence condition for iteration is defined as following :

$$\frac{\|x_{k+1} - x_k\|_2}{\|x_k\|_2} < \varphi \quad (16)$$

Among them, $\| \cdot \|_2$ means the L_2 norm, and φ is a small threshold which set to 0.001 in this paper.

In order to avoid the situation that the topology of the small area in the image pair remains unchanged, multiple local affine transformations are used to approximate the image correspondence (Xia *et al.*, 2022).

We calculate the local affine transformation matrix H_i of each feature point pair. The mapping relationship of interior points (u_i, u'_i) should be consistent with the affine matrix H_i obtained from the correspondence between surrounding features. Therefore, the similarity score between corresponding relationships (u_i, u'_i) can be calculated by Equation (17).

$$S_i = \frac{2}{1 + e^{\lambda \|u'_i - H_i u_i\|_2^2}} \quad (17)$$

Where λ is a constant factor which affects the downward trend of the local affine difference $\|u'_i - H_i u_i\|_2^2$ versus the similarity score S_{ij} .

The neighbor areas of outlier in the input images may be different which almost have no common elements. The reference corresponding set R is attained by Equation (18).

$$R = (u_i, u'_i) | \frac{n_i}{K} > \varepsilon, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (18)$$

Where n_i is the number of common elements within the two K -neighborhoods of the feature points, and the ratio $\frac{n_i}{K}$ means the standard for reference points. We select four pairs of closest feature points from the reference point set R . The least square method is applied to derive the local affine matrix.

The correlation between different corresponding relationships is not only related to similarity, but also to the influence weights between them. Thus, \hat{A} can be obtained from the weight matrix W and similarity matrix C .

The non diagonal term W_{ij} is allocated as the weight of each edge $e_{ij} = (v_i, v_j)$ to quantify the impact of the tail correspondence v_j on the head correspondence v_i . The weight matrix can be obtained by follows:

$$d_{ij} = \frac{\|u_i - u_j\|_2^2}{\|\max(u) - \min(u)\|_2^2} + \frac{\|u'_i - u'_j\|_2^2}{\|\max(u') - \min(u')\|_2^2} \quad (19)$$

$$W_{ij} = \frac{2}{1 + e^{\sum_{j=1}^N d_{ij}}}, i, j = 1, \dots, N \quad (20)$$

Among them, d_{ij} deputizes the normalized distance between two corresponding relationships, and W_{ij} is the edge weight which needs to be normalized to avoid interference from image size or the number and distribution of corresponding relationships.

Given the local Affine transformation H_i , the second order edge similarity score S_{ij} can be defined as following:

$$S_{ij} = \frac{2}{1 + e^{\varepsilon (\|u'_i - u'_j\|_2^2 - \|H_i u_i - H_j u_j\|_2^2)}}, \quad (21)$$

$$i \neq j, i \in [1, N], j \in [1, N] \quad (21)$$

Among them, S_{ij} is the difference between the actual distance of two mapping points. A large value of S_{ij} indicates high affine consistency with respect to edge. The diagonal elements of the similarity matrix C is defined as Equation (22).

$$C_{ii} = S_i \quad (22)$$

Finally, The affinity matrix A is constructed as following:

$$A = W \odot C \quad (23)$$

Where \odot means the product of each element in two matrices. Obviously, the affine matrix covers the geometric consistency fraction in the global topology and is a local affine invariant, which can handle complex non rigid images.

Color difference compensation

Due to the uneven exposure and luminance of the input images, there could be obvious seams in the stitching result. In order to improve the stitching effect, we propose a mean compensation method based on local color and brightness difference. The flow chart of the compensation method is displayed in Fig. 6.

Fig.6. The flow chart of the compensation method.

Firstly, we extract the overlapping regions of warped images, which are attained by the transformation matrix in the previous step. Then, the color space and brightness space of the overlapping regions are separated to calculate the mean of the color difference and that of brightness difference respectively. The calculated means are applied to the original warped images for global brightness space compensation and global color space compensation respectively. Finally, the compensated color space and brightness space are combined into a global image. The average brightness difference and average color difference are defined as followings:

$$L_{avg} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (L_{i1} - L_{i2}) \quad (24)$$

$$A_{avg} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (A_{i1} - A_{i2}) \quad (25)$$

$$B_{avg} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (B_{i1} - B_{i2}) \quad (26)$$

Among them, L_{avg} is the average luminance difference. L_{i1} and L_{i2} are the luminance differences of the overlapping region of the two warped images. A_{avg}

and B_{avg} are the different average color difference. A_{i1} and B_{i1} are the two color spaces of the overlapping region of the one input image. Similarly A_{i2} and B_{i2} are two the colors of the other input image. We select the warped image with higher luminance space as the benchmark to adjust the global luminance space and

(a)

(b)

Fig.7. Original images.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. (a) Stitching image without compensation; (b) Stitching image with compensation.

color space of the other image. Ultimately, the compensated brightness space and color space are fused to obtain a stitching image. The two original input images are shown in Fig. 7. The Fig. 8 displays the stitching results before and after compensation.

Fig. 8 (a) shows the stitching effect without compensation, where there are obvious splicing seams in the red marked area. Fig. 8 (b) shows the splicing effect with compensation. It is easy to find that the stitching result after compensation are smoother and more even. It is sufficient to prove the effectiveness of compensation.

Image enhancing based on dark channel prior

There are some pixels in most images, which have a low value in a channel (Kokul *et al.*, 2020). If a image is represented by J , the dark channel of the image J^D can be represented as:

$$J^D = \min_{C \in \{r,g,b\}} (\min_{y \in M(x)} (J^C(y))) \quad (27)$$

Where $M(x)$ represents a square window centered on pixel x , and J^C means the dark primary colors of the three channels of the fog free image. The dark channel is obtained by performing minimal filtering on the original image. The dark channel of the image without fog except for the sky area tends to zero (He *et al.*, 2010).

After extracting the dark channel, the brightness of the dark channel in the image is used to estimate the overall atmospheric light intensity. The transmittance can be calculated by the deformation of the atmospheric scattering model.

$$\frac{I^C(x)}{A^C} = t(x) \cdot \frac{J^C(x)}{A^C} + (1 - t(x)) \quad (28)$$

Among them, represents the observed intensity, A means the global atmospheric light, and $t(x)$ is the medium transmission which is a constant. Two minimum filters are performed on both ends of the above equation. The first filter takes the minimum values for the three channels R, G, and B at both ends of the equation. The second filter takes the minimum pixel in a square area centered on the target pixel. This process is described in Equation (29).

$$\min_{y \in M(x)} \left(\min_{C \in \{r,g,b\}} \frac{I^C(x)}{A^C} \right) = t'(x) \cdot \min_{y \in M(x)} \left(\min_{C \in \{r,g,b\}} \frac{J^C(x)}{A^C} \right) + (1 - t'(x)) \quad (29)$$

Then, the transmittance is defined as following:

$$t'(x) = 1 - \min_{y \in M(x)} \left(\min_{C \in \{r,g,b\}} \frac{I^C(x)}{A^C} \right) \quad (30)$$

To make the processing results look more natural, we choose to retain a portion of the fog that covers the distant view. The parameter of defogging intensity μ is introduced and the corrected transmittance is adjusted as following:

$$t(x) = 1 - \mu \cdot \min_{y \in M(x)} \left(\min_{C \in \{r,g,b\}} \frac{I^C(x)}{A^C} \right) \quad (31)$$

After obtaining the transmittance map, the brightness of the scene can be restored according to the haze model formula. Finally, $J(x)$ is represented as Equation (32).

$$J(x) = \frac{I(x) - A}{\max(t(x), t_0)} + A \quad (32)$$

Where t_0 represents the lower limit value of atmospheric transmittance, which is taken as 0.1 in this paper. Due to the fact that the brightness of the scene is usually not as bright as that in the atmosphere, an exposure processing is applied to adjust the brightness of the image. Finally, the restored enhanced image can be obtained by calculating the R, G, and B channels of the image separately. The process of image enhancing is shown as Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Enhancing Algorithm

Input: The foggy image and the parameter of defogging intensity μ .

Output: The enhancing image.

- 1: Calculate the minimum pixel value of the input image and locate the dark channel.
 - 2: Finding the brightest pixel point in dark channel for estimating atmospheric light intensity.
 - 3: Divide the image into N blocks.
 - 4: Repeat:
 - 5: Calculate the ratio of each pixel point to atmospheric light intensity the transmission rate in each block by Equation (28).
 - 6: Calculate the transmittance according to Equation (31).
 - 4: Until all the transmittance of N blocks are calculated.
 - 5: Defog and reconstruct R, G, and B channels to obtain defogging image images by Equation (32).
-

RESULTS

In this section, we conduct experiments on two databases using different stitching algorithms to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method in this paper. The two databases in this paper are from the USI SIPI database of the University of Southern California (Mahto *et al.*, 2022)

and Ground truth database of the University of Washington (Brostow *et al.*, 2009) separately. Both databases are open source for image processing. The USI SIPI image database covers different types of images, such as antenna images, texture images, composite images and sequence images. The images in USI SIPI image database are mainly used for research purposes. The Ground truth database contains high quality and high resolution images, which designates extended duration digital lenses to those who have research on ego-motion or driving scenarios images. The emergence of this database meets the evaluation of image related algorithms. Furthermore, all of the experiments in this paper are run in the Matlab 2022b.

To comprehensively evaluate the proposed method, we contrast it with other currently popular methods in terms of intuitive renderings and quantitative assessment.

Intuitive effect

We take two images from the Ground truth Database as examples to compare the matching pairs and stitching results of the proposed method with those in other popular stitching methods. The original images are revealed in Fig. 9. Table 1 shows the comparison stitching results.

Fig. 9. *Original Images*.

The image in bottom right corner of each row represents the enlarged display of the red selected region in Table 1. On the one hand, there are obvious mismatches in the matching results of SURF algorithm. Harris, BRISK, and MSER detected fewer matching pairs. The proposed method not only detects more matching pairs, but also has higher matching accuracy. On the other hand, it is easy to discover that the proposed stitching method provides clearer details for stitching images without ghosting. The blue area in the table indicates that the proposed method preserves the details of the image well with higher contrast. The other comparison methods cannot reflect clear details.

In order to further demonstrate the robustness of the proposed algorithm in this paper, we also add a 20% visibility fog to the original image for comparative experiments of stitching. The Foggy image are displayed in Fig. 10. Table 2 shows the comparison stitching results of foggy images.

Fig. 10. *Foggy Images*.

Among them, Brisk and Harris were unable splice due to the inability to detect matching pairs. Moreover, it is impossible to splice due to less than four matching pairs detected by MSER. In Table 2, the matching pairs detected by other comparison algorithms are relatively few and the splicing results are not clear. It is obvious that the proposed method in this paper can still detect a large number of matching pairs in foggy images. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm has a clearer stitching effect due to image enhancement processing.

Quantitative evaluation

So as to comprehensively assess the availability of the proposed method, we conducted a quantitative evaluation in terms of the quantity of feature matching pairs, RMSE, MAE and processing time (Khajezadeh *et al.*, 2022; Qi *et al.*, 2020).

We randomly select eight sets of images from the databases previously mentioned and perform fuzzy processing to a certain extent. The results of several matching methods on the original images and blurred images are revealed in Table 3

It is easy to observed from Table 3 that both the proposed method and ORB algorithm can detect abundant matching pairs for the original image. But for foggy images, the proposed method can still detect a large number of matching pairs. Other methods sometimes fail to detect matching pairs when matching foggy images.

In order to sufficiently validate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, we compared it with other algorithms in terms of RMSE and MAE. For two input images I_1 and I_2 , RMSE and MAE are calculated by follows:

$$RMSE(I_1, I_2) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (p_{i1} - p_{i2})^2} \quad (33)$$

$$MAE(I_1, I_2) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |p_{i1} - p_{i2}| \quad (34)$$

Among them, N is the number of the matching pairs p_{i1} , p_{i1} and p_{i2} are the matching points in the two input images respectively. Table 4 lists the results of MAE and RMSE using the above eight group images for several different algorithms.

Table 1. The comparison results of different stitching method in original images.

Methods	Match Figure	Stitching Image
SURF[9]		
Harris [14]		
BRISK [11]		
MinEigen		
MSER [13]		
SIFT		
ORB[12]		
Our method		

Table 2. The comparison results of different stitching method in foggy images.

Methods	Match Figure	Stitching Image
SURF		
MinEigen		
MSER		Unable to splice due to insufficient matching pairs
SIFT		
ORB		
Our method		

In Table 4, BRISK and Harris methods cannot calculate MAE and RMSE values due to the lack of feature matching point pairs. The MinEigen algorithm performs well in RMSE and MAE values in some datasets. In most cases, the RMSE and the MAE of the proposed method in this paper perform better than other comparison methods.

Additionally, the processing time of the different stitching methods are also compared in this paper. The comparison results are displayed in Table 5.

It is obvious to observe that stitching based on SURF is comparatively time-saving. The processing time of ORB based splicing method is the longest.

Table 3. The comparison of the number of matching pairs on the different methods.

Data	Type	SURF	BRISK	MSER	MinEigen	Harris	ORB	Proposed
Data1	Org	69	14	20	32	19	101	667
	Fog	11	0	4	6	3	2	114
Data2	Org	123	71	19	68	36	321	769
	Fog	20	4	1	21	6	8	129
Data3	Org	205	109	51	125	87	771	912
	Fog	14	3	11	38	35	27	198
Data4	Org	474	231	135	232	157	2348	1888
	Fog	119	32	38	107	52	227	495
Data5	Org	247	63	38	389	317	3440	4354
	Fog	45	7	19	87	31	67	1322
Data6	Org	327	94	34	366	277	3575	3440
	Fog	21	6	4	53	8	32	262
Data7	Org	354	82	45	180	136	832	2662
	Fog	31	5	2	35	3	21	720
Data8	Org	151	22	18	81	43	223	694
	Fog	7	0	3	19	0	6	181

Table 4. The comparison of MAE and RMSE of different methods.

Data	Estimate	SURF	BRISK	MSER	MinEigen	Harris	ORB	Proposed
Data1	MAE	0.4196	-	0.0585	0.1816	0.3854	0.3969	0.2062
	RMSE	0.4419	-	0.0773	0.1933	0.4159	0.4293	0.2693
Data2	MAE	0.0796	0.0702	0.0989	0.075	0.0831	0.1014	0.0972
	RMSE	0.0954	0.0973	0.1324	0.1021	0.0951	0.1261	0.1226
Data3	MAE	0.1769	0.1356	0.1273	0.1193	0.1245	0.1275	0.1086
	RMSE	0.1936	0.1701	0.1615	0.1533	0.1503	0.1526	0.1139
Data4	MAE	0.1083	0.0747	0.0861	0.0867	0.0843	0.0887	0.0856
	RMSE	0.1655	0.1067	0.1027	0.1186	0.1042	0.1240	0.1116
Data5	MAE	0.0828	0.0818	0.0931	0.0600	0.0795	0.0711	0.0393
	RMSE	0.1021	0.1024	0.116	0.0798	0.0948	0.0883	0.0522
Data6	MAE	0.1833	0.0926	0.1652	0.1434	0.1297	0.1109	0.0915
	RMSE	0.1938	0.1173	0.2016	0.1833	0.1570	0.1316	0.1167
Data7	MAE	0.0823	0.0881	0.0794	0.0598	0.0812	0.0710	0.0778
	RMSE	0.1225	0.1307	0.1095	0.0801	0.1207	0.1038	0.0977
Data8	MAE	0.1376	-	0.1503	0.0870	-	0.0951	0.1487
	RMSE	0.1791	-	0.2013	0.1048	-	0.1253	0.1931

The processing time of the proposed method in this paper is relatively stable and short.

Overall, the method proposed in this paper outperforms other methods in four aspects: number of matching

pairs, RMSE, MAE and processing time. Moreover, the proposed method in this article can be applied to both clear and foggy images. The stitching effect of the proposed method performs much better than other comparison algorithms especially for blurry images.

Table 5. Comparison of the processing time of different methods.

Data	SURF	BRISK	MSER	MinEigen	Harris	ORB	Proposed
Data1	0.4337s	-	0.5232s	0.4907s	0.4429s	0.4469s	0.4202s
Data2	0.4429s	0.5473s	0.5198s	0.5022s	0.5106s	0.5235s	0.5019s
Data3	0.3320s	0.4529s	0.3371s	0.3765s	0.3760s	0.3522s	0.4047s
Data4	0.3334s	0.4517s	0.3673s	0.3908s	0.5600s	0.5355s	0.4490s
Data5	0.7292s	0.7922s	0.7099s	1.0055s	0.7312s	0.9640s	0.8270s
Data6	0.6903s	0.8045s	0.6880s	0.7274s	0.7280s	1.0415s	0.6770s
Data7	0.7441s	0.8564s	0.7927s	0.8829s	0.8153s	1.0203s	0.7365s
Data8	0.6897s	-	0.6737s	0.8282s	-	0.8322s	0.6458s

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this article, an improved stitching method based on local guided KAZE and dark channel prior for image enhancing is proposed. Firstly, the KAZE feature with RANSAC is utilized for feature coarse matching. Secondly, a local fixed point asymptotic method is introduced to optimize the global objective and eliminate mismatched pairs. Then, the transformation matrix for the remaining matching point pairs is estimated. Thirdly, color space and luminance space compensation are raised to the concatenated images to improve the unevenness of the warped images. Aiming at the problem of poor blurry image stitching effect, a dark channel prior image defogging algorithm for post-processing is applied to obtain the excellent result.

The proposed method in this article has been tested on images from both USI SIPI database and Ground truth database, and compared with several popular stitching algorithms in terms of visual effects and quantitative value. The experimental results indicate that the proposed algorithm outperforms other methods in terms of visual effect, number of feature point matching, RMSE, MAE and processing time. Furthermore, the

proposed stitching method can achieve smoother and more detailed stitching images especially for blurred images.

The proposed method can be applied for multiple areas, such as drone panoramic stitching and criminal reconnaissance. Nevertheless, in situations such as high-rise buildings with significant changes in perspective where the disparity is particularly large, the stitching effect of the proposed method cannot be accurately aligned. In future work, we will continue to explore stitching under such large parallax conditions and optimize under other challenging conditions such as low light, motion blur, or glare. In addition, due to the rapid development of deep learning, we will combine feature registration research based on deep learning to optimize the extraction of image features as future work.

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IMPROVEMENT OF YOLOV8 OBJECT DETECTION BASED ON LIGHTWEIGHT NECK MODEL FOR COMPLEX IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

With the advancement of target detection technology, the need for accurate detection of complex scenes is becoming increasingly important in various industries. This can not only improve productivity, but also ensure public safety. However, the current mainstream target detection algorithms have some problems in dealing with complex scenes, for example, some detection models are not able to detect in real time, and the accuracy of the model is degraded when facing disturbing factors such as target occlusion, and low-contrast scenes. In order for these problems to be mitigated, this paper proposes a lightweight convolution LDGConv (Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution), which is utilized to improve the YOLOv8 network model by replacing part of the traditional convolution of the Neck network with this convolution, and improving the bottleneck module in a lightweight way. In addition, we add the Coordinate Attention mechanism to the Neck part. Our proposed model improves mAP50 on the VOC dataset by 1.3% while reducing computation and parameters by 9.8% and 15.3%, respectively, compared to the original model. In the experiments on the steel surface defects dataset NEU-DET, our model overall outperforms the current mainstream detection models. The model is capable of high-precision and low-computational-cost target detection, thus saving labor costs and improving public health and safety and productivity.

Keywords: Attention Mechanism, Lightweight, Neck Networks, Target Detection.

INTRODUCTION

Target detection is a key area of computer vision research, and its main task is to achieve automatic detection and localization of objects of interest in a given image or video. For the target detection stage, it can be categorized into single-stage and two-stage algorithm types. To improve the model detection performance, some network models such as VGG (Tammima, 2019), ResNet (Li and He, 2018) and EfficientNet (Alhichri *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2020b) have been widely used in backbone for feature extraction. These networks have multi-level convolution and pooling operations to learn richer representations of image features. Especially for some target detection models such as Faster R-CNN (Ren *et al.*, 2015; Fan *et al.*, 2016; Meng *et al.*, 2018; Zhang and Shen, 2021; Yang *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2018), the depth and width of the backbone are usually increased to improve the detection performance, but this may further increase the computational effort. However, since these deep networks have more parameters and complex structures, they require greater computational effort during training and inference. To address the

problem of high computational resource requirements, networks such as MobileNet (Li *et al.*, 2018; Michele *et al.*, 2019) and Xception (Carreira *et al.*, 1998) use the convolution operation of DSC (Depthwise Separable Convolution) to reduce the complexity of the model. However, the relatively shallow network structure and reduced number of parameters may also limit the expressive power of the model, leading to relatively poor results on some more complex tasks. To enhance the robustness and generalization of the model, GhostConv (Ghost Convolution) (Cao *et al.*, 2022) divides the input channels of each convolutional layer into a main channel and a ghost channel, and uses the main channel for feature extraction and increases the number of output channels by performing blurring operations through the ghost channel. This design idea helps in areas such as lightweight network design and model compression. According to the analysis in the literature (Redmon and Farhadi, 2017), although the R-CNN family of models (evolving from R-CNN to Fast R-CNN and finally to Faster R-CNN) improves the processing efficiency by integrating the non-CNN processing part into the CNN and fully utilizing the efficient computational features of GPUs, the inference speed of Faster R-CNN is

still limited to 5 frames on GPUs, i.e. Only five images are processed per second. This speed may be insufficient for real-time applications that require high processing speed. In contrast, single-stage models such as YOLO and SSD require less memory for inference due to their lower number of parameters and floating-point operations, which not only facilitates deployment on embedded devices, but also has a significant advantage in inference speed. The YOLO model can reach a processing speed of 45 fps, while the SSD500 model can process at 19 fps, which are significantly faster than Faster R-CNN. However, the single-stage target detection model tends to sacrifice the detection accuracy of the model due to this design by simplifying the model structure to reduce the computational burden. Therefore, in terms of accuracy, such models generally have a large disadvantage.

In the field of target detection, the reliance on expensive high-performance GPUs is avoided by reducing the model parameters and computation so that it can run on lower-cost hardware, such as low- to mid-range GPUs or CPUs. Not only that, for situations where surveillance cameras need to be deployed on a large scale in urban transportation systems or public safety projects, and in surveillance systems that need to run 24/7, a lightweight target detection model also reduces the risk of overheating or overloading of the device, which not only prolongs the life of the device, but also saves a lot of electricity and maintenance costs. Reducing model parameters and calculations therefore not only optimizes technical performance, but also brings significant economic benefits.

The accuracy and lightness of target detection models are crucial in autonomous driving technology, especially when dealing with fast-moving scenes and changing street environments. Accuracy ensures that the self-driving vehicle can accurately recognize and judge various objects in the surrounding environment, such as pedestrians, other vehicles, traffic signs, and obstacles. This is crucial to ensure that the vehicle is traveling safely. If the detection accuracy is not high, it may cause the vehicle to misjudge or miss hazards, thus increasing the risk of traffic accidents. However, lightness is equally important because autonomous driving systems need to make decisions in real-time dynamic environments, and this requires very fast processing speeds because excessive delays may affect the timeliness of decisions and may even lead to danger. Therefore, the target detection model not only needs to recognize objects accurately, but also must have high computational efficiency.

Therefore, current research focuses on how to obtain higher model accuracy with lower computational effort. Based on the above background,

this paper proposes an improved lightweighting approach to optimize the Neck part of the target detection model YOLOv8 in order to reduce the computational effort and improve the performance. Neck networks play the role of adjusting and fusing feature maps in target detection. Through in-depth study of the properties and functions of Neck network, we propose a lightweight improvement method. The main innovations and contributions of this paper are as follows:

We improve the current existing methods and propose LDGConv (Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution), a convolution module with fewer parameters than Ghost Convolution, and apply it to Neck networks.

We lighten and improve the C2f by incorporating the convolution proposed in this paper, and propose and use the more lightweight C2f_LDG. The experiments demonstrate the advantages of the lightweight convolution proposed in this paper in terms of accuracy and computation.

The Coordinate Attention mechanism (Hou *et al.*, 2021) is also added to the Neck network to achieve high efficiency and high accuracy detection performance in complex and dense scenes. And it is demonstrated in the VOC dataset that the model can obtain satisfactory results in terms of accuracy with low computational effort.

In order to verify the robustness and generalization ability of the improved model, we compare it with the original model as well as mainstream models using the steel surface defect dataset.

Through our research, we have made significant progress in the field of target detection in a computationally resource-constrained environment, which is of positive significance for the advancement of the field.

RELATED WORK

YOLO

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) series is the most widely used single-stage target detection algorithm today, and the constant version updates are the main reason for its leading position. The first version of this family, YOLO (Redmon *et al.*, 2016), was launched in 2016 and was trained using an end-to-end approach, where feature maps were extracted from the input images by a convolutional neural network, classification and regression were performed by a fully connected network, and the results were filtered

using NMS (Non-Maximum Suppression) (Jiang *et al.*, 2019). Subsequently, the YOLOv2 (Redmon and Farhadi, 2017) algorithm was introduced in 2017, which adds a BN (Batch normalization) (Liu *et al.*, 2018) layer after the convolutional layer to increase the convergence speed and reduce overfitting, and uses the K-Means method for the prediction of the number of anchors. YOLOv3 (Tian *et al.*, 2019), on the other hand, uses Darknet-53 as the backbone network for feature extraction, and FPN (Feature Pyramid Network) (Zhu *et al.*, 2022) as the Neck part, which fuses high-resolution and low-resolution feature maps by up-sampling and residual concatenation, and the YOLO series has been using the Neck network to process and rationally utilize the feature maps extracted from different stages of the backbone network since YOLOv3. The CSPNet (Wang *et al.*, 2020a) network architecture, introduced in 2019, enhances the learning capabilities of CNNs and provides a lot of insight into improvements after the YOLO series. YOLOv4 (Gai *et al.*, 2023) and YOLOv5 (Wu *et al.*, 2021) are both available in 2020, the former combines Darknet53 with CSPNet as CSPDarknet53 to improve network efficiency and accuracy, while the latter improves on CSPDarknet53 and designs the C3 structure by borrowing from CSPNet in order for the model to learn more features.

Fig. 1. *C2f structure of the YOLOv8 model*

YOLOv8, on the other hand, was proposed in 2023, combining the ideas of CSPNet and ELAN (Zhang *et al.*, 2022b) networks, and designing a lighter C2f structure to replace the previous C3 structure, the structure adopts the shuffling idea of CSPNet and the concept of residual structure to obtain richer information about the gradient flow and

better utilize the upstream information. The number of stacked C2f structures is controlled by the parameter "N", which can be different for different scales of models. The C2f structure of the YOLOv8 model is shown in Fig. 1, which shows that the C2f module enriches the gradient flow of the model by connecting more branches across the layers. The Bottleneck module in the C2f structure is shown in Fig. 2, where CBS denotes the combination of ordinary convolution, batch normalization and SiLU activation function combinations.

Fig. 2. *Bottleneck Module Structure Diagram*

Although the C2f structure enriches the gradient flow of the model and enhances the feature representation of the model through multi-branch cross-layer connections, its inclusion of a large number of convolution operations also leads to the accumulation of a large amount of redundant information, which may result in more parameter requirements and computational resource consumption. YOLOv5s-M (Ren *et al.*, 2023) proposed in 2023 that the method of utilizing increasing the size of the detection model by adding more detection heads provides a 3.9% improvement in mAP metrics compared to the original model, but the computation and parameters of the model increase to 2.52 and 5.19 times that of the original model, respectively, which further increases the model's complexity and makes it difficult to be deployed in computationally resource-constrained devices. YOLOv8-GAM-Wise (Xiong *et al.*, 2024) was proposed in 2024, which incorporates Global Attention Mechanism (Zhou *et al.*, 2023) into the backbone network, Global Attention Mechanism can dynamically adjust the weights based on the importance of different parts of the input sequence, allowing the model to focus more on the information that is more important to the information that is more important for the current task. However, because the Global Attention Mechanism needs to weight the whole sequence, the computational complexity increases significantly when the sequence is long, resulting in the inference time of the model becoming 1.26 times of the original, not only that, because the backbone network feature map needs to be sent to the Neck network for a series of feature fusion, when the number of channels is reduced in the convolutional layer or the spatial dimension is reduced by the pooling layer, the features selected and weighted by

the attention mechanism will be more important to the task. Information of the features selected and weighted by the mechanism may be diluted, causing the model to improve the mAP metric by only 0.1% with a large increase in computational parameters and inference time. Therefore, the focus of the research in this paper is to construct a lightweight network to reduce the computational burden of the model, and to ensure that the model maintains accuracy with a certain degree of stability and robustness, in order to develop a lightweight model that is general and easy to deploy.

CONVOLUTIONAL OPERATIONS IN LIGHTWEIGHT MODE

CNN-based detection models are widely used in various aspects, for example, in the application of tribal dress recognition (Rabbi *et al.*, 2023), by extracting the spatial features and texture information in the dress image, the dress style features of different tribes are obtained, and these features enable the model to accurately recognize and differentiate the dresses of different tribes. While in the medical field (Tawfeeq *et al.*, 2021), Convolutional Neural Networks and heat maps are utilized to predict salient features in medical images, CNN-based models can learn to detailed features in the images and correlate these features with specific diseases or lesions. In the intelligent management of agriculture, CNN-based models also show important value, such as the literature (Mg *et al.*, 2025) proposes to use the improved YOLOv8 model to realize the accurate detection of cattle, combined with the customized tracking algorithm and the motion feature analysis, to construct a fully automated calving time prediction system, which significantly improves the automation level of livestock management. However, in some cases, models need to be deployed on multiple platforms, such as mobile devices, cloud servers, embedded systems, and so on. In these usage environments, lightweight convolution can significantly reduce the number of parameters, computation, and memory consumption of the model, allowing the model to run efficiently under constrained resources, thus reducing the cost of development and deployment.

Ghost Convolution and DWConv (Depthwise Convolution) are common and efficient lightweight convolution operations, and they are usually widely used in lightweight models.

The traditional convolution operation is to first convolve each channel of the input feature map with a convolution kernel separately, and then sum the results of all the channels to get an output feature map. If the

number of output channels is 3, the above steps need to be repeated 3 times, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. *Conventional Convolutional Operations*

The Depthwise Convolution operation is shown in Fig. 4, which applies only one convolutional kernel to each output channel, i.e., there is only one corresponding convolutional kernel and input channel for each output channel. It allows the extraction of feature information for each channel and reduces the computational burden of the model by reducing a large amount of computation relative to the traditional convolution operation.

Fig. 4. *Depthwise Convolution Operation*

Ghost Convolution effectively reduces the number of parameters and computational complexity by dividing the input feature map into two parts, i.e., primary and secondary paths. As shown in Fig. 5, the primary path utilizes only a portion of the channels for ordinary convolution operation, while the secondary path uses an inexpensive Depthwise Convolution to linearly map the output feature maps of the primary path. Afterwards, the two are spliced to achieve the number of output channels, and finally the output feature map is obtained. Depthwise Convolution through auxiliary paths helps to increase the perceptual field and information transfer capability of the model. This in turn improves the nonlinear representation and generalization ability of the model.

Fig. 5. *Ghost Convolution Operation*

Compare ordinary convolution operation to Depthwise Convolution and Ghost Convolution in terms of computation.

The operation of generating n feature maps in all convolutional layers can be expressed by Equation 1 as.

$$Y = X \times f + b \quad (1)$$

where $X \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times h \times w}$ denotes the input to the convolution, c denotes the number of input channels, h and w denote the height and width of the input feature map, respectively, $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h' \times w'}$ and there are n channels to output the feature map, h' and w' are the height and width of the output feature map, and f is the convolution filter of the layer, which has a kernel size $a \times a$, and b is the bias term.

The ordinary convolution operation is computed as:

$$n \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot a \cdot a \quad (2)$$

The Depthwise Convolution operation is computed as:

$$n \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot 1 \cdot a \cdot a \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the computational effort of the Depthwise Convolution operation is about $1/c$ that of the ordinary convolution.

Let the size of the linear arithmetic kernel be $r \times r$, and each basic feature corresponds to s redundant features, $c \gg s$. Given that the original method obtains m feature maps, and that there is constancy in the transformation process of Ghost Module, the actual effective transformations are:

$$m \cdot (s-1) = \frac{n}{s} \cdot (s-1) \quad (4)$$

So the calculation for Ghost Convolution is:

$$\frac{n}{s} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot a \cdot a + (s-1) \cdot \frac{n}{s} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot r \cdot r \quad (5)$$

Dividing the computation of the ordinary convolution operation by the computation of the Ghost Convolution operation.

$$\frac{n \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot a \cdot a}{\frac{n}{s} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot a \cdot a + (s-1) \cdot \frac{n}{s} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot r \cdot r} \approx s \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the computational effort of the Ghost Convolution operation is about $1/s$ of the ordinary convolution operation.

ATTENTION MECHANISM

Single-stage algorithms have the advantage of fast detection, but how to improve accuracy while maintaining speed is a key issue in target detection research. In computer vision, the attention mechanism plays an important role. The attention mechanism was first applied to RNN (Mnih *et al.*, 2014), which can help the model to focus on regions or features related to the target, thus improving the accuracy and efficiency of detection. In the target detection task, the attention mechanism makes the model more accurate and robust by weighting and conditioning the important regions and features in the image.

In the current construction of lightweight networks, traditional attention mechanisms such as the SE module (Humphreys and Sui, 2016) and Channel Attention mechanism (Bastidas and Tang, 2019) mainly focus on inter-channel information, but ignore the importance of spatial location information. Although the subsequently developed CBAM (Fu *et al.*, 2021) captures positional attention information by using convolution after reducing the number of channels, this approach can only deal with local relationships and lacks the ability to capture long-distance spatial relationships. Although DANet (Dual Attention Network) (Li *et al.*, 2020) improves the accuracy of feature representation by integrating local features and global dependencies through its unique positional attention module and channel attention module, its excessive complexity leads to significant limitations on real-time processing and resource-constrained devices as well, and thus is not applicable to lightweight networks.

In order to solve the above problems, researchers have proposed the Coordinate Attention mechanism (Hou *et al.*, 2021). The introduction of the Coordinate Attention mechanism is particularly suitable for lightweight networks because it significantly improves the performance by optimizing the parameters and computational complexity without significantly increasing the computational burden. This mechanism is able to extract more representative

feature information by finely weighting the channel dimensions of the input feature map. This mechanism not only focuses on inter-channel information, but also incorporates spatial features by assigning weights to each location that reflect the importance of each location in the task at hand, and is used to weight the input sequence so that the model can more accurately focus on key locations. The Coordinate Attention mechanism provides a solution for lightweight networks to significantly improve spatial perception while maintaining efficiency. significantly improving spatial perception. Therefore, in this paper, the Coordinate Attention mechanism is used to weight and adjust the channel dimensions of the input feature map to extract more representative feature information.

The Coordinate Attention mechanism module enhances the network's ability to learn features by transforming an intermediate feature tensor X and later outputting a tensor Y of the same size.

$$X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_c] \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C} \quad (7)$$

$$Y = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_c] \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C} \quad (8)$$

The implementation process of the Coordinate Attention mechanism is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Coordinate Attention Mechanism Structure Diagram

The Coordinate Attention mechanism first performs global average pooling of the input feature maps in the width and height directions, respectively, to obtain the feature maps in the corresponding directions. At the same time, the mechanism also encodes the location information as shown in Equation 9 and Equation 10.

$$z_c^h(h) = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{0 \leq i < W} x_c(h, i) \quad (9)$$

$$z_c^w(w) = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{0 \leq j < H} x_c(j, w) \quad (10)$$

Then the feature maps in both directions of width and height of the obtained global receptive field are spliced together, after which they are fed into the convolution module with a shared convolution kernel of 1×1 to make their dimensionality reduced, and then the batch normalized feature map F_1 is fed into the Sigmoid activation function to obtain the feature map f , as shown in Equation 11.

$$f = \delta \left(F_1 \left(\left[z^h, z^w \right] \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

Then the feature map f is sliced into f^h and f^w along the height and width, and then two 1×1 convolution kernels F_h and F_w are used to convolve f^h and f^w respectively to obtain a tensor with the same number of channels as the input X . Finally after Sigmoid activation function the attention weights α^h and α^w are obtained for the feature map in height and width respectively, as shown in Equation 12 and Equation 13.

$$\alpha^h = \sigma \left(F_h \left(f^h \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\alpha^w = \sigma \left(F_w \left(f^w \right) \right) \quad (13)$$

The obtained attentional weights α^h and α^w will be calculated by multiplicative weighting, and finally the feature map with attentional weights in both width and height directions will be obtained as shown in Equation 14.

$$y_c(i, j) = x_c(i, j) \times \alpha_c^h(i) \times \alpha_c^w(j) \quad (14)$$

METHOD

IMPROVE NETWORK STRUCTURE WITH YOLOV8N

The C2f structure in YOLOv8 plays a key role in feature enhancement and information fusion in the network, but it also poses some problems. The feature map information output from the YOLOv8 Neck network contains features at multiple resolutions, and the C2f structure enhances the feature representation of the model, which helps to better capture multi-scale information about the target. However, this also means

Fig. 7. YOLOv8n-improve model structure

that it performs a large number of standard convolution operations on feature maps of different resolutions. This leads to feature redundancy as the information in the feature maps is somehow extracted and represented repeatedly.

Although the C2f module improves the accuracy of the algorithm, it accumulates a large amount of redundant information while increasing the feature expressiveness, which may lead to more parameter requirements and computational resource consumption. This may limit the deployment and application of the model in resource-constrained environments. To alleviate these issues, this study proposes an improved network structure based on YOLOv8n. The specific improvement is shown in Fig. 7.

As shown in Fig. 7, the image is first fed into the model and processed through the three main parts of the network: the Trunk (solid box a), the Neck (solid box b) and the Head (solid box c). The Trunk starts with two convolution operations using a 3x3 kernel with a step size of 2. After several convolution operations and a C2f feature enhancement module, the feature map reaches the Neck part. In the Neck part, after the SPPF spatial pyramid pooling module, we first introduce the Coordinate Attention mechanism before the up-sampling phase for feature fusion of different resolution feature maps in the Neck network and before the down-sampling phase.

Coordinate Attention mechanism By focusing more precisely on important locations or regions, the model can reduce the processing of unnecessary information, thus reducing redundant feature information and improving efficiency and performance. To further reduce the model complexity, we use the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module proposed in this paper for the downsampling part in the Neck network. The feature map will fuse feature information of different sizes after upsampling as well as after downsampling. After feature fusion, feature enhancement is performed using the C2f.LDG module proposed in this paper. Finally the feature map fused with different levels of feature information is fed into the Head part of the network. In the Head part, three Detect modules process and predict the feature maps of different sizes in order to capture the detection targets of different sizes to obtain the final detection map.

MORE LIGHTWEIGHT CONVOLUTION OPERATIONS

In order to alleviate the large amount of feature redundancy caused by repeated extraction and representation of information in the feature map in Neck networks, which makes the model need to take up more parameters and computational resources, this paper proposes an effective convolution method that further combines Ghost Convolution

with Depthwise Convolution, namely LDGConv (Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution) module. Depthwise Convolution is a deep convolution operation that can effectively capture the spatial features of the input data while the number of parameters is small, and its main focus is on the feature transformations within the input channel. Ghost Convolution divides the input feature map into two parts, and without changing the size of the output feature mapping, the total number of parameters required and the computational complexity have been reduced. Therefore, we combine Depthwise Convolution and Ghost Convolution to further utilize the lightweight feature of Depthwise Convolution and the feature utilization of Ghost Convolution, and use low-cost linear transformation to generate many feature maps that can fully reveal the intrinsic feature information, in order to reduce the feature redundancy. Finally, channel shuffle operation is used for interaction and information transfer between different parts. This increases the expressive power of the model and enables it to better capture relevant features in the input data.

The specific steps of the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution operation are as follows.

First use half of the channels for the Ghost Convolution convolution operation, the computation of this part is:

$$\frac{1}{s} \cdot \frac{n}{2} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot a \cdot a \quad (15)$$

where c denotes the number of input channels, n denotes the number of output channels, h' and w' denote the height and width of the output feature map, and the kernel size is $a \cdot a$. s is the number of redundant features corresponding to each basic feature, and $c \gg s$.

Using the other half of the output channel the output of Ghost Convolution is subjected to the Depthwise Convolution operation, the computation of this part is:

$$\frac{n}{2} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot 1 \cdot a \cdot a \quad (16)$$

So the computation of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution operation is:

$$\frac{n}{2} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot \left(\frac{c+s}{s} \right) \cdot a \cdot a \quad (17)$$

Because of $c \gg s$, the computation of ordinary convolution operation is close to $2 * s$ times the

computation of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution operation.

Fig. 8. Channel shuffle operation

The two results of the deep convolution of Ghost Convolution and Depthwise Convolution are then spliced together to ensure that the two branches exchange information. Finally, the channel shuffle operation is performed, the splicing result is first divided into two parts according to the number of channels, and the channels of the two parts are interleaved in order, as shown in Fig. 8. The richness of the features and the expressive power of the model can be improved by the shuffle operation, which allows the model to mix information more efficiently between successive layers and ensures the exchange of information across the feature channels. The structure of the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution structure diagram

Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution generates a number of intrinsic feature mappings in a cost-effective manner and then utilizes linear operations to increase the number of channels. This approach further reduces the model volume and reveals deeper information about the intrinsic features. Finally, interaction and information transfer between different parts is facilitated by using channel shuffle operations to enhance the expressive power of the model.

BOTTLENECK MODULE IMPROVEMENT

The C2f structure of YOLOv8 serves as a feature enhancement and information fusion in the network in order to better capture the multi-scale information of the target. The output feature map information contains feature map information at multiple resolutions, which enhances the feature representation of the model. By extracting features at different resolutions, the model can more comprehensively capture relevant features in the input data, thus improving target recognition and understanding. Although the C2f module, improves the accuracy of the algorithm, it contains a large number of standard convolutions, resulting in increased model parameters and complexity.

In order to further lighten the model, the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module proposed above is combined with Bottleneck. The structure of the LDG Bottleneck module is shown in Fig. 10, which consists of two Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution modules stacked together for feature mapping processing in the network. The first Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module is used as an extension layer to increase the number of channels, and the second Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module is used to reduce the number of channels to match the number of input channels. Finally, the shortcut function is implemented in order to speed up the convergence of the model and improve the accuracy of the model through the use of residual concatenation.

Fig. 10. LDG Bottleneck Module Structure

The C2f.LDG structure is shown in Fig. 11, where the LDG Bottleneck replaces the Bottleneck module in the original C2f structure so that the model has enough information to understand the input data. This improvement reduces the redundant information without increasing the network parameters and effectively improves the speed of the model to understand the image information. The detection accuracy of the network is guaranteed while realizing the light weight of the network.

Fig. 11. C2f.LDG Structure Diagram

EXPERIMENT AND RESULT ANALYSIS

EXPERIMENT ENVIRONMENT

Table 1 describes the software and hardware environments used for model training and testing.

Table 1. Experiment environment

Hardware and Software	Models and Versions
CPU	AMD R5 5600
GPU	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060Ti
OS	Windows 10
Development Language	Python 3.8.17
Deep Learning Framework	PyTorch 1.12.0
Image size	640*640
Optimizer	Adam
Initial learning rate	0.01
Final learning rate	0.01
Optimizer weight decay	0.0005
Warmup epochs	3.0
Warmup initial momentum	0.8
Warmup initial bias lr	0.1
Momentum	0.937

Fig. 12. Comparison of the trend of mAP before and after adding the module

Fig. 13. Detection effect of VOC dataset

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ABLATION EXPERIMENTS

The ablation experiment dataset used in this paper is Pascal VOC 2007+2012, which has 21503 images that can be categorized into 20 classes, including people, TV, sofa, car, cat, etc. The "Pascal VOC 2007 train+val" and all the "Pascal VOC 2012" images are used as the training set. Among them, "Pascal VOC 2007 train+val" and all "Pascal VOC 2012" images are used as the training set, which consists of a total of 16551 images, and the rest of the images are used as the training set. "Pascal VOC 2007 test"

4952 images are used as test set and validation set. In this paper on the Pascal VOC2007+2012 dataset, the hyperparameters were set to epoch 100 and batch size 32 during training.

Through ablation experiments, it is verified that the application of the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution module to the YOLO model of the Neck network reduces a large number of parameters and computations and guarantees model accuracy. The metrics of mAP, parameter size, GFLOP (gigafloating point operations per second), and model size are compared in the same experimental setup, and F_1

scores are introduced to further evaluate the model's precision and recall in a comprehensive manner, as shown in Equation 18.

$$F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (18)$$

The results of the experiment are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Ablation Experiment Results

LDGCConv	CA	C2f.LDG	mAP50(%)	Parameters(M)	GFLOPs	F_1 (%)	Model size(MB)
			75.2	3.01	8.2	71.3	5.94
✓			75.6	2.88	8.0	71.8	5.70
	✓		76.2	3.02	8.2	71.6	5.99
		✓	75.6	2.67	7.5	71.9	5.34
✓		✓	76.1	2.54	7.4	72.3	5.09
✓	✓	✓	76.5	2.55	7.4	72.5	5.14

A comparison of the trend of the evolution of the mAP indicator with epoch before and after adding the module is shown in Fig. 12.

The detection effect in the VOC dataset is shown in Fig. 13, where (a) is the original image, (b) is the detection effect of YOLOv8n, (c) is the detection effect of the improved model YOLOv8n-improve proposed in this paper, and (d) shows the ground truth sample box. The Precision-Recall curves for each class and the Average Precision for each class are shown in Fig. 14, where (a) is the Precision-Recall curve of the original YOLOv8n, and (b) is the Precision-Recall curve of the improved model YOLOv8n-improve.

(a) YOLOv8n

(b) YOLOv8n-improve

Fig. 14. PR curves for target detection models

From Table 2, it can be seen that the improved algorithm adopts a more efficient network structure for YOLOv8n, which improves the mAP and F_1 scores to a certain extent, and reduces the number of parameters and computation of the model. It is also demonstrated that the C2f.LDG module and Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution effectively reduce the number of parameters and computation of the model without reducing the accuracy of the algorithm. The introduction of Coordinate Attention mechanism only increases a small number of parameters, which effectively improves the detection accuracy. Combining the above improvements with the YOLOv8n algorithm can minimize the model volume, with only 2.55M model parameters and 7.4G computation, which are reduced by 15.3% and 9.8%, respectively. The weight file size of the model is reduced by 13.4%.

As can be seen from Fig. 12, the addition of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution and C2f.LDG modules in the Neck network makes the model reduce the computational amount while the accuracy is steadily improved, which further proves the effectiveness of the method, which not only reduces the redundant features, but also promotes the interaction and information transfer between the different parts, and improves the transfer effect of the features in order to improve the stability of the model. The introduction of Coordinate Attention in the original Neck network reduces information loss and better establishes spatial relationships, which enables the network to better understand the image content and significantly improves the detection performance. While the addition of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution and C2f.LDG lightweight module to lighten the Neck network, in the case of sparser relevant features, makes Coordinate Attention capture less spatial structure and correlation information between features in the input data, leading to a certain degree of reduction in the magnitude of the enhancement to the performance of the model, nevertheless, the Coordinate Attention effectively improves the detection efficiency and performance by reducing the processing of low-value information while occupying very few parameters.

Fig. 13 shows that accurate target detection for occluded targets or images with dimly lit scenes is a challenging task due to the fact that a portion of the target features are difficult to obtain, and the improved model in this paper can make better detection results in some of these types of scenes while consuming less computational resources than the original model, reflecting the feasibility of the proposed method.

Fig. 15. Confusion matrix for detection models

As shown in Fig. 14, the experimental results indicate that the improved YOLOv8n-improve model exhibits higher detection accuracy in most target categories, especially in the recognition tasks of occlusion-susceptible objects (e.g., diningtable, sofa, motorbike) and small-scale targets (e.g., bird, pottedplant), and its average precision (Average Precision, AP) is significantly improved compared to the baseline model. This phenomenon fully verifies the effectiveness of the proposed optimization strategy in complex scenarios, and indicates that the algorithmic improvement significantly enhances the model’s ability to capture occlusion-sensitive targets and small-scale features, which provides theoretical support for improving the robustness of the target detection system.

COMPARATIVE EXPERIMENTS ON LIGHTWEIGHT MODELS

To further validate the performance of the lightweight model proposed in this paper, we use

other lightweight convolutional modules added to the YOLOv8n model for comparison in the VOC dataset. In our experiments we compare Ghost Convolution as a convolutional operation for downsampling in Neck networks with Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution operation as a convolutional operation for downsampling in Neck networks, and at the same time we perform experiments comparing GSConv+VoVGSCSP (Zhao and Song, 2023) with LDGConv+C2f_LDG. In order to test the effect of the lightweight module on the overall model, we replace the downsampling convolution and feature enhancement modules in the backbone network with the lightweight convolution and lightweight feature enhancement modules based on the previous ones. The experimental results are shown in Table 3. And we also use ShuffleNetV2 (Ma *et al.*, 2018), EfficientNetV2 (Tan and Le, 2021) as a Backbone network for YOLOv8n model in order to build a lightweight target detection model to compare with the method in this paper, and the experimental results are shown in Table 4. Fig. 15 shows the

confusion matrix for each model in Table 4, where (a) is YOLOv8n, (b) is ShuffleNetV2+YOLOv8n, (c) is EfficientNetV2+YOLOv8n, and (d) is YOLOv8n+LDGConv+C2f_LDG.

Table 3. *Lightweight module comparison experiment*

Model	Backbone	Neck	mAP50(%)	Parameters (M)	GFLOPs
YOLOv8n			75.2	3.01	8.2
YOLOv8n+GhostConv		✓	75.5	2.92	8.1
	✓		74.9	2.73	7.7
YOLOv8n+LDGConv		✓	75.6	2.88	8.0
	✓		74.6	2.59	7.4
YOLOv8n+GSCConv+VoVGSCSP		✓	75.9	2.81	7.4
	✓		73	2.53	6.1
YOLOv8n+LDGConv+C2f_LDG		✓	76.1	2.54	7.4
	✓		72.5	1.95	6

Table 4. *Comparison of lightweight detection models*

Model	mAP50(%)	Parameters(M)	GFLOPs
YOLOv8n	75.2	3.01	8.2
ShuffleNetV2+YOLOv8n	61.2	1.83	5.1
EfficientNetV2+YOLOv8n	60.9	2.13	2.6
YOLOv8n+LDGConv+C2f_LDG	76.1	2.54	7.4

As can be seen from Table 3, the reasonable use of lightweight convolution in the model Neck network can not only further lighten the model, but also improve the accuracy to some extent. This is because Neck networks are usually used to process features from different levels and scales, and synthesize them to form a more semantically informative feature representation. Lightweight modules have the flexibility to perform feature selection and combination in this process to accommodate features from different scales. This flexibility allows the lightweight module to better adapt to multi-scale target detection tasks while maintaining a certain level of accuracy. As for the lightweight improvement of the Model Neck network, the Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution and C2f_LDG lightweight modules proposed in this paper have better performance on the VOC dataset compared to Ghost Convolution and GSCConv+VoVGSCSP.

From the comparison data in Table 4, YOLOv8n+LDGConv+C2f_LDG achieves a significant increase in mAP50 while maintaining a lower number of parameters, which proves the effectiveness of the lightweighting improvement of the Neck network in this paper; The other two comparison models, although significantly compressing the parameters through EfficientNetV2 and ShuffleNetV2 lightweight backbones, respectively, also lead to a serious drop in the mAP50 index, reflecting the serious degradation of feature extraction ability due to excessive lightweight backbones, especially in complex scenarios with serious semantic information loss, highlighting the devastating impact of simply compressing backbones on detection accuracy's destructive impact.

As seen from the confusion matrix comparison in Fig. 15, the improved algorithm in this paper

significantly improves the detection accuracy in most of the key categories by optimizing the Neck network structure, e.g., the normalized accuracies of the categories of car, bird, and aeroplane are higher than those of the other models. While the lightweight Backbone models EfficientNetV2+YOLOv8n and ShuffleNetV2+YOLOv8n significantly increase the false detection rate in complex and smaller targets, such as pottedplant, bottle, person. It shows that over-compression of the backbone network leads to degradation of feature extraction capability. The improved algorithm mitigates the accuracy loss problem by balancing Neck optimization and lightweight design while maintaining efficient inference.

To summarize, in the feature extraction stage, in order to improve the prediction speed, the CNN model usually needs to transform the input image step by step through the Backbone layer to transfer the spatial information to the channel dimension gradually. However, each compression of the spatial feature map and channel expansion may lead to the loss of some semantic information. In this case, the dense convolution operation maximally preserves the connections hidden between each channel, while the lightweight convolution completely cuts off these connections, which will further lead to feature information loss. Therefore, a more appropriate approach is usually to use lightweight convolution only in Neck networks, which can reduce the computational burden while adapting more flexibly to multi-scale detection tasks, thus improving the performance and efficiency of the model.

Fig. 16. *Scatterplot of the model's parameters and mAP metrics*

COMPARATIVE EXPERIMENTS WITH DIFFERENT MODELS

Target detection is one of the important applications in the field of computer vision, which can accurately identify and locate objects in images, reduce labor costs, and have a wide range of applications. For example, it is important in the field of public safety, industry and agriculture. However, there

Fig. 17. Comparison of Loss value in validation phase before and after improvement

are various problems that need to be solved in complex scenes, such as a large number of objects, different backgrounds and lighting conditions, occlusion and overlapping, etc., so it is a challenging task to realize the detection of complex scenes. The accuracy of the YOLOv8n-improved model has been validated on the VOC dataset, and in order to further validate the robustness of the improved model proposed in this paper, experiments are conducted on the publicly available steel surface defects dataset NEU-DET as its application to complex scenarios, whose diverse crack shapes and sizes, as well as the existence of different lighting conditions in real production environments are part of the reasons for its use as a complex scenario. The dataset contains six main types of defects on steel surfaces. The respective defects are Cracking, Inclusion, Patches, Pitted_surface, Rolled_in_Scale and Scratches. There are 300 images for each defect, totaling 1800 images. The dataset is divided into training set, validation set and test set in the ratio of 8:1:1. We trained on this dataset with epoch set to 300 and batch size set to 16. In addition to this, current state-of-the-art target detection algorithms such as YOLOv8-GAM-Wise (Xiong *et al.*, 2024), YOLOv5s, YOLOv7-tiny, YOLOv8n, NanoDet-Plus-m (Huan *et al.*, 2024), and DCNN (Zhang *et al.*, 2022a) algorithm for surface defect detection, as well as CenterNet (Nazir *et al.*, 2021) based on Anchor-Free, are compared to the improved model proposed in this paper on the NEU-DET dataset Comparison experiments are conducted, and the experimental results are shown in Table 5, where the FPS metric is calculated based on the inference time per image, which reflects the average number of inference images per second. In order to make the data more intuitive, we plotted the scatter plots of the parameters and

mAP metrics of each model as shown in Fig. 16, and the comparison plots of the box loss, classification loss and distribution focus loss between the improved model proposed in this paper and the original model in each epoch verification process are shown in Fig. 17. The detection effect of the model in the NEU-DET dataset is shown in Fig. 18, where (a) is the original image, (b) is the detection effect of YOLOv8n, (c) is the detection effect of YOLOv8-GAM-Wise, (d) is the detection effect of YOLOv8n-improve, and (e) shows the ground truth sample box.

Table 5. Comparative Experimental Results of Different Models

Model	mAP50(%)	Parameters(M)	GFLOPs	F_1 (%)	FPS
CenterNet	73.4	32.67	70.2	71.5	45.9
YOLOv8-GAM-Wise	80.2	42.45	92.4	75	54.7
YOLOv5s	78.7	7.03	15.8	74.1	75.6
YOLOv7-tiny	76.6	6.02	13.1	73.8	87.2
DCNN	82.6	40.9	89.8	78.2	63.1
NanoDet-Plus-m	79.3	2.44	3	74.6	124.5
YOLOv8n	79.1	3.01	8.2	74.3	112.4
YOLOv8n-improve	80.5	2.55	7.4	74.5	117.6

As can be seen from the experimental results in Table 5, in terms of steel surface defect detection, the convolutional neural network (CNN) is able to extract a lot of useful features on the picture of steel surface defects, which play an effective role in promoting the detection model to accurately identify and localize the defects. From Fig. 16, it can be seen that the improved model in this paper has certain advantages over some mainstream target detection models in terms of model parameters and mAP indexes combined performance, and the improved algorithm proposed in this paper is better than the original model in terms of model size and inference speed. Although YOLOv8-GAM-Wise has good detection accuracy on the steel surface defects dataset, it is based

Fig. 18. *Effectiveness of NEU-DET defect detection*

on YOLOv8m as the baseline model and introduces the Global Attention Mechanism for improvement, and the complex model makes it underperform in inference speed. Although the improved model in this paper falls short of NanoDet-Plus-m in terms of model size and inference speed, the mAP metrics are improved by 1.4% and 1.2% compared to the original model of YOLOv8n and NanoDet-Plus-m, respectively, and the FPS metrics of the three reach more than 100, which can satisfy the real-time demand of most industrial applications.

Compared with the Anchor-Free based CenterNet, the proposed model in this paper has more significant advantages in steel surface defect detection, increasing the mAP by 7.1%, reducing the amount of model parameters by 30.12M, which is only 7.8% of that of CenterNet, and decreasing the computation amount of the model by 62.8GFLOPs, which is only 10.5% of that of CenterNet. Although the mAP metric of DCNN has a 2.1% improvement compared to YOLOv8n-improve, the model uses a dense cross-stage partial Darknet backbone network for feature extraction resulting in a larger computational resource requirement compared to the lightweight model. requirements compared to the lightweight model, and at the same time the inference speed is difficult to meet the real-time performance. Fig. 17 shows that compared with the original YOLOv8n model, the YOLOv8n-improve model fits faster, performs well,

and is stable, which further proves that the model improvement in this study is effective. Fig. 18 shows that in the picture of steel surface defects, the influence of various texture shapes, low contrast between the background and defects, and uneven brightness causes the algorithmic model to be difficult to detect the defect types quickly and accurately, and the method proposed in this paper mitigates the adverse effect on the inspection task caused by this problem to a certain extent, and it can effectively reduce the rate of rejects in the production process.

In summary, the lightweight model proposed in this paper has the advantages of small model size and low computation under the guarantee of detection accuracy, which makes it easy to be deployed on some terminal detection devices with weak computational capabilities and limited computational resources.

DISCUSSION

Currently, deep learning based object detectors have achieved great success in the field of target detection. Among them, Transformer-based and CNNs-based approaches are the two main technical tools. Transformer-based detectors are able to capture global contextual information by introducing an attention mechanism, which improves the recognition ability of detectors for complex scenes and occlusions.

However, the high computational complexity of the Transformer model leads to certain latency problems in real-time applications. In contrast, CNN-based detectors are still the preferred choice in the industry due to their simple structure, high computational efficiency, and the combination of convolution and pooling to make the network have certain shift-invariant and equivariance, so CNN-based detection models are still the preferred choice in the industry. In addition, CNN-based detectors can further enhance their performance by introducing some improved techniques. For example, the convolution proposed in this paper combines the advantages of Ghost Convolution and Depthwise Convolution to increase the expressive power of the model so that it can better capture the relevant features in the input data. Think about the application of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution in Neck networks in terms of the generalization ability of the model. Neck networks are usually responsible for performing feature fusion and information transfer to extract richer and more abstract features, effectively enhancing the generalization ability of the model. However, the advantages of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution may be less obvious in backbone networks. This is because in backbone networks, the main burden of computation comes from dealing with more details and local information, not just the size of the model. Therefore, when choosing Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution, its advantages and limitations need to be considered comprehensively according to specific application scenarios and requirements.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a lightweight convolution called Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution is proposed for optimizing the Neck network part of the YOLOv8 model. This convolution allows the network to significantly reduce the computational effort and the number of parameters while effectively capturing the target features at different scales. In addition, we improve the bottleneck module using the lightweight convolution proposed in this paper and introduce the Coordinate Attention mechanism. This attention mechanism helps the model to better process the important information in the input sequence by focusing on the information and spatial features between the channels. In order to verify the effectiveness and robustness of Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution, experiments are conducted on different public datasets. The experimental results show that the improved model reduces the amount of computation and the number of parameters by about

one-tenth while ensuring better accuracy than the original model. This improved model can be applied not only in the field of public transportation, but also in the detection of defects or anomalies in industrial products. On the NEU-DET dataset, the improved model proposed in this paper also performs well, overall outperforming other detection models, and realizes high-precision and low-computation target detection, thus reducing labor costs and improving productivity.

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CEREBROVASCULAR ATLAS FROM MRA IMAGING OF 1336 SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to create a comprehensive statistical atlas of cerebral arteries to accurately capture variations among individuals and across different age groups. We utilized 1,336 publicly available multicenter magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) and T1-weighted MRI datasets, employing an automated blood vessel segmentation method, FFCM-MRF, to segment all blood vessels and measure their radii. Subsequently, the binary segmentation and vascular radius images were nonlinearly registered to the Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) brain template using the T1-weighted MRI dataset. This process resulted in the creation of atlases that illustrate the probability of arterial occurrence, the average arterial radius, and the standard deviation of the arterial radius. The constructed vascular statistical atlas effectively showcases the major arteries and, when integrated with the probability atlas and the average vessel radius atlas, indicates a significantly higher probability of larger arteries, which decreases as the vessel radius diminishes. This observation aligns with previous research findings, and the similarity between the probability atlas and individual vascular images reached as high as 0.9659. In conclusion, this atlas effectively covers arterial radius information across nearly the entire age range, enabling the identification of variations between individual arterial voxel radii and the population using this atlas, thereby providing an important reference for cerebral vascular research.

Keywords: Angiography, Cerebral vessels, Magnetic resonance imaging, statistical atlas.

INTRODUCTION

The brain is the central organ of the nervous system in humans and all vertebrates, and it is characterized by one of the most intricate tissue structures. Neuronal computation within the brain requires a substantial and continuous supply of energy, making it highly dependent on the vascular system for the continuous transport of nutrients and oxygen.

Changes in cerebrovascular structure are critical factors that influence various brain diseases. Common cerebrovascular disorders in humans include conditions such as cerebral arteriosclerosis, cerebrovascular stenosis, cerebral infarction, and aneurysms. Studies have shown that defects in the vascular network of the central nervous system are associated with early symptoms of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) (Iadecola *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, gaining a comprehensive understanding of the normal morphology and distribution of cerebral arteries is essential for improving disease detection.

Currently, most brain atlas studies primarily focus on representing and describing tissue types, as well as anatomical and functional brain regions. There is a notable lack of research on the morphology and distribution of cerebral arteries. Developing a cerebral artery atlas could help establish standard data for healthy individuals and facilitate the early detection of cerebrovascular abnormalities. In this study, we refer to the "statistical atlas" as a comprehensive representation of cerebrovascular structures, which includes both the vascular probability atlas (depicting the spatial distribution of vessels) and other statistical measures such as vessel radius distribution. A vascular probability atlas specifically highlights the likelihood of vessel presence in different regions, while the statistical atlas encompasses additional quantitative features to provide a more holistic view of cerebrovascular morphology.

(A) Linearly register T1-weighted images to TOF MRA images.

(B) Perform skull stripping and non-linear registration to MNI space.

(C) Map TOF-MRA images, expanded vessel radius images, vessel segmentation images, and tissue-to-vessel distance maps to MNI space.

Fig. 1. Statistical Atlas Generation Image Processing Pipeline

Previous studies have explored related topics. In 2003, a study constructed a vascular density map with 9 participants ($n = 9$) (Cool *et al.*, 2003), and in 2011, another study created an arteriovenous map using vascular information from 54 participants ($n = 54$) (Dufour *et al.*, 2011). However, the limited number of participants in these studies may significantly affect the results due to individual variability. Building on this, a 2013 study employed a dataset of 700 subjects (Forkert *et al.*, 2013); however, it relied solely on linear registration to standard space, which may not accurately align the data. In 2017, another study analyzed 167 MRA images (Dunås *et al.*, 2015), utilizing nonlinear registration to generate a probabilistic vascular map. Nevertheless, the age of the subjects in this study predominantly ranged from 64 to 68 years, which does not adequately represent the vascular structure and distribution across a broader age range. Although some previous vascular statistical atlases have included datasets with a broader age distribution, the sample sizes remain relatively small (Mouches *et al.*, 2019). This work aims to construct a comprehensive statistical arterial atlas using a larger sample size and diverse age groups, thereby providing a more accurate representation of cerebrovascular morphology and capturing individual variability.

Fig. 1 shows a diagram of the image processing pipeline used for this research, which is described in more detail below.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DATASETS

A total of 1443 datasets from healthy subjects were included. Among them, 78 datasets did not have T1-weighted MRI images, and the remaining datasets included high-resolution T1-weighted MRI and TOF MRA images, which were used to generate a human cerebral artery statistical atlas.

ADAM (<https://adam.isi.uu.nl>) is a dataset for the 2020 Aneurysm Detection and Segmentation Challenge, with 109 subjects in total, of which only 20 are healthy. The ICBM dataset (<https://ida.loni.usc.edu/>) has 192 healthy subjects in total, of which 4 were excluded due to lack of clinical information.

The CHUV dataset (<https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds003949/versions/1.0.1>), obtained from the University Hospital of Lausanne, consists of 284 subjects, including 127 healthy controls and 157 patients with cerebral aneurysms. The BraVa dataset (<http://cng.gmu.edu/brava/>) includes 56 healthy subjects. The 571

datasets from healthy subjects were downloaded from the IXI database (<http://brain-development.org>), which combines MRI collections from three different centers in London, UK. In the IXI dataset, all subjects were normal and healthy, and 19 of them were excluded without clinical information. The MIDAS dataset was collected and provided by CASILab at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC) and distributed by the MIDAS data server of Kitware, Inc. (<http://insight-journal.org/MIDAS/community/view/21>). A total of 109 subjects were included. Ten subjects were excluded due to a lack of clinical data, and another seven UNC

subjects were excluded due to incidental findings (such as ethmoid sinus polyps, micro-intubated acoustic tumors, epidermoid cysts, and micro-strokes). The MSC dataset (<https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds000224/versions/1.0.3>) includes scans of 10 subjects, each scanned four times, and we selected the results of one scan. OASIS3 (<https://www.oasis-brains.org>) is a longitudinal multimodal dataset that includes neuroimaging, clinical, cognitive, and biomarker data for normal aging and Alzheimer's disease. A total of 359 healthy subjects were included.

Table 1. Demographic information of the finally included subjects.

Center	n	Sex		Mean Age(range)
		M	F	
ADAM	20			
ICBM	174	73	101	42(19-80)
CHUV	106			
BraVa	56	21	35	31(19-64)
IXI-HH	176	86	90	47(20-82)
IXI-IOP	58	20	38	43(21-86)
IXI-Guys	294	128	166	50(20-86)
MIDAS	92	42	50	42(19-72)
MSC	10	5	5	29(24-34)
OASIS3	350			69(42-92)

Table 2. TOF MRA acquisition parameters

Center	Scanner	Magnetic field strength(T)	Voxel resolution (mm ³)	TR/TE (ms)	Flip angle (degrees)
ADAM	Philips	1.5/3	0.3571×0.3571×0.5000/ 0.3906×0.3906×0.5000	22/3.45	
ICBM	Siemens	1.5/3	0.6250×0.6250×0.6000/ 0.6187×0.6187×0.6200		
CHUV	Siemens/Philips	3	0.4688×0.4688×0.7000	22/3.95	18
BraVa	Siemens	3	0.6187×0.6187×0.6200	24/4.85	18
IXI-HH	Philips	3	0.4688×0.4688×0.8000	16.7/5.75	16
IXI-IOP	GE	1.5	0.2637×0.2637×0.8000		
IXI-Guys	Philips	1.5	0.4688×0.4688×0.8000		25
MIDAS	Siemens	3	0.5134×0.5134×0.8000		22
MSC	Siemens	3	0.6250×0.6250×1.0000	25/3.34	20
OASIS3	Siemens	3	0.2995×0.2995×0.6000		

After preprocessing, 67 additional datasets were deleted due to data quality problems. The images of these datasets contained severe artifacts that obscured the details of the blood vessels. These artifacts not only degraded the image quality but also compromised the accuracy and reliability of the subsequent analysis. Table 1 describes the demographic information of the remaining 1,336 datasets used to generate the atlases.

To utilize a more diverse set of datasets, those used in this study include various field strengths (1.5T and 3T), scanner types (Siemens and Philips), and acquisition parameters. The scanning parameters related to TOF-MRA are given in Table 2.

PRE-PROCESSING

In the first step of the preprocessing stage, skull stripping, denoising, and bias field correction are performed on MRA images. The BET function (Smith *et al.*, 2002) in FSL 6.0 was used to remove non-brain tissue from the human subjects' images. This preprocessing step is essential for enhancing the accuracy and reliability of subsequent analyses by eliminating potential noise and artifacts from non-brain regions. After skull removal, the images were carefully examined and, if necessary, manually edited using ITK-SNAP. Afterward, the `DenoiseImage` and `N4BiasFieldCorrection` functions in ANTs were used for denoising and bias field correction. To reduce the variability of the intensity distribution between scanners and subjects, histogram specification was used to normalize the images. Histogram specification is a technique employed to adjust the global contrast of an image by aligning its histogram with a target histogram. Before applying histogram specification, the input intracranial TOF-MRA data were convolved with a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ Gaussian kernel to enhance the continuity of grayscale values, as detailed in the reference (Zhang *et al.*, 2019).

In the second step, the FFCM-MRF (Cui *et al.*, 2024) method is used to segment blood vessels in the human dataset. Fast fuzzy c-means (FFCM) clustering is used for rough segmentation of blood vessels. Unlike traditional FCM, the FFCM is based on histograms rather than individual pixels to calculate the membership matrix and clustering center, thereby reducing the execution time of clustering. Due to noise in the coarse segmentation results, it is impossible to capture the vascular structure in low-contrast regions of the image. Therefore, it is necessary to construct the MRF model to further optimize the coarse segmentation results.

In the third step, the 3D centerline representation of each segmentation is calculated by Lee *et al.* (Lee *et al.*, 1994). Next, the distance transform described by

Danielsson (Danielsson *et al.*, 1994) is used to calculate the distance from each centerline voxel to the nearest non-vascular voxel, to define the radius of each centerline voxel. Then, a second distance transform is used to identify the nearest centerline voxel for each voxel within 6 mm of the centerline voxel. In this way, the radius value of the centerline voxel determined by the first distance transform is assigned to all non-centerline voxels that are closest to the centerline voxel and within 6 mm. At the same time, the binary image of blood vessel segmentation is used to calculate the distance from the tissue to the blood vessel. The binary image is inverted, with blood vessels marked as 0 and the background as 1. The distance from all voxels marked as 1 to the nearest 0 voxel is then calculated.

In the last step, each TOF MRA image, along with the corresponding blood vessel segmentation image, blood vessel radius image, and the distance image from the tissue to the blood vessel, was registered to the human standard space. The MNI (Mazziotta *et al.*, 2001) brain atlas with a resolution of 0.5 mm^3 was obtained. To generate a statistical atlas, the intensity-normalized TOF MRA atlas, corresponding vascular probability atlas, average radius, standard deviation atlas, and tissue-to-vessel distance atlas were all normalized to a common space.

The registration process is divided into two steps. The first step is to register the T1-weighted image, including the skull, to the corresponding TOF MRA image. Using image registration with the skull reduces the workload of skull removal and ensures consistent brain volume between the two images. Since the two images are from the same individual, a rigid transformation is used. The second step is to register the skull-stripped T1-weighted image from the TOFMRA space to the brain atlas in the standard space using nonlinear registration. ANTs (Avants *et al.*, 2001) with default parameters is used to complete the registration. For a small number of subjects without T1-weighted images, the TOF MRA was directly non-linearly registered to the MNI template. Finally, using the registration file from the second step, the TOF MRA image and the related vascular image are directly transformed to the standard space. Nearest neighbor interpolation is used to register the blood vessel segmentation image and the radius image to the standard space, while the intensity-normalized TOF MRA image is transformed to the atlas space using linear interpolation.

A total of five atlases were generated using the registered images: the TOF MRA intensity atlas, the vascular probability atlas representing the regions, the mean radius of the blood vessels, the standard deviation of the

blood vessel radius, and the corresponding statistical atlas of the distance from the tissue to the blood vessels (Fig. 2).

ATLAS GENERATION

The average intensity atlas of TOF MRA was constructed using the registered TOF MRA images. The voxel intensity in the atlas represents the average intensity of all the corresponding voxel positions after registration. Because the brain volume varies at different sites, a brain mask is used to limit the range of calculation to eliminate this influence. The distance atlas from tissue to blood vessel is also obtained using the same method.

The probability atlas of blood vessels is generated from the segmented images after registration. The atlas represents the probability of blood vessels at each voxel

position. Due to the varying brain volumes at different sites, TOF MRA scanning must be considered when calculating the probability of blood vessels. If the intensity value of TOF MRA is 0, the image is excluded from the probability calculation at that voxel position to prevent erroneous probability values.

Finally, the average vascular radius and the corresponding standard deviation at each voxel position are calculated using the registered arterial radius images. When calculating the vascular radius, the brain volumes of different images are also taken into account, and only the effective voxel positions are calculated. For a certain voxel position, the average of all non-zero values is calculated to determine the average vascular radius atlas for each voxel position. Finally, the standard deviation atlas of the vascular radius is calculated using the registered individual radius images and the average vascular radius atlas.

Fig. 2. Cerebroarterial statistical atlas. Selected slices from the artery probability atlas (A), the mean tissue-to-vessel distance (B), the mean artery radius atlas (C), and the standard deviation atlas (D) overlaid on the time-of-flight (TOF) MRA average atlas. The artery probabilities are presented as percentages, while the mean radius and its standard deviation are shown in millimeters (mm).

RESULTS

ANALYSIS OF STATISTICAL ATLAS

Visual and quantitative inspections of the generated atlas were performed. The atlas illustrated the major arteries (Fig. 2), indicating a higher probability of their presence. The probability of artery presence diminished as the vessel radius decreased, which aligns with previous research findings (Forkert *et al.*, 2013).

A quantitative analysis was performed on a specific region of interest, namely the vascular segment of the Circle of Willis. The highest probability was observed in the internal carotid artery (ICA), which reached 76%, with an average vessel radius of 1.9 mm. Due to variations in multi-site imaging conditions, the graph does not include the lower segment of the ICA. This measurement falls within the previously reported range of 1.25 to 3.5 mm by Saeki and Rhoton (Saeki & Rhoton, 1977).

The internal carotid artery bifurcates into the middle cerebral artery (MCA) and the anterior cerebral artery (ACA). The average radius of the middle cerebral artery

is approximately 1 mm, with a probability of 47%, as indicated in the probability atlas. In contrast, the average radius of the anterior cerebral artery is approximately 0.8 mm, with a probability of 50% in the same atlas. Previous studies have reported that the radius of the anterior cerebral artery ranges from 0.45 mm to 2 mm (Perlmutter *et al.*, 1976).

The basilar artery (BA) primarily serves the posterior circulation of the brain and bifurcates into the posterior cerebral artery (PCA). The probability of occurrence of the basilar artery is as high as 44%, with an average radius of 1.41 mm. Previous studies by Smoker *et al.* (1986) indicated a radius range for the BA of 0.8 mm to 3 mm. The average radius of the posterior cerebral artery (PCA) is approximately 0.65 mm, with a probability as high as 50% in the probability atlas. Previous studies reported a radius range for the P1 segment between 0.4 mm and 1.9 mm (Zeal *et al.*, 1978). The average distance map from tissue to vessels can effectively show the location of vessel distribution. When the distance from tissue to vessels is short, it indicates a high density of vessels in that area.

Fig. 3. Comparison of vascular morphology in 3T, 7T, and Alzheimer's Disease (AD) images.

DSC BETWEEN SEGMENTED VESSELS AND PROBABILITY ATLASES

The vessel probability atlas, used to represent the probability of vascular structures (Passat *et al.*, 2005),

can assist in vessel segmentation, aiding in the identification and extraction of vascular structures within images. To verify the practicality of the generated probability atlas compared to previous ones, vessel segmentation images from 20 subjects using 3T, AD, and 7T (Fig.

3) were utilized to assess the similarity between the vessel segmentation images and the vascular probability atlas. The 3T images are sourced from the ICBM, IXI, and OASIS3 datasets (which do not involve additional datasets for atlas generation), while the 7T images are obtained from the Forrest dataset (<https://www.studyforrest.org>). Compared to low-field strength magnetic resonance imaging, 7T MRI (Özütemiz *et al.*, 2024) shows significant improvements in resolution, sensitivity, signal quality, and precise diagnostic imaging, allowing for better visualization of distal large arteries and small vascular branches (Sun *et al.*, 2022). The artery probability atlas (2019) and the artery probability atlas generated in this study were registered to individual images, and the similarity between the individual vessel segmentation images and the two vascular probability atlases was calculated.

As shown in Table 3, for both 3T and higher-resolution 7T images, the artery probability atlas (2024) exhibits higher Dice similarity coefficients, indicating that this vascular probability map contains richer and more comprehensive vascular information. It can better generalize to different individual images, making it more suitable for vascular segmentation tasks. In the 3T images, cases 5 and 6 are from AD data, where vascular images of elderly individuals with AD tend to be more tortuous and irregular. However, the Dice similarity coefficient for the artery probability atlas (2024) for these individuals can reach as high as 0.9092, demonstrating that this probability atlas remains stable even when facing complex vascular structures.

Table 3. Compare the DSC between individual and different probability atlas

Magnetic field strength	Subject number	DSC(2019)	DSC(2024)
3T	1	0.8951	0.9488
	2	0.9040	0.9422
	3	0.8876	0.9675
	4	0.9130	0.9659
	5	0.8500	0.9092
	6	0.7710	0.8625
7T	7	0.7847	0.8388
	8	0.7682	0.8282
	9	0.7896	0.8533
	10	0.8600	0.9204
	11	0.7974	0.8641
	12	0.7647	0.7747
	13	0.7420	0.7981
	14	0.7679	0.8019
	15	0.8114	0.8747
	16	0.7018	0.7519
	17	0.8374	0.8935
	18	0.7847	0.8159
	19	0.7967	0.8554
	20	0.8146	0.8487

RADIUS ERROR BETWEEN INDIVIDUAL IMAGES AND MEAN ARTERY ATLASES

Due to the inherent differences in vascular structures among individuals of varying ages, this study compares the mean artery radius atlas (2019) and the mean artery radius atlas (2024) to assess the errors between them and individual radii. By registering the radius atlases to individual images, as shown in Fig. 4A, we calculated the differences between the individual radius and the corresponding mean radius atlas. A 3T MRA image of an elderly individual was selected for this

analysis, with results displayed in Fig. 4B. Panels a-c show the error visualization for the mean artery radius atlas (2019), while panels d-f illustrate the error visualization for the mean artery radius atlas (2024). Larger values indicate greater differences in radius at the corresponding voxel positions. Notably, in the ICA region, the values in the right image are significantly smaller, indicating that the mean artery radius atlas (2024) generated in this study aligns better with the morphology and structure of individual vessels, thereby reflecting the average vascular characteristics of the population more accurately.

Fig. 4. *Registration Process and Mean Radius Comparison.* (A) Illustrates the process of registering the mean radius atlas to individual subject images. (B) Presents a comparison of differences in artery radii: panels a-c show the discrepancies between the individual artery radius and the mean artery radius atlas from 2019, while panels d-f depict the discrepancies with the updated mean artery radius atlas from 2024. The color scale in each panel indicates the magnitude of radius differences, with warmer colors signifying larger discrepancies.

DISCUSSION

The size, shape, and distribution of individual blood vessels exhibit significant variation among individuals and are influenced by age. In this study, we utilized data from up to 10 sites, employing various field strengths and scanning devices, alongside a diverse age range of 1,336 subjects, to create a more comprehensive vascular statistical atlas.

Notably, the new vascular probability atlas demonstrated higher similarity in the Dice similarity coefficient (DSC) comparison, indicating its applicability across images of different individuals. This characteristic is particularly pronounced in images of elderly patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD), underscoring the stability of the new atlas in handling complex vascular structures.

However, due to discrepancies in scanning, not all datasets sufficiently captured the vessels at the base of the internal carotid artery (ICA), leading to the omission of some segments of these vessels in the generated atlas. Additionally, the current images are derived from 1.5T and 3T scanners, which do not adequately visualize the distal small vascular segments. In the future,

incorporating 7T imaging data could enhance the comprehensiveness of the vascular statistical atlas.

In conclusion, this study not only validates the effectiveness of the new vascular probability atlas but also offers valuable insights for future research directions. Subsequent studies could further investigate the differences in vascular characteristics among diverse populations. By incorporating emerging imaging technologies and advanced algorithms, researchers could enhance the accuracy of vascular segmentation, ultimately providing more precise support for clinical applications.

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UPORABA POLNADZOROVANEGA PRISTOPA MEAN TEACHER PRI SEGMENTACIJI SLIK KAMNIN

Jiashan Li and Yuxue Wang

Natančna segmentacija slik kamnin je ključna za proučevanje njihove notranje strukture in lastnosti. Za rešitev problema potrebe po velikem številu označenih slik za učenje modelov pri tradicionalnih metodah segmentacije slik predlagamo izboljšani polnadzorovani algoritem Mean Teacher, ki temelji na arhitekturi ResNet34-UNet. Ta metoda omogoča razmeroma natančno segmentacijo slik kamnin že z majhnim številom označenih podatkov. Najprej kot osnovni model uporabimo ResNet34-UNet za oblikovanje študentskega (Student Model) in učiteljskega modela (Teacher Model) z enakimi strukturami. Nato v polnadzorovani algoritem Mean Teacher uvedemo mehanizem samopozornosti, ki še dodatno izboljša učinkovitost segmentacije slik kamnin. Na koncu s primerjavo učinkovitosti nadzorovanega in polnadzorovanega algoritma Mean Teacher pri segmentaciji slik preverimo učinkovitost polnadzorovanega učenja pri segmentaciji slik kamnin.

Ključne besede: Segmentacija slik; ResNet; slika kamnin; samopozornost; polnadzorovano učenje; UNet.

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NAPOVED VIZUALNE IZKUŠNJE ZA ZGODOVINSKA OBMOČJA S FUZIJSKIM MODELOM CNN-TRANSFORMER

Weijia Wang, Youping Teng, Lu Yan, Longwei Wu, Yinying Yang, and Zijian Luo

Ta raziskava obravnava temeljne izzive pri načrtovanju in oblikovanju zgodovinskih območij, pri čemer se še posebej osredotoča na vključevanje emocionalne vrednosti podob mestnih ulic v oblikovalski proces. Razvili smo sistem za analizo sentimenta, temelječ na metodah globokega učenja, ki uporablja konvolucijsko nevronska mrežo (CNN) in modele transformer za ocenjevanje čustvenih tendenc in časovnih stanj v slikah. Sistem uporablja pristop večpoglednega ekstrahiranja značilk, ki integrira CNN modele VGG in ResNet ter model Swin Transformer, kar omogoča tvorbo nove matrice značilk. Mehanizem pozornosti in strategija prenesenega učenja občutno izboljšata natančnost modela pri prepoznavanju in klasifikaciji oznak. Glavni prispevek raziskave je razvoj novega multimodalnega fuzijskega modela, ki izrazito izboljša natančnost prepoznavanja sentimenta ter praktično uporabnost. Uporaba tega sistema na zgodovinskem območju Jiangnan poudarja izboljšanje privlačnosti z vključevanjem emocionalne vrednosti. S prepoznavanjem čustvenih tendenc v podobah mestnih ulic lahko oblikovalci sprejemajo boljše informirane odločitve, ki spodbujajo pozitivnost. Raziskava inovativno uvaja analizo sentimenta v načrtovanje zgodovinskih območij in izpostavlja potencial sistema za usmerjanje kulturno občutljivega in privlačnega urbanega načrtovanja. Naša analiza slik iz 12 zgodovinskih območij Jiangnana je pokazala učinkovitost sistema pri usklajevanju slik z obstoječimi knjižnicami podob ter omogočila dragocene reference in povratne informacije. Rezultati poudarjajo praktični potencial globokega učenja pri vizualni analizi sentimenta in pomembnost emocionalne vrednosti za izboljšanje uporabniških izkušenj v zgodovinskih

območjih. Raziskava nudi nova spoznanja in metodološko podporo za načrtovanje in oblikovanje takšnih območij.

Ključne besede: konvolucijska nevronska mreža (CNN); evalvacijski sistem; zgodovinska območja; analiza sentimenta; model transformer.

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UČINKOVITA SUPER-RESOLUCIJA SLIK Z VEČVEJNO MEŠALNO TRANSFORMER ARHITEKTURO

Long Zhang and Yi Wan

Metode globokega učenja so dosegle pomemben napredek na področju super-resolucije posamezne slike (single image super-resolution, SISR), pri čemer Transformer modeli pogosto prekašajo pristope, ki temeljijo na konvolucijskih nevronske mrežah (CNN). Zaradi mehanizma samopozornosti, ki ga uporabljajo Transformer modeli, pa ostaja izziv razvijanje preprostih modelov v primerjavi s CNN pristopi. V tej raziskavi predstavljamo preprst model Transformer z imenom »Multi-Branch Mixer Transformer« (MBMT), namenjen super-resoluciji. Oblika MBMT je osnovana na dveh glavnih ugotovitvah: mehanizem samopozornosti sicer učinkovito zajema dolgoročne odvisnosti v značilkah, vendar ima težave pri ekstrahiranju lokalnih značilk. Poleg tega kvadratna kompleksnost samopozornosti predstavlja bistveno oviro pri oblikovanju lahkih modelov. Za reševanje teh težav smo razvili »Multi-Branch Token Mixer« (MBTM), ki omogoča bogatejšo pridobivanje globalnih in lokalnih informacij. V primerjavi z drugimi Transformer mrežami za super resolucijo, MBTM dosega ravnovesje med zajemanjem globalnih informacij in zmanjšanjem računske kompleksnosti samopozornosti s svojo kompaktno večvejno strukturo. MBTM specifično vključuje tri dele: pozornost s premikajočim se oknom (shifted window attention), globinsko konvolucijo (depthwise convolution) in aktivni mešalnik značilk (active token mixer). Ta večvejna struktura hkrati obravnava dolgoročne odvisnosti in lokalne značilke, kar omogoča odlično učinkovitost pri super-resoluciji že z manjšim številom zloženih modulov. Eksperimentalni rezultati kažejo, da MBMT dosega konkurenčne rezultate in hkrati ohranja učinkovitost modela v primerjavi z najsoodnejšimi metodami.

Ključne besede: aktivni mešalnik značilk, večvejni mešalnik značilk, super-resolucija posamezne slike, Transformer

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RAZISKAVA METODE VIZUALNEGA ZAZNAVANJA NAPAK ODLEPLJENEGA LEPILA NA ZVOČNIH FILMIH

Jianchun Liu, Xunjin Jiang, Chaoqi Huang, and Yuquan Lin

Napaka odlepljanja lepila je pogosta napaka pri nanašanju lepila na zvočne filme. Zaradi težav, povezanih z nejasno mejo območja lepila, ki se pogosto pojavlja med postopkom zaznavanja, smo predlagali izboljšano iterativno metodo največje medrazredne variance za zaznavanje teh napak. Zaradi poševne porazdelitve sive krivulje zvočnega filma smo srednjo vrednost sivinskih vrednosti slike nadomestili s povprečno vrednostjo izboljšane iterativne metode, da smo odstranili ozadje zvočnega filma. Začetni prag območja nanašanja lepila je tako hitro konvergiralo. Metodo največje medrazredne variance smo

kombinirali za izboljšanje natančnosti zaznavanja mej območja lepila. Primerjali smo slikovne značilnosti različnih vrst napak – enojnih vrzeli, več vrzeli in dislokacij – pri kakovostnih in okvarjenih izdelkih ter izračunali število in odmik območij lepila za natančno prepoznavanje napak. Za testiranje smo na proizvodni liniji naključno izbrali 15.000 izdelkov, pri čemer so rezultati pokazali, da je bila zaznavna natančnost kakovostnih izdelkov 100 %, zaznavna natančnost napak odlepljenega lepila pa 99,1 %, kar ustreza potrebam podjetij.

Ključne besede: napaka odlepljenega lepila, izboljšana iteracija, metoda največje medrazredne variance, pragovna segmentacija

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KLASIFIKACIJA ODTISOV DLANI Z VEČ FILTRI, FOURIERJEVIMI ZNAČILKAMI IN TEHNIKO GLASOVANJA

Guang Yi Chen and Adam Krzyzak

V tem članku predlagamo novo metodo klasifikacije odtisov dlani. Iz slike odtisa dlani ekstrahiramo osrednjo regijo, iz nje izračunamo osem obraznih filtrov (filter faces – FF) na podlagi osmih parov filtrov, nato iz vsakega filtra izračunamo Fourierjeve značilke, vsako od teh značilk klasificiramo v enega od znanih razredov, na koncu pa izvedemo večinsko glasovanje za določitev končne oznake razreda neznanega odtisa dlani. Z analizo strukture izbranih filtrov lahko ugotovimo, da naša nova metoda učinkovito zavira naključni šum in hkrati ekstrahira smerne značilke iz slik odtisov dlani. To je glavni razlog, zakaj so metode, ki temeljijo na FF, boljše od ostalih metod. Poleg tega pristop večinskega glasovanja, ki temelji na osmih filtrih, bistveno izboljša klasifikacijsko natančnost. Eksperimentalni rezultati potrjujejo, da naša nova metoda presega več obstoječih metod za klasifikacijo odtisov dlani.

Ključne besede:

obrazni filter, tehnika večinskega glasovanja, prepoznavanje odtisov dlani, hitra Fourierjeva transformacija

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MOZAIK SLIK NA PODLAGI LOKALNEGA VODENJA IN PRISTOPA TEMNEGA KANALA

Chong Zhang, Fang Xu, Dejiang Wang, and He Sun

Mozaik slik ima pomembno vlogo na različnih področjih, kot sta sledenje objektom in izvidništvo z brezpilotnimi letalniki. Za izboljšanje težav, kot sta slabša zmogljivost in velika stopnja napačnih ujemanj pri meglenih slikah, je v tem delu predlagana izboljšana metoda sestavljanja slik na osnovi lokalno vodenega algoritma KAZE in pristopa temnega kanala. Najprej smo za grobo ujemanje značilk uporabili algoritem KAZE. Nato smo uvedli lokalno asimptotično metodo fiksne točke, ki optimizira globalni cilj in izloči napačne pare točk. S pomočjo ocenjene matrike transformacije pridobimo popačene slike. Sledi kompenzacija razlik v barvi in svetlosti na področju prekrivanja, kar izboljša homogenost sestavljene slike. Na koncu smo končni rezultat dosegli z algoritmom izboljšanja na osnovi pristopa temnega kanala. Predlagani algoritem smo ocenili z intuitivnimi renderji in kvantitativnimi vrednostmi ter primerjali z drugimi običajnimi metodami sestavljanja slik. Rezultati kažejo, da predlagana metoda izkazuje boljšo zmogljivost glede števila ujemaajočih se parov značilk, povprečne absolutne napake, korena povprečne kvadratne napake in časa obdelave.

Ključne besede: temni kanal, mozaik slik, KAZE, lokalno vodenje

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IZBOLJŠAVA DETEKCIJE OBJEKTOV Z YOLOV8 NA PODLAGI MODELA LAHKEGA VRATU ZA KOMPLEKSNE SLIKE

Tien-Wen Sung, Jie Li, Chao-Yang Lee, and Qingjun Fang

Z napredkom tehnologije detekcije tarč postaja natančno zaznavanje v kompleksnih slikah vse pomembnejše za različne panoge, kar ne le izboljšuje produktivnost, temveč tudi zagotavlja javno varnost. Vendar imajo trenutni glavni algoritmi za detekcijo tarč težave pri obravnavi kompleksnih slik; na primer, nekateri modeli ne omogočajo zaznavanja v realnem času, natančnost modela pa se zmanjša ob motečih dejavnikih, kot sta zakritost tarče in slike z nizkim kontrastom. Da bi omilili te težave, predlagamo lahko konvolucijo LDGConv (angl. Lightweight-DepthGhost Convolution), ki izboljša YOLOv8 mrežni model z zamenjavo dela tradicionalnih konvolucij v vratu mreže s konvolucijo LDGConv ter izboljša modul, ki predstavlja ozko grlo. Poleg tega v del vratu dodajamo mehanizem koordinatne pozornosti (angl. Coordinate Attention). Predlagani model izboljša mAP50 na VOC podatkovnem naboru za 1,3 %, hkrati pa zmanjša izračune in število parametrov za 9,8 % oziroma 15,3 % v primerjavi z izvirnim modelom. V eksperimentih na podatkovnem naboru napak na površini jekla NEU-DET naš model na splošno presega trenutne glavne detekcijske modele. Model omogoča visoko natančno detekcijo tarč z nizkimi računskimi stroški, kar posledično zmanjšuje stroške dela ter izboljšuje javno zdravje, varnost in produktivnost.

Ključne besede: lahka zasnova, mehanizem pozornosti, detekcija tarč, vrat mreže

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ATLAS MOŽGANSKIH ARTERIJ NA PODLAGI MRA-SLIK 1336 OSEB

Xinyu Wang, Jialu Liu, and Xiaoping Lou

Namen te raziskave je bil izdelati celovit statistični atlas možganskih arterij, ki natančno zajema variabilnost med posamezniki in med različnimi starostnimi skupinami. Uporabili smo 1336 javno dostopnih multicentričnih podatkovnih nizov magnetnoresonančne angiografije (MRA) in T1-uteženih MRI-slik, kjer smo s pomočjo avtomatizirane metode segmentacije krvnih žil FFCM-MRF segmentirali vse žile ter izmerili njihove polmere. Nato smo binarno segmentacijo in slike z žilnimi polmeri nelinearno registrirali na vzorec možganov Montrealskega nevrološkega inštituta (MNI) z uporabo T1-uteženih MRI-slik. Ta postopek je omogočil izdelavo atlasov, ki prikazujejo verjetnost pojava arterij, povprečni polmer arterij in standardni odklon njihovega polmera. Ustvarjeni statistični žilni atlas učinkovito prikazuje glavne arterije, pri čemer združitve z verjetnostnim atlasom in atlasom povprečnih žilnih polmerov razkrije izrazito višjo verjetnost večjih arterij, ki se zmanjšuje z manjšanjem polmera žil. Ta ugotovitev je skladna s predhodnimi raziskavami, podobnost med verjetnostnim atlasom in posameznimi žilnimi slikami pa je dosegla vrednost kar 0,9659. Ugotovljamo, da atlas celostno zajema podatke o polmerih arterij v skoraj celotnem starostnem razponu, s čimer omogoča identifikacijo razlik med posameznimi arterijskimi vokslji in populacijskim povprečjem ter predstavlja pomembno referenco za raziskave možganskega žilja.

Ključne besede: angiografija, možganske žile, slikanje z magnetno resonanco, statistični atlas

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